

Zašto neki političari, novinari i zdravstveni djelatnici zagovaraju cijepljenje djece protiv covid-19?

Petar Gabrić^{a, 1}, doktorand (dr. rer. med.)

^aKlinika za psihijatriju i psihoterapiju, Medicinski fakultet, Philippsovo Sveučilište u Marburgu, Marburg, Njemačka

Sažetak

U hrvatskim je medijima sve više govora o cijepljenju djece protiv covid-19, unatoč maloj ulozi djece u prijenosu novog koronavirusa i njihovom malom riziku od teških simptoma, postojanju drugih oblika prevencije, činjenici da klinička ispitivanja nisu dovršena, raznih problema u provedenim ispitivanjima i rastućoj zabrinutosti oko sigurnosti cjepiva i mogućih štetnih učinaka. Cilj je ovog kratkog pregleda odabrane znanstvene literature potaknuti kvalitetnu javnu raspravu prije donošenja potencijalno ishitrenih odluka.

Ključne riječi: medicinska etika; zaraza; nuspojava; medicinska metodologija; pedijatrija; bioetika

1. Uvod

Nalazimo se u 22. mjesecu otkako je Svjetska zdravstvena organizacija proglasila pandemiju bolesti covid-19 [1]. Podaci trenutno sugeriraju da pacijenti dijagnosticirani s covid-19 imaju relativno nizak rizik od razvijanja srednjeg ili teškog oblika bolesti te da je dijagnoza covid-19 povezana s niskom stopom smrtnosti [2–6]. Ipak, rizik od razvijanja teškog oblika bolesti i stopa smrtnosti povećani su u određenim dijelovima populacije kao što su starije osobe i osobe s komorbiditetima kod kojih covid-19 može dovesti do pogoršanja postojećih kardiovaskularnih, metaboličkih, dišnih i drugih poremećaja [7–17], a istraživanja pokazuju da covid-19 može biti povezan s pojavom raznih patoloških procesa [18–31]. Unatoč covid-19, razne druge medicinske pojave imaju dalekosežne posljedice za javno zdravstvo kao što su srčane bolesti, moždani udar, rak, kronične opstruktivne plućne bolesti, prometne i druge nesreće, dijabetes, depresija, alkoholizam, pretilost, kratkovidnost, lošiji socio-ekonomski status itd. [32–47]. Podaci trenutno pokazuju i da je smrtnost od covid-19 oko sto puta manja od smrtnosti od španjolske gripe [48].

2. Cijepljenje djece protiv COVID-19

2.1. Cjepiva bez presedana

¹ *Korespondencija:* gabric@staff.uni-marburg.de; petar.gabric@protonmail.com

Trenutno se u Hrvatskoj provodi velika i naizgled žurna kampanja četirima cjepivima proizvođača Pfizer-BioNTech, Moderna, Janssen (Johnson & Johnson) i AstraZeneca. Proizvodi Pfizera i Moderne tzv. su mRNA-cjepiva. Ukratko, ta cjepiva koriste lipidne nanočestice u kojima je smješten onaj isječak ribonukleinske kiseline (RNK) koji kodira tzv. šiljasti protein (eng. *spike protein*) virusa SARS-CoV-2. Laičkim riječima, ljudski organizam virusnu RNK iz mRNA-cjepiva pri dolasku u stanicu prepoznaje kao ljudsku RNK, omogućujući joj tako da prenese uputu ljudskoj stanici da proizvodi šiljaste proteine virusa SARS-CoV-2, čemu slijedi imunosni odgovor organizma na navedene šiljaste proteine i, u očekivanom raspletu, stvaranje antitijela protiv tog specifičnog šiljastog proteina. Cjepiva proizvođača Janssen i AstraZeneca koriste drugačiju tehnologiju temeljenu na tehnologiji vektora virusne DNK u kojoj se koristi oslabljeni adenovirus (virus koji je jedan od uzročnika prehlade) pri čemu je genom adenovirusa genetski modificiran uvećanjem za isječak DNK-a koji kodira već spomenuti šiljasti protein virusa SARS-CoV-2. Dakle, u obama tipovima kandidata za cjepivo radi se o injekciji genetskog materijala virusa SARS-CoV-2 koji kodira spomenuti šiljasti protein i cilj je da ljudske stanice počnu proizvoditi te šiljaste proteine [49–53].

Niz je pojava vezano uz navedena cjepiva bez presedana. Ovo je:

- (1) prvi pokušaj da se koristi tehnologija mRNA-cjepiva za borbu protiv nekog uzročnika zaraze,
- (2) prvi put da se neki pripravak koristi kao cjepivo samo na temelju preliminarnih analiza o učinkovitosti,
- (3) prvo cijepljenje za koje ne postoje jasni pokazatelji o smanjenju zaraza, prenosivosti i smrtnosti,
- (4) prvi put da zdravstveni djelatnici javnosti govore da su nuspojave očekivane i/ili dobre,
- (5) prva uporaba polietilenskog glikola u injekciji,
- (6) prvo cijepljenje protiv nekog koronavirusa,
- (7) prva injekcija genetski modificiranih polinukleotida u općoj populaciji
- (8) i prvi put da je Moderna na tržište uspjela izbaciti bilo koji proizvod [49].

U nekim dijelovima svijeta već se naveliko krenulo i s cijepljenjem djece (< 17 god.) [54–59], a najavljuje se i cijepljenje novorođenčadi i djece mlađe od pet godina [60, 61]. Negdje se već najavljuje obavezno cijepljenje djece protiv covid-19 [62, 63]; u Austriji trenutni prijedlog zakona s kojim se slažu i vladajuće i oporbene političke stranke predviđa obvezu cijepljenja starijih od 13 godina od veljače 2022. [64], a raspravlja se i o uvođenju obaveze cijepljenja i za mlađe [65]; u Njemačkoj se raspravlja o uvođenju trajnih potkožnih “čipova” kako bi se “uopće znalo tko se nije cijepio” [66–68]. Neke institucije predviđaju da će proglašena pandemija trajati još 5–10 godina te da će biti potrebno kontinuirano cijepljenje, možda i svaka tri do četiri mjeseca [69–72]. Nedavno su i neki hrvatski političari, novinari i zdravstveni djelatnici počeli govoriti o cijepljenju djece, pri čemu se većinom susrećemo s pozivima na cijepljenje djece ili pozitivnim stavovima o cijepljenju djece. Primjerice, pedijatričarka Iva Mihatov Štefanović je u informativnoj emisiji HRT-a već u listopadu 2021. dala svoju preporuku o cijepljenju djece, bez jasnih argumenata, i izjavila “Ja ću i svoje dijete cijepiti.” [73] dok je trenutni predsjednik Zoran Milanović, također bez jasnih argumenata, izjavio “Djeca moraju biti u školi i djeca bi se trebala cijepiti.”, također u listopadu 2021. [74]. U naizgled sudbonosnom se listopadu i novinarka portala *Index.hr* Martina Pauček Šljivak pozabavila temom cijepljenja djece pitajući se u naslovu članka “Može li nas spasiti cijepljenje djece?” [75]. Ne nedostaju listopadni blagoslovi Krunoslava Capka i Alemke Markotić, dviju trenutno prominentnih ličnosti u hrvatskoj javnosti [75]. Ovakav način raspravljanja u javnosti o osjetljivom pitanju kao što je inokulacija

djece kandidatima za cjepiva za koje postoji niz ozbiljnih, a neodgovorenih pitanja začuđujući te je bio poticaj za istraživanje (odabrane) literature i pisanje teksta koji čitate.

Unatoč postojanju ozbiljnih pitanja u vezi učinkovitosti i sigurnosti trenutnih kandidata za cjepivo protiv covid-19, hrvatski mediji u svojem izvještavanju gotovo uvijek ističu pozitivne učinke trenutnih kandidata, zanemarujući ključna pitanja i zanemarujući mnoštvo istraživanja i rasprava objavljenih u znanstvenoj literaturi. To sugerira da mnogi hrvatski građani također nisu upoznati s informacijama iz navedenih znanstvenih publikacija budući da novinarstvo djeluje kao posrednik između znanstvenika i ostalih koji ne mogu samostalno čitati i razumjeti često zamršene i komplicirane znanstvene tekstove. Razlog jednostranosti medijskog izvještavanja i raspravljavanja zdravstvenih djelatnika i političara nije jasan. I od novinara i zdravstvenih djelatnika očekivalo bi se da će u raspravama o zdravstvenim temama nastojati obuhvatiti sve postojeće informacije na temelju kojih će donijeti sintetski zaključak. Vrijeme je u trenutno proglašenoj pandemiji da se rasprave počnu temeljiti na jasnim i detaljnim informacijama, informacijama iz različitih i brojnih izvora, provjerljivim informacijama te informacijama koje na ovaj ili onaj način zadovoljavaju visoke znanstvene kriterije.

U nastavku teksta osvrnut ću se na neka ključna i ozbiljna pitanja u vezi s učinkovitosti i sigurnosti trenutnih kandidata za cjepivo. U kratkim riječima, pitanja se svode na:

- (1) činjenicu da djeca ograničeno sudjeluju u prijenosu novog koronavirusa i nemaju izražen rizik od teškog oblika bolesti i smrti,
- (2) činjenicu da postoje i drugi oblici prevencije od zaraze novim koronavirusom,
- (3) činjenicu da klinička ispitivanja nisu dovršena,
- (4) nepostojanje adekvatnih kliničkih ispitivanja učinkovitosti i sigurnosti trenutnih kandidata za cjepivo te postojanje raznih metodoloških nejasnoća u provedenim preliminarnim ispitivanjima,
- (5) postojanje pokazatelja o pogreškama i prikrivanju pogrešaka tijekom preliminarnih kliničkih ispitivanja
- (6) i velik broj preliminarnih opservacijskih istraživanja koja pokazuju da inokulacija nekim od kandidata za cjepivo može biti povezana s raznolikim i ozbiljnim štetnim učincima na zdravlje koji nisu bili očekivani na temelju preliminarnih kliničkih ispitivanja koja su proveli proizvođači.

2.2. Djeca ograničeno sudjeluju u prijenosu novog koronavirusa i nemaju izražen rizik od teškog oblika bolesti i smrti

Dosadašnje su analize postigle sporazum da djeca imaju minimalan rizik od razvijanja srednjeg ili teškog oblika bolesti i smrti [37, 50, 1042–1064], čak i u slučaju postojanja ozbiljnih komorbiditeta [1048, 1064], te pokazuju da djeca imaju veću vjerojatnost da ih zarazi roditelj ili nastavnik nego da djeca zaraze roditelja ili nastavnika [37, 50, 1043, 1048, 1065–1067]. Primjerice, u jednom je istraživanju na oko 17 000 njemačke djece iz više od sto škola u razdoblju od šest tjedana utvrđeno tek devetnaest pozitivnih PCR-testova od ukupno 100 000 provedenih testova (0.00019 %) [1051].

2.3. Postoje i drugi oblici prevencije

Budući da je pretpostavljeni cilj cijepljenja djece protiv covid-19 smanjenje njihovog rizika od razvijanja teškog oblika bolesti i/ili smrti, očekivano bi bilo da će se prije takve odluke provesti široka stručna rasprava

o načinima prevencije covid-19 kod djece. Takva se rasprava u javnosti prema mojim saznanjima nije dogodila. Nejasno je zašto ako istraživanja pokazuju da postoji niz drugih mogućih intervencija koje mogu smanjiti rizik od zaraze i težinu simptoma covid-19 [76–85], uključujući izlaganje sunčevoj svjetlosti i povećanje unosa vitamina D [15, 79, 86–115], vitamina A [79, 92, 95, 116, 117], vitamina B [79, 92], vitamina C [7, 79, 92, 94, 118, 119], vitamina E [79, 92, 95], vitamina K [90, 95, 120], nekih minerala poput cinka, bakra, željeza, magnezija, mangana, natrija i selenija [79, 83–85, 92, 94, 108], konzumiranje organske hrane umjesto procesuirane hrane bogate kemikalijama [92, 121–123], konzumiranje organskog češnjaka, sjemenki crnjike, đumbira, brusnice, naranče, kurkume, ehinaceje, propolisa, soje, zelenog čaja i maslačka [83, 84, 92, 94, 124–126], unošenje probiotika [120, 125, 127] te omega-3 i -6 masnih kiselina [92]. Primjerice, jedno je istraživanje pretpostavilo da je razina vitamina D3 u krvi od 50 ng/mL povezana sa stopom smrtnosti od 0 % [87]. Povećanje fizičke aktivnosti i tjelovježbe također može doprinijeti prevenciji, primjerice u kontekstu prekomjerne težine i pretilosti kao rizičnih faktora od zaraze i razvijanja težih simptoma i raznih drugih medicinskih pojava vezanih uz manjak fizičke aktivnosti [100, 128–131]. Gradovi bi naprimjer mogli nastojati smanjiti toksično onečišćenje zraka i izlaganje ljudi elektromagnetskom zračenju koji mogu povećati rizik od zaraze i pogoršati simptome [123, 132–139].

Nejasno je zašto ne postoje kampanje za navedene preventivne mjere i nejasno je zašto javne zdravstvene ličnosti ignoriraju cijelu povijest znanja o borbi protiv zaraznih bolesti. Na *Službenoj stranici Vlade za pravodobne i točne informacije o koronavirusu* se kao jedina alternativa cjepivu navodi “lijek” koji, prema Vladi, “za sad ne postoji [...] i teško da će biti dostupan u skorije vrijeme” [140].

2.4. Klinička ispitivanja nisu dovršena

Činjenica jest da klinička ispitivanja trenutnih kandidata nisu dovršena. Primjerice, Pfizer trenutno predviđa da će ispitivanja njihovog kandidata biti završena 2. svibnja 2023. (nakon prvotno 31. siječnja 2023.) dok Moderna predviđa završetak ispitivanja 27. listopada 2022. Stoga nije jasno čemu žurba s cijepljenjem djece [141, 142].

Navedena dvo- do trogodišnja trajanja kliničkih ispitivanja već su ionako drastično ubrzana radi pretpostavljene izvanredne zdravstvene situacije [49, 50]. U publikaciji iz 2018. koju je sponzorirala Fundacija Billa i Melinde Gates navodi se razlika između triju tipova cjepiva: *jednostavna cjepiva*, *složena cjepiva* i *cjepiva bez presedana*. Cjepiva bez presedana odnose se na cjepiva protiv bolesti ili tipa bolesti za koji dosad nisu postojala adekvatna cjepiva i cjepiva razvijena na novim tehnologijama. Navedena publikacija procjenjuje da je za razvoj uspješnog cjepiva bez presedana potrebno 12.5 godina te da kandidati imaju 5 % šansi da prođu fazu 2 testiranja (procjena učinkovitosti) te 2 % da prođu i fazu 2 i fazu 3 (procjena koristi za populaciju) [143]. Ti su podaci zabrinjavajući ako uzmemo u obzir činjenicu da su neka od trenutnih cjepiva započela s distribucijom nakon svega šest mjeseci od registracije kliničkog ispitivanja [154].

2.5. Manjak ispitivanja i metodološke nejasnoće u provedenim kliničkim ispitivanjima

Primarni povod za poticanje ljudi na cijepljenje protiv covid-19 bile su objave primarnih analiza učinkovitosti koje su proveli proizvođači, a koje su iznjedrile rezultate o učinkovitosti kandidata oko i iznad 90 % injekcije dviju doza (tj. u prvih nekoliko tjedana nakon druge doze). Primjerice, Pfizerovo je ispitivanje provedeno na 37 706 ispitanika, 18 860 u skupini koja je primila kandidata za cjepivo te 18 846

u skupini koja je primila placebo. U skupini s cjepivom zabilježeno je 8 slučajeva covid-19, a u skupini s placeboom 162. Rezultat od 95 % dobiven je na temelju jednostavne jednadžbe $E = 100 \times (1 - IRR)$, pri čemu E označava učinkovitost (eng. *efficacy*), a IRR omjer stopa prisutnosti covid-19 u skupini s cjepivom u usporedbi sa skupinom s placeboom [144]. Osim izračunatih 95 % učinkovitosti, ne postoji ni jedan drugi pokazatelj o učinkovitosti kandidata u tom istraživanju. Ova je računica problematična iz nekoliko razloga.

- (1) Za medicinska je i druga istraživanja neobično da se u analizi velikog uzorka ne provode tzv. inferencijske statističke analize kojima bi se ispitala vjerojatnost istinitosti neke hipoteze (npr. hipoteze da je Pfizerov kandidat u usporedbi s placeboom učinkovit u sprečavanju zaraze itd.). To priznaju i sami autori istraživanja: “Rezultati su deskriptivni i nisu temeljeni na testiranju formalnih statističkih hipoteza.” [144].
- (2) Iz kratkog opisa ispitanika gore je jasno da je istraživanje provedeno u populaciji u kojoj je novi koronavirus kolao u tek vrlo ograničenim količinama (0.009 % u placebo-skupini). Analizom takvog uzorka teško se može kvalitetno zaključivati u učinkovitosti kandidata. Ako i pretpostavimo da ta stopa covid-19 odražava stvarnu sliku te da je proizvođač s time računao, uzorak je trebao biti puno veći da bi se mogli uočiti nekakvi učinci kao što je to i inače slučaj kada se istražuju rijetke pojave [145–148].
- (3) Dizajn Pfizerovog kliničkog ispitivanja bio je iz nekog razloga takav da se niti ne može zaključivati o učinkovitosti kandidata na sprečavanje zaraze, smanjenje prijenosa te smanjenje broja hospitalizacija i smrti. To je zato što je jedina varijabla korištena za mjerenje učinkovitosti bila *prisutnost simptomske covid-19* (potvrđenog PCR-testom). Uopće nije jasno zašto Pfizer nije izvjestio i o zaraznosti ispitanika te broju ispitanika koji su bili hospitalizirani zbog covid-19 ili su od njega preminuli. Jedino što se iz tog istraživanja, dakle, da zaključiti, i to samo ako pretpostavimo da je učinkovitost kandidata adekvatno proučena, jest da Pfizerov kandidat smanjuje broj simptomskih slučajeva (uključujući blage slučajeve, npr. samo kašalj). Pfizer nije niti izvjestio o težini simptoma koju su imali pojedini ispitanici s covid-19 pa ne možemo zaključivati ni koje to simptome točno i u kojoj mjeri Pfizerov kandidat može potisnuti [145]. S obzirom na navedeno, i ako ponovno pretpostavimo da je učinkovitost adekvatno analizirana, možemo jedino zaključiti da Pfizerov kandidat ima određeni terapijski učinak, a ne možemo zaključivati ima li preventivan učinak. Pokušava znatizelju da su neki javni zdravstveni djelatnici u medijima pogrešno tvrdili da se varijabla *prisutnost simptomske covid-19* odnosi samo na slučajeve s teškom (najvišom) razinom simptoma [149–151].
- (4) Barem je dvoje autora kritiziralo odabir načina računanja učinkovitosti kandidata koji predstavlja računicu relativnog smanjenja rizika (tj. ne uzima se u obzir koliko ispitanika nije imalo simptomske covid-19). Računanjem apsolutnog smanjenja rizika na temelju objavljenih podataka dobivaju se mnogo niže vrijednosti učinkovitosti kandidata, primjerice za Pfizer 0.7 %, a za Modernu 1.1 % [152, 153].
- (5) Distribucija dobnih skupina u Pfizerovom uzorku također je problematična. Za ispitivanje kandidata za cjepivo za očekivati bi bilo da će uzorak biti najvećim dijelom sačinjen od ljudi u onoj skupini koja je najviše pogođena bolešću protiv koje se razvija cjepivo – u slučaju covid-19 ciljne skupine su starije osobe i osobe s komorbiditetima. Čudi stoga da je, na temelju dostupnih podataka, tek oko 22 % ispitanika bilo u dobi iznad 65 godina. Nadalje, za ispitivanja su primljene samo zdrave osobe i osobe “sa stabilnim kroničnim zdravstvenim stanjima” (uz nedostatan pojašnjenje kriterija za potonju skupinu). Budući da cjepiva mogu imati manju učinkovitost kod starijih osoba

i osoba s određenim bolestima, što je potvrđeno drugim istraživanjima i za trenutne kandidate, ovaj uzorak ne može dati odgovore na pitanja o učinkovitosti (i sigurnosti) kandidata u tim posebnim populacijama [50].

- (6) Nažalost, buduća randomizirana klinička ispitivanja koja bi ispitivala učinkovitost i sigurnost kandidata na dulja razdoblja i/ili ispravila prethodne pogreške praktički više nisu moguća jer su svi proizvođači ispitanicima u placebo-skupini već ponudili inokulaciju svojim kandidatom. Dosad je samo Moderna objavila koliki je broj ispitanika u placebo-skupini primio barem jednu dozu cjepiva: 98 % [154].
- (7) Značajnija pobuđuju i neka druga pitanja. Primjerice, zašto je Pfizer iz analiza isključio 3 410 slučajeva kod kojih je postojala “sumnja u covid-19” te zašto ni Pfizer ni Moderna o tome nisu izvijestili u publikacijama i dokumentima prosljeđenima zdravstvenim institucijama koje njihove kandidate odobravaju za uporabu [147, 148]? Slično nisu izvijestili da je kod 477 ispitanika (nepoznato koliko u kojoj skupini) postojala “sumnja u covid-19”, a da ti ispitanici iz nepoznatog razloga nisu bili podvrgnuti PCR-testiranju [155]. Što se dogodilo s 371 ispitanikom koji je isključen iz analiza zbog “važnih devijacija u protokolu u prvih sedam dana od primanja druge doze”? Zašto je ih je bilo disproporcionalno više u skupini s cjepivom (311) u usporedbi s placebo-skupinom (60) [147]? Nije jasno o kakvim se “devijacijama” radi, a uobičajeno je za znanstvena istraživanja da se isključenja ispitanika brojačano i detaljno opišu. S obzirom na malen broj slučajeva u studiji (170), isključenja i uključivanja malog broja ispitanika iz analiza ili u analize mogu dramatično promijeniti rezultate računanja učinkovitosti. Kako je Pfizer tijekom svojeg ispitivanja uspio zabilježiti devet slučajeva ponovne zaraze novim koronavirusom, u trenutku kada je u svijetu bio poznat, u najboljem slučaju, 31 slučaj ponovne zaraze [147]? Zašto je Pfizerov protokol predvidio mogućnost neizravnog izlaganja cjepivu (izravno je inokulacijom)? Specifično, u protokolu je bilo naznačeno da se izlaganje cjepivu u trudnoći moralo javiti odgovornoj osobi u roku od 24 sata te se među načinima izlaganja navodi i “izlaganje iz okoliša” koje uključuje izlaganje “udisanjem ili kožnim kontaktom”, a predviđena je mogućnost i dviju razina neizravnog izlaganja: “Muški član obitelji ili pružatelj zdravstvenih usluga koji je izložen studijskoj intervenciji [cjepivu] udisanjem ili kožnim kontaktom izloži svoju partnericu prije ili oko vremena začeca.” (67.–68. str.) [156]. Nejasno je i zašto su se proizvođači odlučili u svojim pripravcima koristiti samo genetski materijal koji kodira šiljasti protein kad se u prethodnim istraživanjima na miševima pokazalo da se adekvatni imunski odgovor događa samo s cjepivima protiv covid-19 koja sadrže genetski materijal koji uz šiljasti protein kodira i tzv. proteine M i E novog koronavirusa, a da cjepivo temeljeno samo na šiljastom proteinu ne donosi gotovo nikakav imunski odgovor (jedno od istraživanja provela je Moderna) [157, 158]. Brojna pitanja trenutno odjekuju u prazno i ostaju bez adekvatnih odgovora proizvođača.
- (8) Nažalost, proizvođači su objavili tek vrlo malo podataka o trenutnim ispitivanjima i nije jasno kada će i hoće li podaci u potpunosti biti dostupni javnosti. Razlog tajnovitosti nije jasan. S obzirom da su ti podaci nužni za provjeru dosad objavljenih podataka o učinkovitosti i sigurnosti te proširenje našeg znanja o samim cjepivima, skupina znanstvenika skupljenih pod nazivom Javno zdravstvo i medicinari za transparentnost (eng. *Public Health and Medical Professionals for Transparency*) tužila je američku Upravu za hranu i lijekove (eng. FDA prema *Food and Drug Administration*) koja je pak od suda zatražila vremensko razdoblje od 55 godina za objavu potpunih podataka što bi značilo da bi podaci javnosti mogli biti dostupni tek 2076. godine. Kao razlog tako dugačkog razdoblja Uprava je navela manjak radne snage za obradu zahtjeva [159, 160].

Navedeni argumenti nisu zaustavili Nenada Jarića Dauenhauera, novinara portala *Index.hr*, da izjavi: “[Pfizerovo cjepivo] je postalo jedno od *najprovjerenijih*² koja su ikada dobila potpuno odobrenje.” [161].

Važno je imati na umu da navedene metodološke nejasnoće i propusti otvaraju pitanja i o sigurnosti cjepiva. Mnogo je znanstvenika izrazilo zabrinutost zbog slabe kvalitete provedenih istraživanja i nedostupnosti velikog broja podataka o ispitanicima, mnogi i u kontekstu sigurnosti cjepiva [49, 50, 52, 145–148, 152–154, 162–212, 824–833].

Iz navedenih je točaka jasno da je na temelju postojećih podataka teško raspravljati o učinkovitosti trenutnih kandidata za cjepivo, bili oni u stvarnosti učinkoviti ili ne. Nakon distribucije trenutnih kandidata za cjepivo razna su istraživanja na razne načine pokušala provjeriti njihovu učinkovitost. Sve više preliminarnih istraživanja pokazuje da cijepljene osobe značajnim dijelom sudjeluju u prijenosu novog koronavirusa. Osobe cijepljene dvjema dozama mogu se zaraziti, prenositi uzročnika te razviti težak oblik bolesti i umrijeti [162, 213–216]. Virus se od zaraženih cijepljenih može i izolirati u staničnim kulturama [217]. Neka su istraživanja pokazala da i cijepljeni i necijepljeni mogu u sličnom kapacitetu prenositi novi koronavirus [218–224]. U jednom je još nereguliranim istraživanju među zatvorenicima jednog zatvora utvrđeno 95 osoba s pozitivnim PCR-testom od čega je 78 zatvorenika (82 %) bilo cijepljeno [223]. U srpnju je u američkoj saveznoj državi Massachusetts tijekom raznih događaja zabilježeno 469 slučajeva covid-19, 346 (74 %) od njih je bilo cijepljeno, a 274 (79 %) od tih 346 razvilo je simptome [219]. Od 1. siječnja do 30. travnja 2021. u SAD-u je službeno zabilježeno 10 262 slučaja covid-19 kod cijepljenih, od čega je 995 (10 %) bilo hospitalizirano, a 160 (2 %) je preminulo [225]. U jednom je istraživanju u staračkom domu u kojem su svi štićenici bili cijepljeni, a osoblje barem testirano, zabilježeno 119 slučajeva covid-19 među štićenicima, uključujući s teškim simptomima. Autori su zaključili da je cijepljenje u njihovom uzorku bilo povezano s “nedostatnom imunosti i manjkom zaštite protiv kolonizacije ili zaraze” [226]. Slični su slučajevi objavljeni i drugdje [227]. Jedno je epidemiološko istraživanje podataka iz 68 država i 2 947 američkih okruga zaključilo da ne postoji statistički značajna povezanost između stope slučajeva covid-19 i stope procijepljenosti, ali da postoji pozitivan trend između dviju varijabli (odnosno, trend prema većim stopama covid-19 u populacijama s višom stopom procijepljenosti) [228], a slični rezultati dolaze i od jedne analize francuskih podataka [229]. Slična, zasad neregulirana analiza podataka iz 145 država došla je do zaključka da je stopa procijepljenosti statistički značajno povezana s brojem slučajeva covid-19 i smrti povezanih s covid-19 u velikom dijelu država (87 %). Konkretno, cijepljenje je prema analizi bilo povezano s rastom od 261 % u broju slučajeva covid-19 te 463 % u broju smrti [230]. Međutim, nije jasno u kojoj su mjeri službeni podaci o procijepljenosti, slučajevima covid-19, hospitalizacijama i smrtima pouzdani i valjani za znanstvena istraživanja [7, 8, 50, 231–252]. Jedno je istraživanje došlo do zaključka da cijepljeni imaju statistički značajno veći rizik zaraziti se onim sojevima koji su povezani sa smanjenom neutralizacijom antitijela u usporedbi s necijepljenima [224]. Istraživanja također pokazuju da imunost hitro opada s vremenom; Pfizerovo pokazuje (relativnu) učinkovitost od 47 % nakon četiri mjeseca, Modernino 59 %, a AstraZenecino -19 % (minus implicira da se u uzorku zarazilo više cijepljenih nego necijepljenih). Nakon četiri mjeseca, učinkovitost nastavlja padati prema neučinkovitosti [253–257]. Također je poznato da neke populacije već ionako imaju slabiju mogućnost stvaranja imunosti s pomoću trenutnih kandidata, uključujući starije, osobe s višim indeksom tjelesne mase ili povišenim krvnim tlakom, pušače, muškarce itd. [258–262].

² Istaknuo Petar Gabrić.

Imajući na umu dosadašnje informacije iz teksta, nije primjerice jasno što je Marija Bubaš, pomoćnica ravnatelja Hrvatskog zavoda za javno zdravstvo, htjela reći kad je izjavila: “Sva [cjepiva] koja dolaze i dolaziti će u Hrvatsku, za koja se Hrvatska predbilježila i za koja je zainteresirana, a osobito ova tri cjepiva koja jesu tu, *sto posto*³ štite od umiranja u slučaju zaraze bolešću COVID-19”, dodajući: “Nadam se da svi žele život i da im je život dragocjen toliko da će se odlučiti za cjepivo koje im prvo dođe pod ruku” [263]. Na kojim je informacijama temeljena ova izjava? Zasigurno nije temeljena na podacima dostupnima od proizvođača, a nije temeljena ni na rezultatima drugih znanstvenih istraživanja.

Kandidati za cjepiva protiv covid-19 za djecu od pet do 15 godina nedavno su počeli objavljivati pozitivne rezultate s kliničkih ispitivanja. Primjerice, Pfizerov uzorak za djecu od 12 do 15 godina imao je 2 228 ispitanika. Teško je raspravljati o tako malom uzorku, a nema naznaka da problemi navedeni gore ne vrijede jednako i za ispitivanja na djeci [264, 265].

2.6. Pokazatelji o pogreškama i prikrivanju pogrešaka tijekom preliminarnih kliničkih ispitivanja

U studenom 2021. prestižni je medicinski znanstveni časopis *BMJ* (prema eng. *British Medical Journal*) objavio svjedočanstvo zviždačice Brook Jackson, regionalne direktorice u organizaciji Ventavia s kojom je Pfizer sklopio ugovor o provođenju dijela kliničkih ispitivanja Pfizerovog kandidata za cjepivo. Jackson je tajno prikupila interne tvrtkine dokumente, fotografirala, snimala razgovore s izvršnim direktorima i napravila kopije povjerljivih e-mailova. Jackson je razotkrila krivotvorenje istraživačkih podataka (čija priroda zasad još nije jasna), omogućavanje i osoblju i pacijentima da znaju jesu li u skupini za cjepivo ili placebo (što narušava cijeli dizajn istraživanja), zapošljavanje neadekvatno educiranih cjepitelja, nedostatak osoblja za provođenje PCR-testiranja i manjak praćenja onih pacijenata koji su imali nuspojave, uključujući teške nuspojave. Snimke komunikacija s izvršnim direktorima pokazuju da su bili svjesni krivotvorenja podataka i ostalih propusta te, prema izjavi jednog od izvršnih direktora, da je propusta bilo toliko da “tvrtka nije mogla kvantificirati tipove i broj pogrešaka koje su pronalazili pregledavajući dokumentaciju za kvalitetu kontrole”. Jackson je od Ventavie dobila otkaz isti dan kada je pogreške prijavila američkoj Upravi za hranu i lijekove (FDA), a Uprava nikad nije provela inspekciju. Uprava je inače u kolovozu 2021. objavila da se inspekcija provodila na svega devet od 153 lokacije na kojima su bila organizirana klinička ispitivanja. Manjak inspekcija Uprava je objasnila činjenicom “da je istraživanje bilo u tijeku pa podaci o istraživačkom novom lijeku potrebni za ovjeru i usporedbu nisu bili dostupni”. Zanimljivo je da je Pfizer i nakon Jacksonine prijave sklopio četiri daljnja ugovora s Ventaviom za provođenje kliničkih ispitivanja, uključujući klinička ispitivanja Pfizerovog kandidata kod djece i trudnica te ispitivanje treće doze (eng. *booster*) [155, 266].

S obzirom da, nažalost, detalji navedenog skandala nisu poznati, nije jasno u kojoj su mjeri navedene pogreške utjecale na ishod istraživanja, no on sigurno ne može značiti ništa dobro za već ionako upitnu kvalitetu provedenih istraživanja.

2.7. Moguće štetne posljedice za zdravlje

U prethodnim dvama razdjelima navedeno je više problematičnih aspekata u vezi s trenutnim cjepivima protiv covid-19 zbog kojih je objavljena učinkovitost tih cjepiva upitna. Postojanje tih problema i nejasnoća

³ Istaknuo Petar Gabrić.

također otvara pitanja o sigurnosti cjepiva. Proizvođači su nakon provedenih preliminarnih analiza objavili da su njihovi kandidati sigurni. Međutim, teško je raspravljati o sigurnosti cjepiva na temelju tih preliminarnih analiza. Primjerice, Pfizerova studija pratila je ispitanike do oko dva mjeseca nakon druge doze te je fokus bio na “lokalnim [bol na mjestu injekcije, crvenilo, oticanje] i sistemskim [povišena tjelesna temperatura, umor, glavobolja] štetnim” učincima. Što se drugo pratilo, a da nije bilo u fokusu, nije pretjerano jasno, no njihova se analiza u svakome slučaju temeljila na simptomima, tj. štetni učinak zabilježen je samo onda kada ga je ispitanik samostalno javio ispitivačima [144]. Pfizerovo ograničavanje na navedene medicinske pojave problematično je iz nekoliko razloga i ne ulijeva povjerenje u proizvođačeve objave o sigurnosti cjepiva.

- (1) Ovakav način praćenja mogućih štetnih učinaka kandidata za cjepivo ne može se ni u kojem slučaju smatrati kvalitetnim neovisno o bilo kojim drugim čimbenicima. Je li to razina kvalitete znanstvenih istraživanja s kojom se možemo zadovoljiti [49, 50]?
- (2) Šiljasti protein novog koronavirusa koji bi tijelo trebalo proizvoditi nakon cijepljenja protiv covid-19 izrazito je toksičan i već je u kontekstu zaraze novim koronavirusom bio povezan s raznim patološkim stanjima povezanim s hiperinflamacijom, hiperkoagulacijom, hipoksijom itd. kao što su primjerice oštećenje krvnih žila i povećanje propusnosti krvno-moždane barijere, ali i oštećenje testisa [169, 267–280]. Istraživanja sugeriraju da šiljasti protein često može samostalno izazvati navedene štete, neovisno o drugim proteinima novog koronavirusa [281–285]. To je potencijalno zabrinjavaćuje budući da cjepiva protiv covid-19 potiču sintezu šiljastog proteina što znači da bi taj šiljasti protein mogao kod cijepljenih izazvati jednaku takvu ili veću štetu. Mnogi autori su izrazili zabrinutost zbog uporabe šiljastog proteina u cjepivima protiv covid-19 i implikacija koje to može imati za sigurnost cjepiva [49, 50, 53, 171, 177, 183, 187, 190, 208, 286]. Nadalje, neki predviđaju da je šiljasti protein iz cjepiva čak štetniji od šiljastog proteina zarazom zbog zaobilaznja urođenog imunskog sustava cijepljenjem, veće količine šiljastih proteina koji ulaze u krvotok i dodatnim toksičnim učincima sastojaka lipidne nanočestice [49, 50, 53, 187].
- (3) Zato su neki očekivali da će istraživanje sigurnosti kandidata za cjepivo uključiti i primjerice mjerenja razine d-dimera za dokazivanje povećane koagulacije (zgrušavanje krvi) i stvaranja krvnih ugrušaka, c-reaktivnih proteina za dokazivanje povećanih upalnih procesa, troponina za dokazivanje oštećenja srca, okludina i kladina za dokazivanje povećane propusnosti krvno-moždane barijere, kisika u krvi za dokazivanje hipoksije, amiloida beta i fosforiliranog tau-proteina za dokazivanje povećane predispozicije za Alzheimerovu bolest, seruma HMGB1, CXCL13 i Dickkopf-1 za dokazivanje povećane predispozicije na autoimmune bolesti itd. [50, 53].
- (4) Zbog manjka takvih mjerenja razina biomarkera ne mogu se uočiti patološke i/ili abnormalne promjene u tijelu primatelja cjepiva koje nakon dva mjeseca nisu dosegle razinu simptoma. Primjerice, poremećaj povećanog zgrušavanja krvi ne mora odmah biti prepoznat kao slučaj ozbiljne tromboze ili sl., ali svedjedno može povećati predispoziciju za ozbiljne krvne ugruške u budućnosti zbog postojanja većeg broja mikrougrušaka nakon cijepljenja [50, 290, 291], naročito kod osoba životnih stilova koji promoviraju stvaranje krvnih ugrušaka [287–289].
- (5) Brojčanost, raznolikost i ozbiljnost štetnih događaja prijavljenih u službenim bazama podataka spontano prijavljenih štetnih događaja povezanih s cijepljenjem protiv covid-19 te štetnih učinaka povezanih s cijepljenjem covid-19 iz preliminarnih opservacijskih istraživanja primjene cjepiva u stvarnome svijetu nisu bile predviđene na temelju podataka koje su dosad objavili proizvođači [50].

- (6) Skandal s Ventaviom sugerira da barem neki slučajevi teških nuspojava nisu bili zabilježeni ili su neadekvatno zabilježeni [155]. Motivacija za takvo postupanje nije jasna.
- (7) Proizvođači načelno nisu objavili biodistribucijska istraživanja svojih kandidata kojima bi se ustanovilo u koje dijelove tijela i u kojoj količini odlazi cjepivo. Neki navode da prisutnost šiljastih proteina u plazmi cijepljenih implicira da oni mogu dospjeti do svakog dijela tijela [50, 292]. Istraživanja mRNA-cjepiva protiv gripe iz 2017. i mRNA-cjepiva protiv bjesnoće iz 2020. pokazala su da RNK odlazi u jetra i slezenu preko limfnog sustava da bi konačno završilo u krvotoku, i mozgu [293, 294]. I Modernino i AstraZenecino cjepivo dopijeva u mozak [295, 296]. Preliminarne analize sugeriraju i da Pfizerovo cjepivo dopijeva u razne organe, uključujući jajnike i koštanu srž [50, 297]. Potencijalna biodistribucija RNK-a u mozgu mogla bi biti vrlo problematična jer bi mogla navesti moždane stanice da proizvode šiljaste proteine što bi posljedično moglo dovesti do imunosnog napada tijela na vlastite moždane stanice ili moždane tromboze. Potonje možda objašnjava slučajeve cerebralne venske tromboze nakon cijepljenja protiv covid-19 (v. dolje). Štetni učinci šiljastog proteina na jajnike mogli bi imati katastrofične posljedice za plodnost i razmnožavanje [49, 50, 53].

Budući da su proizvođači nekvalitetno istražili sigurnost svojih kandidata za cjepivo, trenutno nam, da bismo spoznali o sigurnosti kandidata, preostaje jedino promatrati što se događa tijekom distribucije cjepiva u općoj populaciji. To je krajnje neobična i neočekivana situacija ako uzmemo u obzir da se radi o cjepivima koja su iz raznih aspekata bez presedana te da posljedično ne postoji povijest korištenja na temelju koje bi se mogla adekvatno procijeniti sigurnost i da se namjerava cijepiti najveći dio svjetske populacije.

Brojni su autori izrazili zabrinutost u vezi sa sigurnosti cijepljenja djece protiv covid-19, neki su izrazili mišljenje da se trenutna cjepiva ne bi trebala davati djeci [49, 50, 53, 172, 190, 286, 299–310]. Neka iskustva iz prošlosti pozivaju nas na oprez [302, 311–321].

U nastavku teksta slijedi kratki pregled dosadašnje (odabrane) znanstvene literature o štetnim događajima povezanim s cijepljenjem protiv covid-19. Iako pregled sadrži relativno mnogo bibliografskih jedinica, on predstavlja samo dio dosadašnje znanstvene literature, a novi radovi objavljuju se svaki dan te je za očekivati da će njihova dnevna stopa samo rasti povećanjem osviještenosti o štetnim učincima cijepljenja protiv covid-19 i njihovom detabuizacijom, rastućem broju distribuiranih doza cjepiva i rastućoj količini vremena proteklog od svake pojedine distribucije doze cjepiva. U dosadašnjoj znanstvenoj literaturi uglavnom se pronalaze studije slučaja (klinički prikaz pojedinog pacijenta) i serije slučajeva, a nedostaju istraživanja s većim brojem podataka i/ili ispitanika. Zbog toga je malo poznato o tipovima, učestalosti i težini pojedinih štetnih učinaka povezanih s cijepljenjem. Cjelovita slika potencijalno je ozbiljna. Pretpostavlja se da će se neki štetni učinci simptomatski prikazati tek za nekoliko godina ili desetljeća. Nadalje, rizik od štetnih učinaka i više težine simptoma moguće su povećani sa svakom novom dozom, naročito ako bi neki štetni učinci bili kumulativni i nepovratni [49, 50].

Važno je napomenuti da baze podataka spontano prijavljenih štetnih događaja povezanih s cijepljenjem pokazano znatno podcjenjuju razinu učestalosti pojedinih štetnih učinaka. Razni autori procjenjuju da takve baze podataka predstavljaju od primjerice 1 % do 20 % stvarnih slučajeva [50, 312, 322, 323]. Također, vjerojatnost da će neki štetni slučaj povezan s cijepljenjem naletiti na znanstveno vješte liječnike ili druge znanstvenike te da će oni napisati znanstveni članak i objaviti ga u relevantnom znanstvenom časopisu vjerojatno je vrlo malena.

Treba napomenuti da vremenska povezanost cijepljenja i štetnog događaja ne implicira nužno da je cijepljenje uzročno dovelo do štetnog događaja. Međutim, za neke poremećaje već postoji (rani) sporazum da su uzrokovani cijepljenje protiv covid-19, a nekoliko je analiza baza podataka spontanijh prijava štetnih događaja povezanih s cijepljenjem sugeriralo na temelju relativno čvrstih grupacija slučajeva oko vremena cijepljenja da veze između raznih poremećaja i cijepljenja nisu slučajne [50, 204, 322, 324–326].

Uznemiruju neki podaci iz baza spontano prijavljenih štetnih događaja. Primjerice, od 1. siječnja do 3. prosinca 2021. u američkoj je takvoj bazi podataka VAERS (prema eng. *Vaccine Adverse Event Reporting System*, ‘Sustav za prijavljivanje štetnih događaja povezanih s cijepljenjem’) prijavljeno 898 661 štetnih slučajeva za sva cjepiva (i cjepiva osim onih protiv covid-19). Od tih 898 661 štetnih slučajeva 858 913 odnosi se na cjepiva protiv covid-19. Od 18 563 smrti povezanih s cijepljenjem u tom razdoblju 17 998 se odnosilo na cjepiva protiv covid-19. Nažalost, ne znamo koliko je kojeg cjepiva podijeljeno u tom razdoblju i koliko na prijave utječe trenutna svjetska pozornost na covid-19, no usporedbe brojki i dalje su vrlo dramatične [1249].

Gotovo sve dolje navedene medicinske pojave zabilježene su i kod djece u bazama podataka spontano prijavljenih štetnih događaja [50].

Alergijske reakcije i anafilaksa – mRNK-cjepiva koriste lipidnu nanočesticu koja obaviju virusnu mRNK i sigurno je dovodi do stanice. U mRNK-cjepivima protiv covid-19 te su nanočestice sačinjene od ionizirajućih lipida, fosfolipida, kolesterola i polietilenskog glikola. Istraživanje na miševima pokazalo je da sastojci tih lipidnih nanočestica imaju izraziti upalni potencijal što može biti povezano s raznim abnormalnim pojavama [327]. Polietilenski glikol (PEG; koji se prvi put upotrebljava u injekciji) među njima je posebno problematičan te postoji znatan broj istraživanja koja PEG dovode u vezu s alergijskim reakcijama i anafilaksom [327–331]. Istraživanja na životinjama potvrđuju da izlaganje PEG-u može dovesti do anafilakse i kardiovaskularnog kolapsa [332, 333]. Problematično je što veliki udio ljudi ima razvijena antitijela protiv PEG-a jer su mu izloženi korištenjem svakodnevnih predmeta ili uzimanjem terapija koje sadrže PEG. Neka istraživanja pokazuju da od 42 do 72 % ljudi u danoj populaciji ima razvijena antitijela protiv PEG-a te su zabilježeni brojni slučajevi anafilakse nakon ponovnog izlaganju PEG-u [331, 334–341]. Iako je anafilaksa relativno rijetka pojava, može biti smrtonosna. Rizik od anafilakse zbog izlaganja PEG-u povećan je kod ljudi s razvijenim antitijelima protiv PEG-a pa je njihova uporaba u mRNK-cjepivima koja zahtijevaju više injekcija potencijalno zabrinjavajuća [342]. Sve je veći broj zabilježenih slučajeva anafilakse nakon primanja cjepiva protiv covid-19 [153, 170, 172, 343–353]. Jedno je preliminarno istraživanje kod zdravstvenih djelatnika ustanovilo stopu od 2.1 % alergijskih reakcija nakon jedne doze cjepiva, a 247 djelatnika na milijun doživjelo je anafilaksu što je oko 130 puta veća stopa anafilakse nego što se procjenjuje za druga cjepiva [49, 343, 351, 354, 355]. S obzirom da cijepljenje protiv covid-19 trenutno zahtijeva dvije doze te da se najavljuje još doza nakon druge doze, ti će brojevi rasti budući da je rizik od anafilakse uzrokovane PEG-om povećan sa svakom novom dozom terapije, jednim dijelom i jer se očekuje da će osobe bez razvijenih PEG-antitijela razviti ih nakon prve doze [50, 179, 332].

Autoimune i autoupalne bolesti – Više je autora izrazilo zabrinutost da bi trenutna cjepiva protiv covid-19 mogla dovesti do razvoja raznih autoimunih i autoupalnih bolesti [170, 286, 356–360, 809, 810]. Predložena su dva opća mehanizma: tzv. autoimuni/autoupalni sindrom uzrokovan adjuvansima (sindrom ASIA, prema eng. *autoimmune/inflammatory syndrome induced by adjuvants*) te autoimunost uzrokovana unakrsnom

reaktivnošću antitijela protiv SARS-CoV-2 i ljudskih tkivnih antigena. Prvotne teorije o mogućoj povezanosti cjepiva protiv covid-19 i sindroma ASIA našalost se potvrđuju rastućim brojem opservacijskih istraživanja i podataka u bazama spontano prijavljenih štetnih učinaka povezanih s cjepivima. Specifično, zabilježeni su već brojni slučajevi poremećenog rada štitnjače, najčešće u obliku hipertireoze (pojačana aktivnost štitnjače) te inače rijetkih subakutnog tireoiditisa (upala štitnjače) i Gravesove bolesti [361–385]. Pacijenti sa subakutnim tireoiditisom nakon cijepljenja protiv covid-19 žale se na bolove u ramenima i vratu (čija razina može biti teška), psihomotoričku agitaciju (nenamjerno i besmisleno kretanje udova), poteškoće u gutanju, nagao gubitak tjelesne mase, psihički nemir, povećano znojenje, nesanicu, palpitacije (doživljen pojačani rad srca), osjetljivost na toplinu itd. Problematično je što postoje i slučajevi tihog (tj. bezbolnog) subakutnog tireoiditisa što može dovesti do nedijagnoze tireoiditisa ili pogrešne dijagnoze što pak može dovesti do pogoršanja i produljenja simptoma zbog neličenja. Posljedično je moguće da postoji mnogo pacijenata s tireoiditisom nakon cijepljenja protiv covid-19 koji zasad nisu identificirani [361]. Pacijenti s Gravesovom bolesti uz navedene simptome mogu razviti i Gravesovu oftalmopatiju koju karakteriziraju izbuljene oči. Razne su druge autoimune/autoupalne bolesti zabilježene koje su vjerojatno povezano sa spomenutom unakrsnom reaktivnošću antitijela protiv SARS-CoV-2 i ljudskih tkivnih antigena. Zabrinjavajuće je da antitijela protiv SARS-CoV-2 imaju mogućnost za reaktivnost s 28 od 55 ljudskih tkivnih antigena [358]. Primjerice, zabilježeni su slučajevi stečene hemofilije (jedan od poremećaja zgrušavanja s primjetno povećanim krvarenjem) [386, 387], mijastenije gravis (bolest koju obilježuje progresivna slabost mišića tijekom napora zbog poremećaja na neuromuskularnome spojištu) [388, 389], anemije (smanjena koncentracija hemoglobina i/ili eritrocita u krvi) [390–392] itd. Zabilježene su razne reumatske bolesti [393, 394], uključujući artritis (upala zglobova) [389, 395, 396], miozitis (upala mišića) [397], Stillovu bolest (povišena tjelesna temperatura, bolovi u zglobovima, kvrgavi osip, moguća oštećenja organa) [398–401], sustavni eritematozni lupus (prouzročuje oštećenje brojnih organa) [389, 402–405], Behçetovu bolest (zahvaća male i srednje krvne žile i popraćena je ponavljajućim vrijedovima na sluznici spolnih organa i oka te oštećenjem većega broja organskih sustava, a najčešće na usnoj sluznici) [389, 406], razne oblike vaskulitisa (upalne promjene krvnih žila pri kojima dolazi do infiltracije limfocita s trombozom, vaskularnom okluzijom, hemoragijom i ishemijom) [389, 407–423], reumatsku polimijalgiju (izraženi i rašireni bolovi i ukočenost) [389, 424–426], sinovitis (upala sinovijalnih tkiva unutrašnjosti zgloba) [389, 427] i druge [428]. Zabilježeni su i slučajevi autoimunog hepatitisa uzrokovanog cijepljenjem protiv covid-19 [429–445]. Rizik od autoimunog hepatitisa nakon cijepljenja protiv covid-19 povećan je nakon druge doze i vjerojatno sljedećih doza [444]. Iniče je rizik od autoimunih i autoupalnih poremećaja moguće povećan sa svakom novom imunizacijom namijenjenom stvaranju istog antitijela [446].

Važno je napomenuti i da mnoga druga stanja nakon cijepljenja koja ću navesti mogu predstavljati imunosno posredovane bolesti, no radi preglednosti ću ostale poremećaje navesti prema tjelesnim sustavima koje zahvaćaju.

Poremećaji s očima i vidom – Zabilježene su brojne poteškoće s očima koje mogu dovesti do poteškoća u vidu te se one isto često povezuju s autoimunim i autoupalnim procesima. Poteškoće uključuju eritemne edeme (nakupljanje tekućine u tkivnim prostorima zbog nedostatnoga uklanjanja tekućine iz tkiva uz upalno crvenilo) i osip s purpurama (promjena boje tkiva zbog krvarenja) na gornjim kapcima, odbijanje presatka rožnice (i 25 godina nakon transplantacije), episkleritis (upala episkleralnoga tkiva povezana s nelagodnom i boli), odignuće mrežnice (odvajanje neurosenzorne mrežnice od mrežničnog pigmentnog epitela uz nakupljanje tekućine u subretinalnome prostoru), uveitis (upala srednje očne ovojnice), koroiditis (stražnji

uveitis kod kojega je upalom zahvaćena žilnica), različite oblike retinopatije, vaskularne okluzije mrežnice, nekrozu mrežnice (konačno nepovratno stanje smrti stanica mrežnice), optički neuritis (upala vidnoga živca) i druge. Pacijenti se žale na smanjenje ili gubitak vida, crvenilo, bol, fotofobiju (netolerancija ili intenzivna osjetljivost na svjetlost), krvarenje, glavobolju, bljeskove, percipirane strukture u vidnom polju koje ometaju vid itd. [447–458].

Miokarditis i perikarditis – Više nema sumnje da miokarditis (upala srčanog mišića) i perikarditis (upala srčane ovojnice) nisu tek “ekstremno rijetke” [459, 460] pojave nakon cijepljenja protiv covid-19, naročito kod djece i mladih. Postoji već vrlo velik broj preliminarnih opservacijskih istraživanja koja miokarditis i perikarditis dovode u uzročno-posljedičnu vezu s cijepljenjem protiv covid-19 [170, 172, 461–559]. Čini se da su najizloženiji dječaci i mladi muškarci. Jedno zasad još neregulirano (slabokvalitetno) istraživanje pokazalo je da zdravi dječaci od 12 do 15 godina starosti imaju između tri i šest puta veći rizik od razvijanja kardiovaskularnih poremećaja nakon cijepljenja protiv covid-19 nego što im je rizik od hospitalizacije zbog covid-19 [463]. Jedna je analiza javno dostupnih podataka o spontanom javljanju štetnih događaja povezanih s cjepivima pokazala da je već u prvih nekoliko tjedana nakon početka distribucije cjepiva među adolescentima između 12 i 15 godina rizik od miokarditisa bio povećan 19 puta u usporedbi s onime što bi se očekivalo s ostalim cjepivima [461]. Ta recenzirana studija objavljena u prestižnom časopisu misteriozno je i bez ikakvog objašnjenja izbrisana sa stranice časopisa. To je vrlo neobično za znanstvene časopise koji u pravilu objavljene radove mogu povući (eng. *retract*) u slučaju postojanja pogrešaka u radu, no i u tom slučaju sadržaj ostaje dostupan (uz napomenu o povlačenju, eng. *retraction*). U ovome slučaju uredništvo nije izrazilo nikakvu zabrinutost u vezi pogrešaka, već je ostavilo samo napomenu da je “članak povučen [eng. *withdrawn*] na zahtjev autora i/ili urednika”. Još se očekuje rasplet ove mini-drame te će, pretpostavljam, rad biti objavljen u nekom drugom časopisu. Bilo kako bilo, potrebna su daljnja istraživanja, no rastući broj opservacijskih istraživanja i spontanijih prijava miokarditisa i perikarditisa nakon cijepljenja protiv covid-19 zabrinjava, naročito ako uzmemo u obzir da su najviše pogođena djeca koja imaju još cijeli život pred sobom.

Tromboze i trombocitopenija – Uz miokarditis i perikarditis, najbrojnije su opservacije povećanog zgrušavanja krvi koje je povezano s raznim oblicima tromboza i trombocitopenije te je njihov rastući broj također zabrinjavajuć [170, 172, 560–650]. U medijima se ove pojave također nerijetko opisuju kao “ekstremno rijetke” [459, 651]. Iako se navedeni poremećaji u najvećem dijelu događaju nakon vektorskih cjepiva, mnogo je slučajeva i nakon mRNA-cjepiva. Trombocitopenija je potencijalno smrtonosna bolest obilježena smanjenjem broja trombocita, a očituje se pojavom hemoragičnih lezija, spontanijih gingivnih krvarenja te petehijama i ekhimoza na usnoj sluznici [652]. Posebno su zabrinjavajući slučajevi poremećaja zgrušavanja krvi u mozgu i specifično cerebralne venske tromboze koja je povezana s infarktom i moždanim krvarenjem te mogu u oko 50 % slučajeva povezanih s cijepljenjem protiv covid-19 dovesti do smrti [560]. Jasno je da posljedice smrti moždanih stanica i moždanog krvarenja kod osoba koje prežive mogu biti dramatične te konačno uključivati nemogućnost samostalnog svakodnevnog funkcioniranja. Zbog manjka kvalitetnih istraživanja još uvijek nije jasno u kojoj su mjeri poremećaji zgrušavanja krvi zastupljeni kod cijepljenih osoba, a izgledno je da mnogi slučajevi još uvijek nisu identificirani jer se, pretpostavlja se, radi o mikrougrušcima koji nisu doveli do simptomatskog izražaja [50, 618]. Vjerojatnost od razvijanja poremećaja zgrušavanja krvi moguće je povećana sa svakom novom dozom cjepiva [50].

Neurološki poremećaji – Cijepljenje protiv covid-19 povezano je s raznim neurološkim poremećajima, uključujući već spomenute cerebralne venske tromboze, Guillain-Barréov sindrom (slabost mišića zbog autoimunog oštećenja perifernog živčanog sustava), mijelitis (upala kralježnične moždine s potencijalnom oštećenjem mijelinske ovojnice i aksona koji mogu dovesti do paralize), paraliza facijalnog živca, demijelinizaciju optičkog živca, mozga i kralježnične moždine (oštećenje mijelinske ovojnice koje može dovesti do gubitka vida, slabosti u udovima i paralize, parastezija itd.), moždano krvarenje, ishemijski moždani udar, aseptički meningoencefalitis, afaziju (gubitak govora), neuralgičnu amiotrofiju (slabost i atrofija mišića kojima prethodi teška bol), tinitus [49, 170, 207, 481, 653–679], reaktivaciju latentnog herpesa zoster (reaktivacija virusa *varicella zoster* pri padu imunosti koja se očituje osjetljivošću i bolnošću pojedinih dermatoma, nakon čega slijedi makulopapularni osip koji prelazi u mjehuriće i kraste) [680–710] itd. Brojne pojave reaktivacije latentnog herpesa zoster sugeriraju da ta cjepiva dovode do supresije urođenog imunskog sustava [49] što sugerira i jedno drugo neregulirano istraživanje [711]. Posebno su uznemirujuće nove dijagnoze multiple skleroze [389, 712] te slučaj demencije s hitrim propadanjem moždanog tkiva kod inače zdrave starije žene, jedan dan nakon druge doze cjepiva, praćeno delirijem, smanjenim pamćenjem i halucinacijama nakon pet dana. Nakon dva tjedna neurodegeneracija je dovela do respiratornog distresa i šoka te je pacijentica preminula mjesec dana nakon primanja druge doze [661]. U kontekstu neurodegeneracije, neki su pretpostavili da bi cjepiva protiv covid-19 mogla dovesti do prionskih bolesti i posljedično neurodegeneracije [49, 713, 714]. Prioni su pogrešno savijeni i/ili fragmentirani proteini koji obilježavaju izrazito progresivne i uvijek smrtonosne neurodegenerativne bolesti. U tom kontekstu zabrinjava da je Pfizer u svojoj dokumentaciji poslanoj Europskoj agenciji za lijekove (EMA-i) za odobrenje cjepiva naveo da u njegovim injekcijama postoje “fragmentirani specijesi” virusne RNK te da je u injekcijama korištenima za klinička ispitivanja bilo znatno manje tih “fragmentiranih specijesa” u injekcijama. Pfizer je bez previše argumenata tvrdio da navedeni fragmenti “vjerojatno [...] neće rezultirati ekspresijom proteina”. EMA je izrazila zabrinutost ostavivši komentar: “Te strukture [fragmentirani specijesi] slabo su opisane, a ograničeni dostupni podaci o ekspresiji proteina ne razrješuju u potpunosti nesigurnosti povezane s rizikom od sinteze proteina/peptida osim namijenjenog šiljastog proteina” [295, 808]. Pfizer dosad prema mojim saznanjima nije dao na raspolaganje nikakve nove relevantne informacije.

Ostalo – Nažalost, cijepljenje protiv covid-19 povezano je s raznim drugim poremećajima koje ću radi kratkoće i preglednosti samo navesti, uključujući limfadenopatiju (povećanje limfnih čvorova) [715–736], rabdomiolizu (naglo oštećenje i raspadanje skeletnih mišića) [737–743], ozljedu slezene i pankreatitis (upala slezene) [744, 745], ozljedu i upalu pluća [481, 746–750], oštećenje i upalu bubrega (uključujući glomerulonefritis) [751–760], razne i brojne kožne bolesti [761–800], dijabetes [385] itd. Neki pretpostavljaju da će trenutno masovno cijepljenje moguće dovesti do novih sojeva novog koronavirusa koji bi mogli biti otporni na cjepiva [49, 172, 183, 190, 801–803]. Više je autora pretpostavilo da bi cijepljenje protiv covid-19 moglo dovesti do tzv. poboljšanja ovisnog o antitijelima (ADE, prema eng. *antibody-dependent enhancement*), pojave u kojoj opetovana imunizacija (tj. stvaranje specifičnih antitijela) određenim procesima dovodi do veće zaraznosti uzročnika olakšavajući uzročniku ulazak u stanicu. Drugim riječima, osobe koje su provele više imunizacija protiv novog koronavirusa mogle bi biti suočene s ADE-om pri zarazi novim koronavirusom ili novim imunizacijama (npr. treća doza, četvrta doza itd.). ADE u najgorem slučaju može dovesti do citokinske oluje koja uzrokuje široko oštećenje lokalnog tkiva i može biti smrtonosna [49, 153, 172, 173, 177, 190, 804–807]. Jedno je istraživanje pokazalo da se RNK novog koronavirusa može obrnutom transkripcijom uklopiti u ljudsku DNK kod zaraženih [823] čime se otvara pitanje može li se to postići i cijepljenjem [49, 822].

Malo je podataka o cijepljenju u trudnoći. Trenutne preporuke institucija trudnicama za cijepljenje uglavnom se temelje na jednoj skromnoj analizi koja je zaključila da cijepljenje protiv covid-19 nije povezano s povećanim rizikom od spontanog pobačaja i smrti novorođenčeta [817]. Međutim, to je istraživanje kritizirano [811, 818] te je naknadno objavljen ispravak prvotnog članka u kojem autori konačno zaključuju da s njihovim podacima “nije mogla izračunati procjena rizika spontanog pobačaja” [819]. U baza podataka spontano prijavljenih štetnih događaja povezanim s cijepljenjem raste broj prijavljenih spontanih pobačaja nakon cijepljenja protiv covid-19, uključujući slučajeve svega nekoliko sati nakon injekcije [50, 170, 298, 1249]. Zabilježeni su i slučajevi prijenosa cjepiva s majke na dojenče preko majčinog mlijeka [298]. Brojne su prijave promjena u menstruaciji [50, 170, 1249]. Neki su autori izrazili zabrinutost oko mogućih štetnih učinaka cjepiva na plodnost i razmnožavanje, između ostalog distribucijom šiljastog proteina u jajnicima i testisima [49, 50, 170, 172, 275, 306, 811–821].

Nije jasno zašto se informacije iz ovog razdjela načelno ne mogu naći u hrvatskim medijima i izjavama hrvatskih zdravstvenih djelatnika. Nažalost, izvještavanje u medijima obilježeno je velikim dijelom pogrešnih informacija, provociranjem, pretjeravanjem te poticanjem straha i ostalih negativnih emocija [834–854].

3. Nefarmakološke mjere suzbijanja covid-19

3.1. Zatvaranje (eng. *lockdown*)

Hrvatska vlada je kao odgovor na covid-19 uvela niz tzv. mjera za suzbijanje pandemije koje su donijele ograničenja ljudskog ponašanja i prestanak funkcioniranja raznih postojećih sustava, a Vlada se nije libila uključiti i djecu u navedene mjere. Neke od istaknutijih mjera koje je Vlada uvela i primijenila na djeci su tzv. zatvaranje (eng. *lockdown*), zatvaranje škola i nošenje maski. Problematično je što za navedene mjere postoje tek slabi ili nikakvi pokazatelji u znanstvenoj literaturi da doprinose suzbijanju covid-19, a postoje pokazatelji da navedene mjere mogu dovesti do raznih štetnih učinaka na zdravlje i kvalitetu života i kod odraslih i kod djece. Iako su neka slabokvalitetna istraživanja pokazala da zatvaranje jest barem vremenski povezano s određenim smanjenjem prijenosa novog koronavirusa u populaciji [13, 855–858], neka druga slabokvalitetna istraživanja i rasprave nisu došli do takvih zaključaka i/ili su ustanovili da zatvaranje nije povezano sa smanjenjem težine simptoma i smrtnosti [859–884], naročito kod zdravih mladih osoba [870].

Istovremeno, brojna su istraživanja i rasprave pokazale da zatvaranje ima niz štetnih učinaka na javno zdravstvo i funkcioniranje društva, uključujući smanjenu kvalitetu života [885–894], povećanje društvenih nejednakosti [885, 892, 894–897], nezaposlenost [892, 894, 898–901], nasilje u obitelji [894, 902], ograničen pristup zdravstvenim uslugama [903–918], pojavu i pogoršanje postojećih kroničnih bolesti (kardiovaskularne bolesti [904–910, 919–932], dijabetes [933], rak [911–916], depresija i poremećaji tjeskobe [890, 891, 894, 895, 917, 934–981], ovisnosti [982–984] itd.), stres [985–993], smanjen pristup svježem zraku i sunčevoj svjetlosti [994], manjak vitamina D [994], povećan rizik od tzv. oportunističkih zaraza [37], manjak druženja i usamljenost [894, 935, 995], povećan rizik od samoubojstva [936, 940–942], smanjenje fizičke aktivnosti [929, 935, 953, 961, 962, 996–1000], bolove u kostima i mišićima zbog povećanog sjedenja [929, 1001], prekomjernu težinu i pretilost [1002] smanjenu kvalitetu sna [1003], povećan rizik od smrti [48, 1004–1006] itd., na što su djeca zbog nedovršenog razvoja i drugih čimbenika posebno osjetljiva [1007–1041].

Primjerice, jedna je analiza pokazala da je tijekom zatvaranja u Italiji rizik od infarkta miokarda bio uvećan za tri puta u usporedbi s istim razdobljem u 2019. [922] dok je druga analiza pokazala da je u Engleskoj i Walesu u prvoj polovici 2020. zabilježen porast broja smrtnih slučajeva od akutnih kardiovaskularnih bolesti za 35 % u usporedbi s onime što bi se očekivalo na temelju podataka iz razdoblja 2014.–2019. [923]. U Švicarskoj se predviđa da će ozbiljne posljedice zatvaranja na psihičko zdravlje dovesti do skraćenog životnog vijeka od ukupno 1.7 milijuna godina za 180 000 ljudi [937]; u Engleskoj se procjenjuje da jedno do tromjesečno odgađanje operacije kod onkoloških bolesnika u bilo kojem stadiju bolesti uzrokuje dodatnih 4 700 smrti godišnje [911]; i tako dalje. Navedeni su podaci vrlo uznemirujući, naročito ako u obzir uzmemo činjenicu da su svi navedeni čimbenici međusobno isprepleteni.

3.2. Zatvaranje škola

Djeca ograničeno sudjeluju u prijenosu novog koronavirusa i nemaju izražen rizik od teškog oblika bolesti i smrti pa je smislenost mjere zatvaranja škola i iz tog aspekta upitno (v. § 2.2).

Kao i cjelokupno zatvaranje, i zatvaranje škola odnosno onemogućavanje pojedinim razrednim zajednicama da održavaju nastavu u školi zbog sumnje na zarazu novim koronavirusom kod pojedinog učenika pokazano ima štetne učinke na zdravlje i razvoj djece te se u kontekstu covid-19 povezuje s pretiulošću i kratkovidnošću zbog smanjenog kretanja i povećanog gledanja u zaslone elektroničkih uređaja, usamljenošću, stresom, depresijom, povećanim rizikom od samoubojstva, tjeskobom, akutnim i kroničnim umorom, poremećenim spavanjem, usporenim razvojem jezika i govora, usporenim kognitivnim i emocionalnim razvojem, smanjenim učenjem, povećanim rizikom od odustajanja od škole, izrabljivanjem i zlostavljanjem djece, ranom trudnoćom itd. [37, 1007–1041, 1068–1085].

3.3. Nošenje maski

Nošenje maski i kod odraslih i kod djece također je kontroverzna tema u znanstvenoj literaturi. Trenutno ne postoje kvalitetna istraživanja na temelju kojih bi se moglo zaključivati o stupnju učinkovitosti maski u smanjenju prijenosa novog koronavirusa [1086, 1087]. Učinci na težinu simptoma i smrtnost u populaciji vrlo su slabo istraženi. Neka slabokvalitetna istraživanja provedena tijekom proglašene pandemije zaključila su da maske mogu doprinijeti smanjenju prijenosa novog koronavirusa u određenim kontekstima [1088–1091] dok su druga slabokvalitetna istraživanja zaključila da nošenje maski ima slab ili nikakav učinak na prijenos novog koronavirusa [1086, 1092–1103]. Prije proglašenja pandemije u znanstvenoj literaturi i službenim uputama relevantnih ustanova nije bilo govora da bi zdrave osobe nosile masku kako bi izbjegle zarazu ili kako osobe s “asimptomatskom” zarazom ne bi prenijele virus na druge [1100, 1104]. To je zato što su randomizirana kontrolirana istraživanja (u kojima se uspoređuju zdrave osobe koje nose masku s osobama koje ne nose) prije proglašenja pandemije pokazala da maske, a naročito kirurške i platnene, ne smanjuju prijenos virusa sličnih novome koronavirusu, a kamoli da smanjuju težinu simptoma i smrtnost u populaciji [1101, 1105–1024]. Trenutno nedostaju randomizirana kontrolirana istraživanja koja bi ispitala učinkovitost maski na kretanje novog koronavirusa u populaciji i razinu opasnosti koju ono predstavlja [1100, 1125].

Mnogo je istraživanja i rasprava istaknulo moguće štetne učinke nošenja maski, uključujući učinke na zdravlje, zbog čega razni autori smatraju da se i u slučaju da maske mogu doprinijeti suzbijanju covid-19 i/ili drugih virusa njihova opća uporaba ne preporuča [1086, 1095, 1096, 1099, 1100, 1126].

Maska predstavlja očitu prepreku između nosa/usta i vanjskog zraka te u istraživanjima postoji sporazum da nošenje maske dovodi do povećanja razina ugljikovog dioksida (tj. trenda prema tzv. hiperkapniji) i smanjenja razina kisika u tijelu (tj. trenda prema tzv. hipoksemiji) [1086, 1095, 1096, 1100, 1125–1149], poglavito zbog manje dostupnosti kisika tijelu i ponovnog udisanja dijela izdišenog ugljikovog dioksida [1086, 1126, 1131, 1149]. Kratkoročni učinci navedenih pojava uključuju otežano disanje [1095, 1129, 1130, 1050–1052], povišenu srčanu frekvenciju (broj otkucaja srca) [1129, 1134, 1136, 1148, 1153] i frekvenciju disanja (broj udisaja) [1129, 1134, 1136, 1148], zbuđenost, dekoncentraciju, dezorijentaciju i smanjene psihomotoričke sposobnosti [1132, 1136, 1142, 1145, 1153, 1154], vrtoglavicu [1142], smanjene kognitivne sposobnosti (razmišljanje) [1142, 1145, 1154–1158], glavobolju (i po četiri glavobolje dnevno, djelomično i zbog iritacije vratnih živaca uslijed zatezanja vrpce oko ušiju) [1115, 1140, 1159–1161] te umor i iscrpljenost [1095, 1133, 1148, 1161–1165]. Budući da je ljudskom organizmu za funkcioniranje potrebna pravilna izmjena kisika i ugljikovog dioksida, očekivano je da opetovano nošenje maske na dulja razdoblja (npr. nekoliko sati dnevno) može dovesti do ozbiljnih učinaka na zdravlje i pojave novih bolesti kao što su povišeni krvni tlak, arterioskleroza, koronarna bolest srca (začepljenje krvnih žila oko srca), astma, neurološki poremećaji zbog oštećenja žila koje vode u mozak itd. [1086, 1095, 1133, 1148, 1161]. Nošenje maski može biti povezano i s kliničkim razinama tjeskobe i depresije [1125, 1138, 1155, 1166–1172], paničnim napadajima [1172–1174], osjećajem gubitka slobode i autonomije [1086, 1152, 1175], štetnim učincima na trudnoću [1086, 1133, 1135, 1141, 1176], poteškoćama u verbalnoj i neverbalnoj komunikaciji [1086, 1126, 1152, 1177–1179], trajnim oštećenjem glasnica zbog opetovanog glasnog govorenja [1178], smanjenom kvalitetom života [1144], smanjenim vidnim poljem i zamagljivanjem naočala koje može povećati rizik od nesreća i smanjiti radnu učinkovitost [1126, 1152, 1180], poteškoćama u prepoznavanju lica [1086, 1126] i poteškoćama u razumijevanju emocija kod drugih [1086, 1126].

Nošenje maske pokazano dovodi i do povećanja temperature i vlage pod maskom [1086, 1100, 1142, 1152, 1153, 1149, 1181], čemu slijedi nakupljanje virusa, bakterija i gljivica i na vanjskoj i unutarnjoj površini maske [1182–1185] čime se povećava rizik od virusnih, bakterijskih i gljivičnih infekcija [1182–1189] te kožnih poremećaja poput perioralnog dermatitisa, akni, osipa i svrbeža [1153, 1154, 1190–1196], i u slučajevima kada se maska nosi “ispravno”. U slučaju postojeće zaraze, udisanje dijela već izdišenog zraka i izdisanje kontaminiranog zraka u oči može dovesti do produljenja i pogoršanja postojećih simptoma, i u slučaju covid-19 [1100, 1026, 1197]. Od kožnih poremećaja zabilježeni su i pojava prolazne ili trajne hiperpigmentacije (uočljivo tamnjenje kože u području nošenja maske) [1191, 1193] te kontaktni dermatitis u vezi s osjetljivošću na industrijske sastojke u maskama poput formaldehida i tirama [1176, 1192, 1198]. Formaldehid je karcinogeni biocid koji se koristi kao industrijsko dezinfekcijsko sredstvo, a tiram je originalno pesticid i koroziv [1086]. Udisanje polipropilenskih vlakana iz maski može dovesti do iritacije nosne sluznice te posljedično hujavice i kihanja [1199]. Nošenje maske povezano je i sa smanjenim tokom sline i povećanim disanjem kroz usta što dovodi do suhoće ustiju i posljedično može povećati rizik od halitoze (smrad u ustima), gingivitisa (upala zubnih desni), kandidijaze (gljivična upala) i upale usana [1086, 1200, 1201].

Osobe koje nose masku imaju smanjenu radnu učinkovitost u usporedbi s osobama koje ne nose masku [1115, 1129, 1132, 1134, 1140, 1145, 1148, 1153, 1159, 1160, 1162, 1165, 1178, 1191, 1199, 1202].

Navedeni rizici mogu biti povećani kod djece [1086, 1095, 1126, 1139, 1148, 1203–1219]. Primjerice, jedno je istraživanje u kontekstu covid-19 provedeno na 25 930 djece ustanovilo da su maske bile povezane

s glavoboljom (kod 53 % djece), dekoncentriranošću (50 %), anhedonijom (klinički smanjenom motivacijom ili mogućnošću za doživljajem zadovoljstva; 49 %), poteškoćama u učenju (38 %), iscrpljenošću (37 %), a čak je 25 % djece zadovoljavalo uvjete za novu dijagnozu poremećaja tjeskobe uz visoku stopu prisutnosti noćnih mora [1206]. Očekivano je i da će mnogo djece imati zakašnjeli ili drugačije poremećeni razvoj govora i jezika, komunikacije, kognicije, obrade emocija i empatije ako su tijekom dojenačkog doba ili ranog djetinjstva kontinuirano bili izloženi bliskim osobama koje nose masku jer će, između ostalog, teško usvajati i prepoznavati glasove i nove riječi te teško usvajati i prepoznavati emocije te želje i namjere druge osobe, u oba slučaja jer je potrebno gledati govorniku u usta [1126]. Navedene su pojave karakteristične za neke psihijatrijske i neurološke razvojne poremećaje poput autizma [1220–1223]. Nošenje maske u učionici smanjuje usvajanje znanja i vještina jer maske ometaju komunikaciju i blokiraju emocionalne signale između nastavnika i učenika [1126].

Maske za odrasle u smanjenom izdanju koje se na raznim mjestima prodaju za djecu nisu odobrene za uporabu kod djece kao zaštitna medicinska oprema i nisu testirane za tu namjenu [1086, 1100, 1203].

S obzirom na navedeno, nejasno je zašto hrvatski zdravstveni djelatnici i dalje neutemeljeno inzistiraju na mjerama zatvaranja, zatvaranja škola odnosno održavanja tzv. e-nastave te nošenju maski ako je (1) učinkovitost takvih mjera u najmanju ruku sporna, (2) djeca nisu osjetljiva na covid-19, (3), djeca imaju smanjenu vjerojatnost da će zaraziti odrasle te (4) navedene mjere imaju vrlo zabrinjavajuće štetne učinke na zdravlje i razvoj djece, sugerirajući da će velik broj djece u Hrvatskoj u sljedećih nekoliko desetljeća patiti od raznih kroničnih oboljenja kao posljedica zatvaranja, zatvaranja škola i nošenja maski. Također je nejasno zašto zdravstveni djelatnici koji preko medija daju preporuke o zdravstvenom ponašanju ne informiraju javnost o mogućim ozbiljnim štetnim učincima tih mjera na aspekte javnog zdravstva i osobnog zdravlja nevezanog za covid-19, a u skladu sa Zakonom o zaštiti prava pacijenata [1224].

Ovo je bio samo kratki pregled nekih od problematičnih aspekata u trenutno proglašenoj pandemiji koji se ne tiču cjepiva. I druge pojave treba imati na umu u raspravama o djeci (i odraslima). Primjerice, povećana uporaba dezinfekcijskih sredstava za ruke i površine također može biti povezana s štetnim učincima na zdravlje [1225, 1226]. Moguć je razvoj kožnih reakcija poput iritantnog kontaktnog dermatitisa koji može dovesti do suhoće kože, svrbeža, eritema (upalno crvenilo) i krvarenja [1227–1229] te alergijskog kontaktnog dermatitisa koji može dovesti do pucanja kože od suhoće, ali i anafilakse [1230–1232]. Različiti su mehanizmi pretpostavljeni prema kojima uporaba dezinfekcijskih sredstava može dovesti do oboljenja, uključujući denaturaciju proteina u *stratum corneum* (najvišem sloju vanjskog sloja kože), promjene međustaničnih lipida, smanjenje kohezije korneocita i smanjenje mogućnosti *stratum corneum* da veže vodu [1225, 1233, 1234]. Opetovanim se korištenjem narušava lipidna barijera čime se omogućava sastojcima dezinfekcijskih sredstava da prodru dublje u slojeve kože i promjene floru kože, posljedično povećavajući prisutnost bakterijskih kolonija [1235–1239]. Uporaba dezinfekcijskih sredstava za ruke može dovesti do poremećaja sluznice nosa, usne šupljine i oči zbog diranja tih dijelova dezinficiranim rukama [1240–1241]. Veća dostupnost dezinfekcijskih sredstava u trenutno proglašenoj pandemiji povezana je s rastom slučajeva trovanja i oštećenja organa zbog nepravilne uporabe [1242–1246], čime su posebno pogođena djeca [1242, 1247]. Često pranje ruku sapunom u trenutno proglašenoj pandemiji također je povezano s dermatitisom [1248].

4. ZAKLJUČAK

U ovome kratkom pregledu odabrane literature vjerujem da sam dovoljno informacija i izvora za poticanje ozbiljne i javne rasprave o eventualnom cijepljenju djece protiv covid-19 i nastavku primjene tzv. mjera za suzbijanje pandemije. Očito je da postoje brojna pitanja o učinkovitosti i sigurnosti trenutnih cjepiva koja se moraju raspraviti kako bi se donijela smisljena i etična odluka.

Liječnici imaju dužnost obavijestiti osobe voljne cijepiti se o mogućim štetnim učincima na njihovo zdravlje. Obaviješteni pristanak pacijenta preduvjet je za primjenu terapije. Liječnici također moraju adekvatno reagirati u slučaju prisile pacijenta na cijepljenje.

Na državnoj bi se razini trebalo pod hitno započeti veliko istraživanje i kvalitetno skupljanje podataka o primjeni cjepiva kao i ostalih mjera.

Izjava o sukobu interesa

Autor izjavljuje da ne postoji sukob interesa.

Izjava o ograničenju odgovornosti

Svi stavovi u rukopisu su autorovi i ne predstavljaju nužno stavove Philippsovog sveučilišta u Marburgu.

Literatura

- [1] Mahase E (2020). Covid-19: WHO declares pandemic because of “alarming levels” of spread, severity, and inaction. *BMJ* 368, m1036. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.m1036>
- [2] Feinhandler I, Cilento B, Beauvais B, ... Fulton L (2020). Predictors of death rate during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Healthcare* 8(3), 339. <https://doi.org/10.3390/healthcare8030339>
- [3] Kang S-J, Jung SI (2020). Age-related morbidity and mortality among patients with COVID-19. *Infection & Chemotherapy* 52(2), 154. <https://doi.org/10.3947/ic.2020.52.2.154>
- [4] Scannell Bryan M, Sun J, Jagai J, ... Argos M (2021). Coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) mortality and neighborhood characteristics in Chicago. *Annals of Epidemiology* 56, 47–54.e5. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.annepidem.2020.10.011>
- [5] Niforatos JD, Melnick ER, Faust JS (2020). Covid-19 fatality is likely overestimated. *BMJ* 368, m1113. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.m1113>
- [6] Stafford N (2020). Covid-19: Why Germany’s case fatality rate seems so low. *BMJ* 369, m1395. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.m1395>

- [7] Davidson RM, Winey TR (2021). Vitamin C mitigating and rescuing from synergistic toxicity: Sodium fluoride, silicofluorides, aluminum salts, electromagnetic pollution, and SARS-CoV-2. *International Journal of Vaccine Theory, Practice, and Research* 1(2), 243–282. <https://www.ijvtp.com/index.php/IJVTPr/article/view/12>
- [8] Kostoff RN, Briggs MB, Porter AL, ... Tsatsakis A (2020). The under-reported role of toxic substance exposures in the COVID-19 pandemic. *Food and Chemical Toxicology* 145, 111687. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fct.2020.111687>
- [9] Ioannidis JPA, Axfors C, Contopoulos-Ioannidis DG (2020). Population-level COVID-19 mortality risk for non-elderly individuals overall and for non-elderly individuals without underlying diseases in pandemic epicenters. *Environmental Research* 188, 109890. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2020.109890>
- [10] Singh AK, Gillies CL, Singh R, ... Khunti K (2020). Prevalence of co-morbidities and their association with mortality in patients with COVID-19: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Diabetes, Obesity and Metabolism* 22(10), 1915–1924. <https://doi.org/10.1111/dom.14124>
- [11] Magdy Beshbishy A, Hetta HF, Hussein DE, ... Batiha GE-S (2020). Factors associated with increased morbidity and mortality of obese and overweight COVID-19 patients. *Biology* 9(9), 280. <https://doi.org/10.3390/biology9090280>
- [12] Gacche RN, Gacche RA, Chen J, ... Li G (2021). Predictors of morbidity and mortality in COVID-19. *European Review for Medical and Pharmacological Sciences* 25(3), 1684–1707. https://doi.org/10.26355/eurev_202102_24880
- [13] Mattern J, Vauloup-Fellous C, Zakaria H, ... Vivanti AJ (2020) Post lockdown COVID-19 seroprevalence and circulation at the time of delivery, France. *PLoS ONE* 15(10), e0240782. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0240782>
- [14] Comas-Herrera A, Zalakaín J, Lemmon E, ... Fernández J-L (2020, April 20). Mortality associated with COVID-19 in care homes: International evidence. *LTCcovid.org*. <https://ltccovid.org/2020/04/12/mortality-associated-with-covid-19-outbreaks-in-care-homes-early-international-evidence>
- [15] Biesalski HK (2020). Vitamin D deficiency and co-morbidities in COVID-19 patients: A fatal relationship? *NFS Journal* 20, 10–21. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nfs.2020.06.001>
- [16] Biesalski HK (2020). Corrigendum to “Vitamin D deficiency and co-morbidities in COVID-19 patients: A fatal relationship?” [NFS Journal 20 (2020) 10–21]. *NFS Journal* 21, 38. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nfs.2020.09.001>
- [17] Powell T, Bellin E, Ehrlich AR (2020). Older adults and Covid-19: The most vulnerable, the hardest hit. *The Hastings Center Report* 50(3), 61–63. <https://doi.org/10.1002/hast.1136>

- [18] Brann DH, Tsukahara T, Weinreb C, ... Datta SR (2020). Non-neuronal expression of SARS-CoV-2 entry genes in the olfactory system suggests mechanisms underlying COVID-19-associated anosmia. *Science Advances* 6(31), eabc5801. <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.abc5801>
- [19] Ameres M, Brandstetter S, Toncheva AA, ... Wellmann S (2020). Association of neuronal injury blood marker neurofilament light chain with mild-to-moderate COVID-19. *Journal of Neurology* 267(12), 3476–3478. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00415-020-10050-y>
- [20] Fox SE, Akmatbekov A, Harbert JL, ... Vander Heide RS (2020). Pulmonary and cardiac pathology in African American patients with COVID-19: An autopsy series from New Orleans. *The Lancet Respiratory Medicine* 8(7), 681–686. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s2213-2600\(20\)30243-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/s2213-2600(20)30243-5)
- [21] Rapkiewicz AV, Mai X, Carsons SE, ... Reynolds HR (2020). Megakaryocytes and platelet-fibrin thrombi characterize multi-organ thrombosis at autopsy in COVID-19: A case series. *EClinicalMedicine* 24, 100434. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eclinm.2020.100434>
- [22] Solomon IH, Normandin E, Bhattacharyya S, ... Sabeti P (2020). Neuropathological features of Covid-19. *New England Journal of Medicine* 383(10), 989–992. <https://doi.org/10.1056/nejmc2019373>
- [23] Kes P (2021). Akutno oštećenje bubrega u bolesnika s COVID-19: Izazov za nefrologe. *Acta medica Croatica* 75, 3–27. <https://hrcak.srce.hr/259143>
- [24] Soldevila B, Puig-Domingo M, Marazuela M (2021). Basic mechanisms of SARS-CoV-2 infection: What endocrine systems could be implicated? *Reviews in Endocrine and Metabolic Disorders*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11154-021-09678-6>
- [25] Ferenc T, Mrzljak A, Tabain I, Vilibić-Čavlek T (2021). Subacute thyroiditis: A neglected complication of SARS-CoV-2 infection. *Infektološki glasnik* 41(1), 22–26. <https://doi.org/10.37797/ig.41.1.4>
- [26] Kutleša M (2020). COVID-19 i citokinska oluja. *Medicus* 29(2), 151–153. <https://hrcak.srce.hr/244321>
- [27] Lešin Gaćina D, Ivkić PK, Škegro I, ... Vukojević N (2020). Oftalmološki aspekti COVID-19: Pregled literature i naše iskustvo. *Infektološki glasnik* 40(2), 64–67. <https://doi.org/10.37797/ig.40.2.4>
- [28] Bašić Kes V, Supanc V, Trkanjec Z, ... Kes P (2020). Neurološke manifestacije COVID-19: Preporuke za dijagnostiku i liječenje. *Acta medica Croatica* 74(4), 385–398. <https://hrcak.srce.hr/257000>
- [29] Lovrenčić-Huzjan A (2020). COVID-19 i pacijent s moždanim udarom. *Medicus* 29(2), 233–236. <https://hrcak.srce.hr/244335>
- [30] Budinčević H, Vidaković D, Jurlina H, Demarin V (2020). COVID-19 pandemic: Neurological aspects of the disease. *Rad CASA: Medical Sciences* 543(50–51), 3–10. <https://doi.org/10.21857/moxpjhwnqm>

- [31] Sarohan AR, Kızıl M, İnkaya AÇ, ... Cen O (2021). A novel hypothesis for COVID-19 pathogenesis: Retinol depletion and retinoid signaling disorder. *Cellular Signalling* 87, 110121. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cellsig.2021.110121>
- [32] Jemal A (2005). Trends in the leading causes of death in the United States, 1970–2002. *JAMA* 294(10), 1255. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.294.10.1255>
- [33] Lim D, Ha M, Song I (2014). Trends in the leading causes of death in Korea, 1983–2012. *Journal of Korean Medical Science* 29(12), 1597. <https://doi.org/10.3346/jkms.2014.29.12.1597>
- [34] Steffen A, Thom J, Jacobi F, ... Bätzing J (2020). Trends in prevalence of depression in Germany between 2009 and 2017 based on nationwide ambulatory claims data. *Journal of Affective Disorders* 271, 239–247. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jad.2020.03.082>
- [35] McElroy SL (2015). The epidemic of depression with obesity. *The Journal of Clinical Psychiatry* 76(10), e1340–e1342. <https://doi.org/10.4088/jcp.14com09722>
- [36] Polanczyk GV, Salum GA, Sugaya LS, ... Rohde LA (2015). Annual research review: A meta-analysis of the worldwide prevalence of mental disorders in children and adolescents. *Journal of Child Psychology and Psychiatry* 56(3), 345–365. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jcpp.12381>
- [37] Spitzer, M. (2021). Open schools! Weighing the effects of viruses and lockdowns on children. *Trends in Neuroscience and Education* 22, 100151. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tine.2021.100151>
- [38] Loraine JA (1981). Alcoholism: A new pandemic. *Contemporary Review* 238(1381), 75–81. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/11631821>
- [39] Roth J, Qiang X, Marbán SL, ... Lowell BC (2004). The obesity pandemic: Where have we been and where are we going? *Obesity Research* 12(S11), 88S–101S. <https://doi.org/10.1038/oby.2004.273>
- [40] Kohl HW 3rd, Craig CL, Lambert EV, ... Kahlmeier S (2012). The pandemic of physical inactivity: Global action for public health. *The Lancet* 380(9838), 294–305. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736\(12\)60898-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736(12)60898-8)
- [41] Wen CP, Wu X (2012). Stressing harms of physical inactivity to promote exercise. *The Lancet* 380(9838), 192–193. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736\(12\)60954-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736(12)60954-4)
- [42] Tišma V, Barić R, Karlović Vragolov M (2021). Kvaliteta života i motivacija za vježbanje adolescenata normalne i prekomjerne tjelesne mase. *Društvena istraživanja* 30(3), 533–552. <https://doi.org/10.5559/di.30.3.04>
- [43] Ding D, Lawson KD, Kolbe-Alexander TL, ... Pratt M (2016). The economic burden of physical inactivity: A global analysis of major non-communicable diseases. *The Lancet* 388(10051), 1311–1324. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736\(16\)30383-x](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736(16)30383-x)
- [44] Vitale S (2008). Prevalence of refractive error in the United States, 1999–2004. *Archives of Ophthalmology* 126(8), 1111–1119. <https://doi.org/10.1001/archophth.126.8.1111>

- [45] Williams KM, Verhoeven VJM, Cumberland P, ... Hammond CJ (2015). Prevalence of refractive error in Europe: The European Eye Epidemiology (E3) Consortium. *European Journal of Epidemiology* 30(4), 305–315. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10654-015-0010-0>
- [46] Williams KM, Kraphol E, Yonova-Doing E, ... Hammond CJ (2018). Early life factors for myopia in the British Twins Early Development Study. *British Journal of Ophthalmology* 103(8), 1078–1084. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bjophthalmol-2018-312439>
- [47] Tideman JW, Polling JR, van der Schans A, ... Klaver CCW (2016). Bijziendheid, een groeiend probleem. *Nederlands tijdschrift voor geneeskunde* 160, D803. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/27879184>
- [48] Melnick ER, Ioannidis JPA (2020). Should governments continue lockdown to slow the spread of covid-19? *BMJ* 369, m1924. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.m1924>
- [49] Seneff S, Nigh G (2021). Worse than the disease? Reviewing some possible unintended consequences of the mRNA vaccines against COVID-19. *International Journal of Vaccine Theory, Practice, and Research* 2(1), 38–79. <https://www.ijvtp.com/index.php/IJVTPr/article/view/23>
- [50] Kostoff RN, Calina D, Kanduc D, ... Tsatsakis A (2021). Why are we vaccinating children against COVID-19? *Toxicology Reports* 8, 1665–1684. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.toxrep.2021.08.010>
- [51] Kostoff RN, Calina D, Kanduc D, ... Tsatsakis A (2021). Erratum to “Why are we vaccinating children against COVID-19?” [Toxicol. Rep. 8C (2021) 1665–1684 / 1193]. *Toxicology Reports*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.toxrep.2021.10.003>
- [52] Shah SM, Alsaab HO, Rawas-Qalaji MM, Uddin MN (2021). A review on current COVID-19 vaccines and evaluation of particulate vaccine delivery systems. *Vaccines* 9(10), 1086. <https://doi.org/10.3390/vaccines9101086>
- [53] Palmer M, Bhakdi S (2021, July 23). The Pfizer mRNA vaccine: Pharmacokinetics and toxicity. *Doctors for COVID Ethics*. <https://doctors4covidethics.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/07/Pfizer-pharmacokinetics-and-toxicity.pdf>
- [54] Mahase, E. (2021). Covid vaccine could be rolled out to children by autumn. *BMJ* 372, n723. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.n723>
- [55] Iacobucci G (2021). Covid-19: Children aged 12–15 should be offered vaccine, say UK’s chief medical officers. *BMJ* 374, n2248. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.n2248>
- [56]
- [57] Pauček Šljivak M (2021, October 29). Može li nas spasiti cijepljenje djece? *Index.hr*. <https://www.index.hr/vijesti/clanak/moze-li-nas-spasiti-cijepljenje-djece/2314563.aspx>
- [58] P V, Vištica S (2020, December 15). Infektolog otkrio hoće li se djeca morati cijepiti protiv korone, a zamjenica ravnatelja HZJZ-a kad bi cjepivo moglo stići u Hrvatsku. *Dnevnik.hr*. <https://dnevnik.hr/vijesti/koronavirus/infektolog-goran-tesovic-otkrio-vise-o-pfizerovu-cjepivu-protiv-koronavirusa---632346.html>

- [59] Epoch Times (2021, December 13). Impfkampagne für Fünf- bis Elfjährige beginnt in dieser Woche. *The Epoch Times*. <https://www.epochtimes.de/politik/deutschland/corona-impfungen-mit-kindervakzin-starten-in-dieser-woche-a3664565.html>
- [60] Petit R (2021, October 27). Next up for COVID-19 vaccine is children as young as 6 months. *ABC Action News*. <https://www.abcactionnews.com/news/coronavirus/next-up-for-covid-19-vaccine-is-children-as-young-as-6-months>
- [61] Breslin M (2021, November 19). Fauci says babies and toddlers could be eligible for COVID-19 vaccine by early 2022. *The Hill*. <https://thehill.com/policy/healthcare/582380-fauci-says-babies-and-toddlers-could-be-eligible-for-covid-19-vaccine-by>
- [62] Gutman R (2021, November 5). COVID-vaccine mandates for kids are coming: But are they a good idea? *The Atlantic*. <https://www.theatlantic.com/health/archive/2021/11/kids-school-covid-vaccine-mandate/620622>
- [63] Epoch Times (2021, December 2). Söder für Impfpflicht ab zwölf Jahren – Handelsverband beklagt Milliardenbußen. *The Epoch Times*. <https://www.epochtimes.de/politik/deutschland/soeder-fuer-impfpflicht-ab-zwoelf-jahren-handelsverband-beklagt-milliardeneinbussen-a3657699.html>
- [64] Mihm A (2021, December 9). Österreich führt Impfpflicht ab 14 Jahre ein. *Frankfurter Allgemeine Zeitung*. <https://m.faz.net/aktuell/politik/ausland/oesterreich-fuehrt-allgemeine-corona-impfpflicht-ab-14-jahren-ein-17675604.amp.html>
- [65] Anonymous (2021, November 30). Regierung diskutiert Impfpflicht für Kinder unter 12. *Heute*. <https://www.heute.at/s/regierung-diskutiert-impfpflicht-fuer-unter-12-jaehrige-100176218>
- [66] Alphonso D (2021, December 10). Warum am Chip kein Weg vorbeiführt. *Die Welt*. <https://www.welt.de/kultur/deus-ex-machina/plus235577672>
- [67] Wolf K, Costanzo A (2021, December 12). Weshalb dieser Mann keinen Impfpass mehr braucht. *Bild*. <https://www.bild.de/regional/hamburg/hamburg-aktuell/dr-patrick-kramer-hat-sechs-implantate-unter-haut-der-gechipte-mann-78502820.bild.html>
- [68] Müller M (2021, December 12). Vom QR-Code zu COVID zur digitalen Identität. *The Epoch Times*. <https://www.epochtimes.de/wissen/vom-qr-code-zu-covid-zur-digitalen-identitaet-a3659367.html>
- [69] Blakely R, Lay K (2021, December 3). NHS will be plagued by Covid ‘for at least five years’. *The Times*. <https://www.thetimes.co.uk/article/nhs-will-be-plagued-by-covid-for-at-least-five-years-7v9010516>
- [70] Nelson S (2021, August 27). Biden, Fauci discuss requiring COVID booster shots every 5 months. *New York Post*. <https://nypost.com/2021/08/27/biden-and-fauci-discuss-covid-19-booster-shots-every-5-months>
- [71] Bild (2021, December 3). „Das Virus mutiert schneller, als ich erwartet habe“: Ugur Sahin zur aktuellen Corona-Lage in Zeiten von Omikron. *Bild*. <https://www.bild.de/ratgeber/2021/ratgeber/biontech-chef-das-virus-mutiert-schneller-als-ich-erwartet-habe-78431552.bild.html>

- [72] Epoch Times (2021, December 10). „Wir werden Corona auch in vier Jahren nicht ganz besiegen“. *The Epoch Times*. <https://www.epochtimes.de/politik/deutschland/wir-werden-corona-auch-in-vier-jahren-nicht-ganz-besiegen-a3663505.html>
- [73] Index Vijesti (2021, October 7). Pedijatrica: Ja ću cijepiti svoje dijete. *Index.hr*. <https://www.index.hr/vijesti/clanak/pedijatrica-ja-cu-cijepiti-svoje-dijete/2309185.aspx>
- [74] N1 Hrvatska (2021, October 28). Milanović: I djeca bi se trebala cijepiti, škole trebaju nastaviti s radom. *N1info*. <https://hr.n1info.com/vijesti/milanovic-i-djeca-bi-se-trebala-cijepiti-skole-trebaju-nastaviti-s-radom>
- [75] Pauček Šljivak M (2021, October 29). Može li nas spasiti cijepljenje djece? *Index.hr*. <https://www.index.hr/vijesti/clanak/moze-li-nas-spasiti-cijepljenje-djece/2314563.aspx>
- [76] Giulio P (2021). Covid-19 pandemic – All possible effective solutions to eradicate the problem: Cross-sectional analysis of clinical, socioeconomic, political and psychological profiles. *Archives of Community Medicine and Public Health* 7(2), 099–110. <https://doi.org/10.17352/2455-5479.000147>
- [77] Thirumdas R, Kothakota A, Pandiselvam R, ... Barba FJ (2021). Role of food nutrients and supplementation in fighting against viral infections and boosting immunity: A review. *Trends in Food Science & Technology* 110, 66–77. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tifs.2021.01.069>
- [78] Gaziano R, Pistoia ES, Campione E, ... Di Francesco P (2021). Immunomodulatory agents as potential therapeutic or preventive strategies for COVID-19. *European Review for Medical and Pharmacological Sciences* 25(11), 4174–4184. https://doi.org/10.26355/eurrev_202106_26061
- [79] Ahvanooei MRR, Norouzian MA, Vahmani P (2021). Beneficial effects of vitamins, minerals, and bioactive peptides on strengthening the immune system against COVID-19 and the role of cow's milk in the supply of these nutrients. *Biological Trace Element Research*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12011-021-03045-x>
- [80] Daei Sorkhabi A, Sarkesh A, Daei Sorkhabi A, ... Bannazadeh Baghi H (2021). Vitamin supplementation as a potential adjunctive therapeutic approach for COVID-19: Biological and clinical plausibility. *Journal of Basic and Clinical Physiology and Pharmacology*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1515/jbcpp-2021-0111>
- [81] Vlachou M, Siamidi A, Dedeloudi A, ... Papanastasiou I (2021). Pineal hormone melatonin as an adjuvant treatment for COVID-19 (review). *International Journal of Molecular Medicine* 47, 47. <https://doi.org/10.3892/ijmm.2021.4880>
- [82] Thornthwaite, JT, Strasser D, Loomis L (2021). How to kill a virus: Strengthening the immune system, reducing inflammation, relieving oxidative stress, early detection in the prevention and treatment of SARS-CoV-2 (COVID-19). *Acta Scientifica Microbiology* 4(2), 06–12. <https://doi.org/10.31080/asmi.2020.04.0760>

- [83] Srivastava A, Gupta RC, Doss RB, Lall R (2021). Trace minerals, vitamins and nutraceuticals in prevention and treatment of COVID-19. *Journal of Dietary Supplements*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19390211.2021.1890662>
- [84] Keflie TS, Biesalski HK (2021). Micronutrients and bioactive substances: Their potential roles in combating COVID-19. *Nutrition* 84, 111103. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nut.2020.111103>
- [85] Gröber U, Holick MF (2021). The coronavirus disease (COVID-19): A supportive approach with selected micronutrients. *International Journal for Vitamin and Nutrition Research*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1024/0300-9831/a000693>
- [86] Nakano T, Chiang K-C, Chen C-C, ... Goto S (2021). Sunlight exposure and phototherapy: Perspectives for healthy aging in an era of COVID-19. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* 18(20), 10950. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph182010950>
- [87] Borsche L, Glauner B, von Mendel J (2021). COVID-19 mortality risk correlates inversely with vitamin D3 status, and a mortality rate close to zero could theoretically be achieved at 50 ng/mL 25(OH)D3: Results of a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Nutrients* 13(10), 3596. <https://doi.org/10.3390/nu13103596>
- [88] Jain A, Chaurasia R, Sengar NS, ... Narain S (2020). Analysis of vitamin D level among asymptomatic and critically ill COVID-19 patients and its correlation with inflammatory markers. *Scientific Reports* 10, 20191. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-020-77093-z>
- [89] Ali N (2020). Role of vitamin D in preventing of COVID-19 infection, progression and severity. *Journal of Infection and Public Health* 13(10), 1373–1380. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jiph.2020.06.021>
- [90] Goddek S (2020). Vitamin D3 and K2 and their potential contribution to reducing the COVID-19 mortality rate. *International Journal of Infectious Diseases* 99, 286–290. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijid.2020.07.080>
- [91] Islam MT, Salehi B, Karampelas O, ... Calina D (2020). High skin melanin content, vitamin D deficiency and immunity: Potential interference for severity of COVID-19. *Farmacia* 68(6), 970–983. <https://doi.org/10.31925/farmacia.2020.6.3>
- [92] Islam MT, Quispe C, Martorell M, ... Sharifi-Rad J (2021). Dietary supplements, vitamins and minerals as potential interventions against viruses: Perspectives for COVID-19. *International Journal for Vitamin and Nutrition Research*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1024/0300-9831/a000694>
- [93] Sidiropoulou P, Docea A, Nikolaou V, ... Drakoulis N (2020). Unraveling the roles of vitamin D status and melanin during Covid-19 (review). *International Journal of Molecular Medicine* 47(1), 92–100. <https://doi.org/10.3892/ijmm.2020.4802>
- [94] Yaseen MO, Jamshaid H, Saif A, Hussain T (2021). Immunomodulatory role and potential utility of various nutrients and dietary components in SARS-CoV-2 infection. *International Journal for Vitamin and Nutrition Research*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1024/0300-9831/a000715>

- [95] Samad N, Dutta S, Sodunke TE, ... Haque M (2021). Fat-soluble vitamins and the current global pandemic of COVID-19: Evidence-based efficacy from literature review. *Journal of Inflammation Research* 14, 2091–2110. <https://doi.org/10.2147/jir.s307333>
- [96] Turrubiates-Hernández F, Sánchez-Zuno G, González-Estevez G, ... Muñoz-Valle J (2021). Potential immunomodulatory effects of vitamin D in the prevention of severe coronavirus disease 2019: An ally for Latin America (review). *International Journal of Molecular Medicine* 47(4), 32. <https://doi.org/10.3892/ijmm.2021.4865>
- [97] Niño DA, Mora-Plazas M, Poveda E (2021). Vitamina D, sus posibles efectos en la función inmune y la respuesta ante la COVID-19: Una revisión sistemática exploratoria. *Revista de nutrición clínica y metabolismo* 4(3), 73–97. <https://doi.org/10.35454/rncm.v4n3.278>
- [98] Benskin LL (2020). A basic review of the preliminary evidence that COVID-19 risk and severity is increased in vitamin D deficiency. *Frontiers in Public Health* 8, 513. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2020.00513>
- [99] Zhang J, McCullough PA, Tecson KM (2020). Vitamin D deficiency in association with endothelial dysfunction: Implications for patients with COVID-19. *Reviews in Cardiovascular Medicine* 21(3), 339. <https://doi.org/10.31083/j.rcm.2020.03.131>
- [100] Biesalski HK (2020). Obesity, vitamin D deficiency and old age a serious combination with respect to coronavirus disease-2019 severity and outcome. *Current Opinion in Clinical Nutrition & Metabolic Care* 24(1), 18–24. <https://doi.org/10.1097/mco.0000000000000700>
- [101] Bennouar S, Cherif AB, Kessira A, ... Abdi S (2021). Vitamin D deficiency and low serum calcium as predictors of poor prognosis in patients with severe COVID-19. *Journal of the American College of Nutrition* 40(2), 104–110. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07315724.2020.1856013>
- [102] Farid N, Rola N, Koch EAT, Nakhoul N (2021). Active vitamin D supplementation and COVID-19 infections: Review. *Irish Journal of Medical Science* 190, 1271–1274. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11845-020-02452-8>
- [103] Boulkrane MS, Ilina V, Melchakov R, ... Baranenko D (2020) COVID-19 disease and vitamin D: A mini-review. *Frontiers in Pharmacology* 11, 604579. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fphar.2020.604579>
- [104] Bui L, Zhu Z, Hawkins S, ... Bellon A (2021). Vitamin D regulation of the immune system and its implications for COVID-19: A mini review. *SAGE Open Medicine* 9, 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1177/20503121211014073>
- [105] Taha R, Abureesh S, Alghamdi S, ... Abdulkhaliq A (2021). The relationship between vitamin D and infections including COVID-19: Any hopes? *International Journal of General Medicine* 14, 3849–3870. <https://doi.org/10.2147/ijgm.s317421>
- [106] AlSafar H, Grant WB, Hijazi R, ... Al Anouti F (2021). COVID-19 disease severity and death in relation to vitamin D status among SARS-CoV-2-positive UAE residents. *Nutrients* 13(5), 1714. <https://doi.org/10.3390/nu13051714>

- [107] Shah K, Varna VP, Pandya A, Saxena D (2021). Low vitamin D levels and prognosis in a COVID-19 pediatric population: A systematic review. *QJM* 114(7), 447–453. <https://doi.org/10.1093/qjmed/hcab202>
- [108] Ramaiah P, Elfaki BAAM, Mustafa HEM (2020). Battle with COVID-19: Role of vitamin D and zinc as a preventive strategy. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Research International* 32(21), 32–39. <https://doi.org/10.9734/jpri/2020/v32i2130750>
- [109] Menshawey E, Menshawey R, Nabeh OA (2021). Shedding light on vitamin D: The shared mechanistic and pathophysiological role between hypovitaminosis D and COVID-19 risk factors and complications. *Inflammopharmacology* 29, 1017–1031. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10787-021-00835-6>
- [110] O’Shea PM, Griffin TP, Brennan M, Mulkerrin EC (2020). COVID-19: The older adult and the importance of vitamin D sufficiency. *Journal of Nutritional Science* 9, e40. <https://doi.org/10.1017/jns.2020.36>
- [111] Purnama DI, Kusuma WLF, Purnama DK (2021). The role of vitamin D and cardiovascular risk in COVID-19 patients. *Cardiovascular and Metabolic Science* 32(3), 149–156. <https://doi.org/10.35366/101309>
- [112] Haug EG, de Lalouvière D, Isharc L (2020). Vitamin D and COVID-19: Is there a lack of risk/reward understanding among health authorities? [Preprint]. *ResearchGate*. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13972.12164>
- [113] Szponar L, Matczuk E (2021). SARS-CoV-2: Nutritional determinants of reducing the risk of infection of the central nervous system. *Postępy psychiatrii i neurologii* 30(2), 130–140. <https://doi.org/10.5114/ppn.2021.108477>
- [114] Maloney S, Maloney MR (2020). Determination of optimal active vitamin D levels to decrease COVID-19 viral replication and to mitigate its secondary inflammation [Preprint]. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3671169>
- [115] Abdollahzadeh R, Shushizadeh MH, Barazandehrokh M, ... Heidarzadehpilehrood R (2021). Association of vitamin D receptor gene polymorphisms and clinical/severe outcomes of COVID-19 patients. *Infection, Genetics and Evolution* 96, 105098. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.meegid.2021.105098>
- [116] Sarohan AR (2020). COVID-19: Endogenous retinoic acid theory and retinoic acid depletion syndrome. *Medical Hypotheses* 144, 110250. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mehy.2020.110250>
- [117] Turrubiates-Hernández FJ, Hernández-Bello J, Oregón-Romero E, ... Muñoz-Valle JF (2021). Participación de la vitamina A en la producción de IgA secretora en el epitelio del tracto respiratorio para la potencial protección de infección por SARS-CoV-2. *Revista alergia México* 68(3), 185–197. <https://doi.org/10.29262/ram.v68i3.977>
- [118] Hemilä H, Chalker E (2019). Vitamin C can shorten the length of stay in the ICU: A meta-analysis. *Nutrients* 11(4), 708. <https://doi.org/10.3390/nu11040708>

- [119] Simonson W (2020). Vitamin C and coronavirus. *Geriatric Nursing* 41(3), 331–332. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gerinurse.2020.05.002>
- [120] Ali AM, Kunugi H, Abdelmageed HA, ... Hendawy AO (2021). Vitamin K in COVID-19: Potential anti-COVID-19 properties of fermented milk fortified with bee honey as a natural source of vitamin K and probiotics. *Fermentation* 7(4), 202. <https://doi.org/10.3390/fermentation7040202>
- [121] Rico-Campà A, Martínez-González MA, Alvarez-Alvarez I, ... Bes-Rastrollo M (2019). Association between consumption of ultra-processed foods and all cause mortality: SUN prospective cohort study. *BMJ* 365, 11949. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.11949>
- [122] Muley A, Medithi S (2021). Nutritional aspects related to COVID-19: A bibliometric analysis using Scopus database. *Library Philosophy and Practice* 2021, 5159. <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/5159>
- [123] Galimberti A, Cena H, Campone L, ... Labra M (2020). Rethinking urban and food policies to improve citizens safety after COVID-19 pandemic. *Frontiers in Nutrition* 7, 569542. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnut.2020.569542>
- [124] Tran HTT, Gigl M, Le NPK, ... Lamy E (2021). In vitro effect of *Taraxacum officinale* leaf aqueous extract on the interaction between ACE2 cell surface receptor and SARS-CoV-2 spike protein D614 and four mutants. *Pharmaceuticals* 14(10), 1055. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ph14101055>
- [125] Barber MS, Barrett R, Bradley RD, Walker E (2021). A naturopathic treatment approach for mild and moderate COVID-19: A retrospective chart review. *Complementary Therapies in Medicine* 63, 102788. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ctim.2021.102788>
- [126] Meyer Letona A, Columbié Pileta M, Piedrasanta AR (2021). Fitoterapia de la Medicina Tradicional China para combatir de forma exitosa la covid-19. *Revista Cubana de tecnología de la salud* 12(2), 117–128. <http://revtecnologia.sld.cu/index.php/tec/article/view/2407>
- [127] Sharifi-Rad J, Rodrigues CF, Stojanović-Radić Z, ... Calina D (2020). Probiotics: Versatile bioactive components in promoting human health. *Medicina* 56(9), 433. <https://doi.org/10.3390/medicina56090433>
- [128] Dicker D, Bettini S, Farpour-Lambert N, ... Busetto L (2020). Obesity and COVID-19: The two sides of the coin. *Obesity Facts* 13(4), 430–438. <https://doi.org/10.1159/000510005>
- [129] Sattar N, Valabhji J (2021). Obesity as a risk factor for severe COVID-19: Summary of the best evidence and implications for health care. *Current Obesity Reports* 10, 282–289. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13679-021-00448-8>
- [130] Dietz W, Santos-Burgoa C (2020). Obesity and its implications for COVID-19 mortality. *Obesity* 28(6), 1005. <https://doi.org/10.1002/oby.22818>
- [131] Stefan N, Birkenfeld AL, Schulze MB, Ludwig DS (2020). Obesity and impaired metabolic health in patients with COVID-19. *Nature Reviews Endocrinology* 16(7), 341–342. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41574-020-0364-6>

- [132] Hoang U, Jones NR (2020, April 29). Is there an association between exposure to air pollution and severity of COVID-19 infection? *The Centre for Evidence-Based Medicine*. <https://www.cebm.net/covid-19/is-there-an-association-between-exposure-to-air-pollution-and-severity-of-covid-19-infection>
- [133] Travaglio M, Yu Y, Popovic R, ... Martins LM (2021). Links between air pollution and COVID-19 in England. *Environmental Pollution* 268, 115859. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2020.115859>
- [134] Wu X, Nethery RC, Sabath MB, ... Dominici F (2020). Air pollution and COVID-19 mortality in the United States: Strengths and limitations of an ecological regression analysis. *Science Advances* 6(45), eabd4049. <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.abd4049>
- [135] Cole MA, Ozgen C, Strobl E (2020). Air pollution exposure and COVID-19 [Preprint]. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3628242>
- [136] Rubik B, Brown RB (2021). Evidence for a connection between COVID-19 and exposure to radiofrequency radiation from wireless communications including 5G. *Journal of Clinical and Translational Research* 7(5), 7. <https://doi.org/10.18053/jctres.07.202105.007>
- [137] Doyon PR, Johansson O (2017). Electromagnetic fields may act via calcineurin inhibition to suppress immunity, thereby increasing risk for opportunistic infection: Conceivable mechanisms of action. *Medical Hypotheses* 106, 71–87. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mehy.2017.06.028>
- [138] Kostoff RN, Heroux P, Aschner M, Tsatsakis A (2020). Adverse health effects of 5G mobile networking technology under real-life conditions. *Toxicology Letters* 323, 35–40. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.toxlet.2020.01.020>
- [139] Piszczek P, Wójcik-Piotrowicz K, Gil K, Kaszuba-Zwoińska J (2021). Immunity and electromagnetic fields. *Environmental Research* 200, 111505. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2021.111505>
- [140] Anonymous (2021, February 9). Cijepljenje protiv COVID-19 bolesti: Najčešća pitanja i odgovori. *Službena stranica Vlade za pravodobne i točne informacije o koronavirusu*. <https://www.koronavirus.hr/o-covidu/892>
- [141] ClinicalTrials.gov [Internet]. BioNTech, Pfizer. 2020 Apr 29 – . Identifier NCT04368728, *Study to Describe the Safety, Tolerability, Immunogenicity, and Efficacy of RNA Vaccine Candidates Against COVID-19 in Healthy Individuals*. <https://clinicaltrials.gov/ct2/show/NCT04368728>
- [142] ClinicalTrials.gov [Internet]. Moderna TX, Inc. 2020 Jul 27 – . Identifier NCT04470427, *A Study to Evaluate Efficacy, Safety, and Immunogenicity of mRNA-1273 Vaccine in Adults Aged 18 Years and Older to Prevent COVID-19*. <https://clinicaltrials.gov/ct2/show/NCT04368728>
- [143] Young R, Bekele T, Gunn A, ... Yamey G (2020). Developing new health technologies for neglected diseases: A pipeline portfolio review and cost model. *Gates Open Research* 2, 23. <https://doi.org/10.12688/gatesopenres.12817.3>

- [144] Polack FP, Thomas SJ, Kitchin N, A... Gruber WC (2020). Safety and efficacy of the BNT162b2 mRNA Covid-19 vaccine. *New England Journal of Medicine* 383(27), 2603–2615. <https://doi.org/10.1056/nejmoa2034577>
- [145] Doshi P (2020). Will covid-19 vaccines save lives? Current trials aren't designed to tell us. *BMJ* 371, m4037. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.m4037>
- [146] Doshi P (2020). Covid-19 vaccine trial protocols released. *BMJ* 371, m4058. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.m4058>
- [147] Doshi P (2021, January 4). Peter Doshi – Pfizer and Moderna's "95% effective" vaccines: We need more details and the raw data. *The BMJ Opinion*. <https://blogs.bmj.com/bmj/2021/01/04/peter-doshi-pfizer-and-modernas-95-effective-vaccines-we-need-more-details-and-the-raw-data>
- [148] Doshi P (2021, February 5). Clarification – Pfizer and Moderna's "95% effective" vaccines: We need more details and the raw data. *The BMJ Opinion*. <https://blogs.bmj.com/bmj/2021/02/05/clarification-pfizer-and-modernas-95-effective-vaccines-we-need-more-details-and-the-raw-data>
- [149] Anonymous (2020, July 27). Phase 3 clinical trial of investigational vaccine for COVID-19 begins. *National Institutes of Health*. <https://www.nih.gov/news-events/news-releases/phase-3-clinical-trial-investigational-vaccine-covid-19-begins>
- [150] Topol EJ (2020, September 9). Paul Offit's biggest concern about COVID vaccines. *Medscape*. <https://www.medscape.com/viewarticle/936937>
- [151] Hussey C, Budwick D, Talukdar L (2020, June 11). Moderna advances late-stage development of its vaccine (mRNA-1273) against COVID-19. *Business Wire*. <https://www.businesswire.com/news/home/20200611005456/en/Moderna-Advances-Late-Stage-Development-Vaccine-mRNA-1273-COVID-19>
- [152] Brown RB (2021). Outcome reporting bias in COVID-19 mRNA vaccine clinical trials. *Medicina* 57(3), 199. <https://doi.org/10.3390/medicina57030199>
- [153] Ali T, Mujawar S, Sowmya AV, ... Chaudhury S (2021). Dangers of mRNA vaccines. *Industrial Psychiatry Journal* 30(3), 291–293. <https://doi.org/10.4103/0972-6748.328833>
- [154] Doshi P (2021). Covid-19 vaccines: In the rush for regulatory approval, do we need more data? *BMJ* 373, n1244. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.n1244>
- [155] Thacker PD (2021). Covid-19: Researcher blows the whistle on data integrity issues in Pfizer's vaccine trial. *BMJ* 375, n2635. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.n2635>
- [156] BioNTech, Pfizer (2020). A Phase 1/2/3, placebo-controlled, randomized, observer-blind, dose-finding study to evaluate the safety, tolerability, immunogenicity, and efficacy of SARS-CoV-2 RNA vaccine candidates against COVID-19 in healthy individuals. *Pfizer, Inc.* https://media.tghn.org/medialibrary/2020/11/C4591001_Clinical_Protocol_Nov2020_Pfizer_BioNTech.pdf

- [157] Corbett KS, Edwards DK, Leist SR, A... Graham BS (2020). SARS-CoV-2 mRNA vaccine design enabled by prototype pathogen preparedness. *Nature* 586(7830), 567–571. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-020-2622-0>
- [158] Lu J, Lu G, Tan S, ... Lin J (2020). A COVID-19 mRNA vaccine encoding SARS-CoV-2 virus-like particles induces a strong antiviral-like immune response in mice. *Cell Research* 30(10), 936–939. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41422-020-00392-7>
- [159] Mautone K (2021, November 19). FDA says it needs until year 2076 to reveal data pertaining to Pfizer vaccine approval. *MSN*. <https://www.msn.com/en-us/news/us/fda-says-it-needs-until-year-2076-to-reveal-data-pertaining-to-pfizer-vaccine-approval/ar-AAQSOWp>
- [160] Shaheen M (2021, November 19). FDA says it wants 55 YEARS to process FOIA requests about COVID-19 vaccines – meaning data may not be available to the public until 2076. *Daily Mail Online*. <https://www.dailymail.co.uk/health/article-10222035/FDA-says-need-55-YEARS-make-vaccine-related-information-available-public.html>
- [161] Jarić Dauenhauer N (2021, August 25). Ne, cjepiva nisu eksperimentalna. *Index.hr*. <https://www.index.hr/vijesti/clanak/ne-cjepiva-nisu-eksperimentalna/2299169.aspx>
- [162] Kampf G (2021). COVID-19: Stigmatising the unvaccinated is not justified. *The Lancet* 398(10314), 1871. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736\(21\)02243-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736(21)02243-1)
- [163] Hernández AF, Calina D, Poulas K, ... Tsatsakis AM (2021). Safety of COVID-19 vaccines administered in the EU: Should we be concerned? *Toxicology Reports* 8, 871–879. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.toxrep.2021.04.003>
- [164] Tanveer S, Rowhani-Farid A, Hong K, ... Doshi P (2021). Transparency of COVID-19 vaccine trials: Decisions without data. *BMJ Evidence-Based Medicine*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjebm-2021-111735>
- [165] Godlee F (2021). Covid 19: A strong pandemic response relies on good data. *BMJ* 375, n2668. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.n2668>
- [166] Paul E, Brown GW, Kalk A, Ridde V (2021). Playing vaccine roulette: Why the current strategy of staking everything on Covid-19 vaccines is a high-stakes wager. *Vaccine* 39(35), 4921–4924. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.vaccine.2021.07.045>
- [167] Kostoff RN, Kanduc D, Porter AL, ... Tsatsakis A (2020). Vaccine- and natural infection-induced mechanisms that could modulate vaccine safety. *Toxicology Reports* 7, 1448–1458. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.toxrep.2020.10.016>
- [168] Haidere MF, Ratan ZA, Nowroz S, ... Cho JY (2021). COVID-19 vaccine: Critical questions with complicated answers. *Biomolecules & Therapeutics* 29(1), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.4062/biomolther.2020.178>

- [169] Kanduc, D., Shoenfeld, Y. (2020). Molecular mimicry between SARS-CoV-2 spike glycoprotein and mammalian proteomes: Implications for the vaccine. *Immunologic Research* 68, 310–313. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12026-020-09152-6>
- [170] Rose J (2021). A report on the US vaccine adverse events reporting system (VAERS) of the COVID-19 messenger ribonucleic acid (mRNA) biologicals. *Science, Public Health Policy, and the Law* 2, 59–80. https://www.publichealthpolicyjournal.com/_files/ugd/adf864_a0a813acbfdc4534a8cb50cf85193d49.pdf
- [171] Suzuki YJ, Gychka SG (2021). SARS-CoV-2 spike protein elicits cell signaling in human host cells: Implications for possible consequences of COVID-19 vaccines. *Vaccines* 9(1), 36. <https://doi.org/10.3390/vaccines9010036>
- [172] Kelleni MT (2021). Sars Cov-2 vaccination autoimmunity, antibody dependent Covid-19 enhancement and other potential risks: Beneath the tip of the iceberg. *International Journal of Pulmonary & Respiratory Sciences* 5(2), 555658. <https://doi.org/10.19080/IJOPRS.2021.05.555658>
- [173] Yahi N, Chahinian H, Fantini J (2021). Infection-enhancing anti-SARS-CoV-2 antibodies recognize both the original Wuhan/D614G strain and Delta variants: A potential risk for mass vaccination? *Journal of Infection*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jinf.2021.08.010>
- [174] Edafese Alakpa G (2021). Vaccine against SARS-COV-2, questions arising: Just another citizen’s opinion. *Advances in Bioscience and Bioengineering* 9(2), 55. <https://doi.org/10.11648/j.abb.20210902.16>
- [175] Labidi AH (2021). The anti SARS-CoV-2 vaccines and the questions they raise. *International Journal of Advanced Research* 9(4), 578–598. <https://doi.org/10.21474/ijar01/12734>
- [176] Catalán V, Rodríguez A, Becerril S, ... Frühbeck G (2021). The ‘new normality’ in research? What message are we conveying our medical students? *European Journal of Clinical Investigation* 51(9), e13586. <https://doi.org/10.1111/eci.13586>
- [177] Karwaciak I, Sałkowska A, Karaś K, ... Ratajewski M (2021). Nucleocapsid and spike proteins of the coronavirus SARS-CoV-2 induce IL6 in monocytes and macrophages: Potential implications for cytokine storm syndrome. *Vaccines* 9(1), 54. <https://doi.org/10.3390/vaccines9010054>
- [178] Azakarian P (2021). Mechanisms that could increase cancer vulnerability in COVID-19 mRNA vaccine recipients [Preprint]. *OSF Preprints*. <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/2ts54>
- [179] Igyártó BZ, Jacobsen S, Ndeupen S (2021). Future considerations for the mRNA-lipid nanoparticle vaccine platform. *Current Opinion in Virology* 48, 65–72. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.coviro.2021.03.008>
- [180] Poole J (2021). Covid-19 vaccination side-effects & reactions: Indicated homoeopathic remedies [Unpublished]. *ResearchGate*. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/349493987>
- [181] Kostoff R, Briggs M, Porter A, ... Tsatsakis A (2020). COVID-19 vaccine safety. *International Journal of Molecular Medicine* 46(5), 1599–1602. <https://doi.org/10.3892/ijmm.2020.4733>

- [182] Calina D, Docea A, Petrakis D, ... Tsatsakis A (2020). Towards effective COVID-19 vaccines: Updates, perspectives and challenges (review). *International Journal of Molecular Medicine* 46(1), 3–16. <https://doi.org/10.3892/ijmm.2020.4596>
- [183] Kowarz E, Krutzke L, Reis J, ... Marschalek R (2021). “Vaccine-induced Covid-19 mimicry” syndrome: Splice reactions within the SARS-CoV-2 Spike open reading frame result in Spike protein variants that may cause thromboembolic events in patients immunized with vector-based vaccines [Preprint]. *Research Square*. <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-558954/v1>
- [184] Sahelian R (2021, December 2). Covid vaccine side effects. *Ray Sahelian*. <https://www.raysahelian.com/covidvaccinesideeffects.html>
- [185] Calina D, Hernández AF, Hartung T, ... Docea AO (2021). Challenges and scientific prospects of the newest generation of mRNA-based vaccines against SARS-CoV-2. *Life* 11(9), 907. <https://doi.org/10.3390/life11090907>
- [186] Juhl Jørgensen K, Auken M, Brinth L, ... Jefferson T (2020). Suspicions of possible vaccine harms must be scrutinised openly and independently to ensure confidence. *npj Vaccines* 5, 55. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41541-020-0202-9>
- [187] McKernan K, Kyriakopoulos AM, McCullough PA (2021). Differences in vaccine and SARS-CoV-2 replication derived mRNA: Implications for cell biology and future disease [Preprint]. *OSF Preprints*. <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/bcsa6>
- [188] Paul E, Brown GW, Dechamps M, ... Zizi M (2021). COVID-19: An ‘extraterrestrial’ disease? *International Journal of Infectious Diseases* 110,155–159. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijid.2021.07.051>
- [189] Tinari S, Riva C (2021). Donuts, drugs, booze, and guns: What governments are offering people to take covid-19 vaccines. *BMJ* 374, n1737. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.n1737>
- [190] Couey JJ, Stover PL (2021). 5 concerns about SARS-CoV2 biology: A call to pause, deliberate and revise policy. *MacRyan*. https://www.macryan.com/wp-content/uploads/2021/07/SARS2parentsReview_CoueyJJ.pdf
- [191] Benucci M, Infantino M, Manfredi M, ... Caproni M (2021). Covid vaccination in patients with autoimmune diseases treated with mycophenolate: Let’s think back to the recommendations. *Autoimmunity Reviews* 20(10), 102908. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.autrev.2021.102908>
- [192] Block J (2021). US college covid-19 vaccine mandates don’t consider immunity or pregnancy, and may run foul of the law. *BMJ* 373, n1397. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.n1397>
- [193] Block J (2021). Vaccinating people who have had covid-19: Why doesn’t natural immunity count in the US? *BMJ* 374, n2101. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.n2101>
- [194] Anonymous (2021). Vaccinating people who have had covid-19: Why doesn’t natural immunity count in the US? *BMJ* 374, n2272. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.n2272>

- [195] Mohseni Afshar Z, Babazadeh A, Janbakhsh A, ... Ebrahimipour S (2021). Coronavirus disease 2019 (Covid-19) vaccination recommendations in special populations and patients with existing comorbidities. *Reviews in Medical Virology*, e2309. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1002/rmv.2309>
- [196] Berdine G (2021). Mandatory COVID vaccines and Fermi's paradox. *The Southwest Respiratory and Critical Care Chronicles* 9(39), 76–78. <https://doi.org/10.12746/swrccc.v9i39.833>
- [197] Ahmed A, Nezami M, Alkattan A (2021). Pitfalls at chemistry of adenoviral vector vaccine against COVID-19 and how to circumvent it. *Advanced Pharmaceutical Bulletin*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.34172/apb.2022.024>
- [198] Malhotra S (2021). Lessons from a vaccine contract. *Journal of Postgraduate Medicine, Education and Research* 55(4), 153–154. <https://doi.org/10.5005/jp-journals-10028-1454>
- [199] Gibson J (2020). Jabbing the economy back to life? *Working Papers in Economics* 21, 11. <https://ideas.repec.org/p/wai/econwp/21-11.html>
- [200] Simandan D, Rinner C, Capurri V (in press). Confronting the rise of authoritarianism during the COVID-19 pandemic should be a priority for critical geographers and social scientists. *ACME*. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/353934883>
- [201] Herndon JM, Whiteside M (2021). Viral environmental warfare: Technology Bill of Rights critically needed. *Advances in Social Sciences Research Journal* 8(11), 1–19. <https://doi.org/10.14738/assrj.811.11200>
- [202] Der subjektive Student (2021, November 30). Das Spiel mit dem Feuer: Die Impfpflicht und ihre möglichen Folgen. *Reitschuster*. <https://reitschuster.de/post/das-spiel-mit-dem-feuer>
- [203] Kennedy RF Jr (2021). *The Real Anthony Fauci: Bill Gates, Big Pharma, and the Global War on Democracy and Public Health*. New York, NY: Skyhorse Publishing – Children's Health Defense. <https://www.skyhorsepublishing.com/9781510766808/the-real-anthony-fauci>
- [204] Stoner V (2021, May 4). The deadly COVID-19 vaccine coverup. *Virginia Stoner*. <https://www.virginiastoner.com/writing/2021/5/4/the-deadly-covid-19-vaccine-coverup>
- [205] Mercola J, Cummins R (2021). *The Truth About COVID-19: Exposing The Great Reset, Lockdowns, Vaccine Passports, and the New Normal*. White River Junction, VT: Chelsea Green Publishing. <https://www.chelseagreen.com/product/the-truth-about-covid-19>
- [206] Petric D (2021). Can a multi-epitope vaccine be a solution for COVID-19 pandemic? *Academia Letters* 2021, 4010. <https://doi.org/10.20935/al4010>
- [207] Murphy WJ (2021). The urgent need for more basic research on SARS-Cov2 infection and vaccines in assessing potential psychoneurological effects using maternal immune activation (MIA) and other preclinical modeling. *Brain, Behavior, and Immunity* 97, 1–3. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bbi.2021.06.009>

- [208] Lazebnik Y (2021). Cell fusion as a link between the SARS-CoV-2 spike protein, COVID-19 complications, and vaccine side effects. *Oncotarget*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.18632/oncotarget.28088>
- [209] Beran, RG (2021). Astra zeneca Covid vaccination conversion reaction. *Global Journal of Medical and Clinical Case Reports* 8(2), 069–071. <https://doi.org/10.17352/2455-5282.000132>
- [210] Buttery JP (2021). Developing standard safety outcomes for COVID-19 vaccines. *Vaccine* 39(22), 3025–3027. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.vaccine.2021.03.004>
- [211] Munoz FM, Cramer JP, Dekker CL, ... Lambert PH (2021). Vaccine-associated enhanced disease: Case definition and guidelines for data collection, analysis, and presentation of immunization safety data. *Vaccine* 39(22), 3053–3066. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.vaccine.2021.01.055>
- [212] Riccardi B, Resta S (2021). The Covid virus infection – A critical review of the whole affair: Personal opinion. *International Journal of Clinical Skills* 15(7), 491–501. [https://doi.org/10.37532/1753-0431.2021.15\(7\).195](https://doi.org/10.37532/1753-0431.2021.15(7).195)
- [213] Brogna B, Bignardi E, Brogna C, ... Musto LA (2021). COVID-19 pneumonia in vaccinated population: A six clinical and radiological case series. *Medicina* 57(9), 891. <https://doi.org/10.3390/medicina57090891>
- [214] Hayawi K, Shahriar S, Serhani MA, ... Masud MM (2021). Vaccine versus variants (3Vs): Are the COVID-19 vaccines effective against the variants? A systematic review. *Vaccines* 9(11), 1305. <https://doi.org/10.3390/vaccines9111305>
- [215] Jain VK, Iyengar KP, Ish P (2021). Elucidating causes of COVID-19 infection and related deaths after vaccination. *Diabetes & Metabolic Syndrome: Clinical Research & Reviews* 15(5), 102212. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dsx.2021.102212>
- [216] Dolle F (2021, September 20). Münster: Inzwischen 85 Infizierte nach 2G-Party im Club. *WDR*. <https://www1.wdr.de/nachrichten/westfalen-lippe/corona-infektionen-clubbesuch-muenster-100.html>
- [217] Tober-Lau P, Schwarz T, Hillus D, ... Corman VM (2021). Outbreak of SARS-CoV-2 B.1.1.7 lineage after vaccination in long-term care facility, Germany, February–March 2021. *Emerging Infectious Diseases* 27(8), 2169–2173. <https://doi.org/10.3201/eid2708.210887>
- [218] Singanayagam A, Hakki S, Dunning J, ... Lackenby A (2021). Community transmission and viral load kinetics of the SARS-CoV-2 delta (B.1.617.2) variant in vaccinated and unvaccinated individuals in the UK: A prospective, longitudinal, cohort study. *The Lancet Infectious Diseases*. Online ahead of print. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s1473-3099\(21\)00648-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/s1473-3099(21)00648-4)
- [219] Brown CM, Vostok J, Johnson H, ... Laney AS (2021). Outbreak of SARS-CoV-2 infections, including COVID-19 vaccine breakthrough infections, associated with large public gatherings: Barnstable County, Massachusetts, July 2021. *Morbidity and Mortality Weekly Report* 70(31), 1059–1062. <https://doi.org/10.15585/mmwr.mm7031e2>

- [220] Baunez C, Degoulet M, Luchini S, ... Teschl M (2021). COVID-19 acceleration and vaccine status in France, summer 2021 [Preprint]. *medRxiv*. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2021.09.18.21263773>
- [221] Baunez C, Degoulet M, Luchini S, ... Teschl M (2021). COVID-19 acceleration and vaccine status in France, summer 2021 [Preprint]. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3933074>
- [222] Acharya CB, Schrom J, Mitchell AM, ... Havlir D (2021). No significant difference in viral load between vaccinated and unvaccinated, asymptomatic and symptomatic groups when infected with SARS-CoV-2 Delta variant [Preprint]. *medRxiv*. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2021.09.28.21264262>
- [223] Salvatore PP, Lee CC, Sleweon S, ... Hagan LM (2021). Transmission potential of vaccinated and unvaccinated persons infected with the SARS-CoV-2 Delta variant in a federal prison, July–August 2021 [Preprint]. *medRxiv*. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2021.11.12.21265796>
- [224] Servellita V, Sotomayor-Gonzalez A, Gliwa AS, ... Chiu, C. Y. (2021). Predominance of antibody-resistant SARS-CoV-2 variants in vaccine breakthrough cases from the San Francisco Bay Area, California [Preprint]. *medRxiv*. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2021.08.19.21262139>
- [225] Birhane M, Bressler S, Chang G, ... Thompson G (2021). COVID-19 vaccine breakthrough infections reported to CDC: United States, January 1–April 30, 2021. *Morbidity and Mortality Weekly Report* 70(21), 792–793. <https://doi.org/10.15585/mmwr.mm7021e3>
- [226] Hsu L, Wisplinghoff H, Kossow A, ... Schildgen V (2021). Limited protection against SARS-CoV-2 infection and virus transmission after mRNA vaccination. *Journal of Infection*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jinf.2021.06.023>
- [227] Ye P, Fry L, Liu H, ... Champion JD (2021). COVID outbreak after the 1st dose of COVID vaccine among the nursing home residents: What happened? *Geriatric Nursing* 42(5), 1105–1108. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gerinurse.2021.06.022>
- [228] Subramanian SV, Kumar A (2021). Increases in COVID-19 are unrelated to levels of vaccination across 68 countries and 2947 counties in the United States. *European Journal of Epidemiology*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10654-021-00808-7>
- [229] Bouanane M (2021). Weak or no correlation between recent COVID-19 data and vaccination rates in France [Preprint]. *Research Square*. <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-1028704/v1>
- [230] Beattie K (2021). Worldwide Bayesian causal impact analysis of vaccine administration on deaths and cases associated with COVID-19: A BigData analysis of 145 countries [Preprint]. *ResearchGate*. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.34214.65605>
- [231] Fenton N, Neil M, Mclachlan S (2021). Paradoxes in the reporting of Covid19 vaccine effectiveness: Why current studies (for or against vaccination) cannot be trusted and what we can do about it [Preprint]. *ResearchGate*. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.32655.30886>
- [232] Neil M, Fenton N, Mclachlan S (2021). Discrepancies and inconsistencies in UK Government datasets compromise accuracy of mortality rate comparisons between vaccinated and unvaccinated [Preprint]. *ResearchGate*. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.32817.10086>

- [233] Neil M, Fenton N, Smalley J, ... Rose J (2021). Latest statistics on England mortality data suggest systematic mis-categorisation of vaccine status and uncertain effectiveness of Covid-19 vaccination [Preprint]. *ResearchGate*. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.14176.20483>
- [234] McLachlan S (2021). Lies, damn lies and sham statistics: Simulation using poor quality estimation and assumption has hijacked public and health policymaking during COVID-19 [Preprint]. *ResearchGate*. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.31691.92960>
- [235] Kostoff RN, Briggs MB, Porter AL (2021). Toxicology issues related to the COVID-19 outbreak. In: AM Tsatsakis (Ed.). *Toxicological Risk Assessment and Multi-System Health Impacts from Exposure*. Amsterdam: Elsevier, 359–372. <https://doi.org/10.1016/b978-0-323-85215-9.00017-9>
- [236] Stang A, Robers J, Schonert B, ... Cullen P (2021). The performance of the SARS-CoV-2 RT-PCR test as a tool for detecting SARS-CoV-2 infection in the population. *Journal of Infection* 83(2), 237–279. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jinf.2021.05.022>
- [237] Hsu L, Wisplinghoff H, Kossow A, ... Schildgen V (2021). Limited protection against SARS-CoV-2 infection and virus transmission after mRNA vaccination. *Journal of Infection*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jinf.2021.06.023>
- [238] Velavan TP, Meyer CG (2021). COVID-19: A PCR-defined pandemic. *International Journal of Infectious Diseases* 103, 278–279. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijid.2020.11.189>
- [239] Klement RJ, Bandyopadhyay PS (2020). The epistemology of a positive SARS-CoV-2 test. *Acta Biotheoretica* 69, 359–375. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10441-020-09393-w>
- [240] Romero-Alvarez D, Garzon-Chavez D, Espinosa F, ... Reyes J (2021). Cycle threshold values in the context of multiple RT-PCR testing for SARS-CoV-2. *Risk Management and Healthcare Policy* 14, 1311–1317. <https://doi.org/10.2147/rmhp.s282962>
- [241] Cohen AN, Kessel B, Milgroom MG (2020). Diagnosing SARS-CoV-2 infection: The danger of over-reliance on positive test results [Preprint]. *medRxiv*. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2020.04.26.20080911>
- [242] Mouliou DS, Gourgoulianis KI (2021). False-positive and false-negative COVID-19 cases: Respiratory prevention and management strategies, vaccination, and further perspectives. *Expert Review of Respiratory Medicine* 15(8), 993–1002. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17476348.2021.1917389>
- [243] Cohen AN, Kessel B (2021). Prevalence of asymptomatic SARS-CoV-2 infection. *Annals of Internal Medicine* 174(2), 284–285. <https://doi.org/10.7326/120-1284>
- [244] Neil M, Fenton N, Maclachlan S, Osman M (2020). Don't panic: Limits to what we know about UK Covid-19 PCR testing, inferred infection rates and the rate of false positives [Preprint]. *ResearchGate*. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.10554.00966>
- [245] Esteve C, Catherine FX, Chavanet P, ... Piroth L (2020). How should a positive PCR test result for COVID-19 in an asymptomatic individual be interpreted and managed? *Médecine et maladies infectieuses* 50(8), 633–638. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.medmal.2020.09.014>

- [246] Mutevečić Turković A, Bećiragić A, Dervišević A, Ćorić A (2021). COVID-19 reinfection in a patient with endstage renal disease on chronic hemodialysis: Is it possible or is it inaccuracy of testing? *Acta medica Croatica* 75(2), 163–166. <https://hrcak.srce.hr/261273>
- [247] Yeadon M (2020, September 20). Lies, damned lies and health statistics: The deadly danger of false positives. *The Daily Sceptic*. <https://dailysceptic.org/lies-damned-lies-and-health-statistics-the-deadly-danger-of-false-positives>
- [248] Al Bayat S, Mundodan J, Hasnain S, ... Al-Thani MHJ (2021). Can the cycle threshold (Ct) value of RT-PCR test for SARS CoV2 predict infectivity among close contacts? *Journal of Infection and Public Health* 14(9), 1201–1205. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jiph.2021.08.013>
- [249] Neagu M, Calina D, Docea AO, ... Tsatsakis A (2021). Back to basics in COVID-19 – Antigens and antibodies: Completing the puzzle. *Journal of Cellular and Molecular Medicine* 25(10), 4523–4533. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jcmm.16462>
- [250] Mandavilli A (2020, August 29). Your coronavirus test is positive: Maybe it shouldn't be. *The New York Times*. <https://www.nytimes.com/2020/08/29/health/coronavirus-testing>
- [251] Carmen (2021, November 28). In Lake Louise, ten positive cases for Covid-19... Then only one in the end. *News in 24*. <https://new.in-24.com/News/345806.html>
- [252] Daon Y, Huppert A, Obolski U (2021). An accurate model for SARS-CoV-2 pooled RT-PCR test errors. *Royal Society Open Science* 8(11), 210704. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsos.210704>
- [253] Nordström P, Ballin M, Nordström A (2021). Effectiveness of Covid-19 vaccination against risk of symptomatic infection, hospitalization, and death up to 9 months: A Swedish total-population cohort study [Preprint]. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3949410>
- [254] Jo D-H, Minn D, Lim J, ... Kim K-N (2021). Rapidly declining SARS-CoV-2 antibody titers within 4 months after BNT162b2 vaccination. *Vaccines* 9(10), 1145. <https://doi.org/10.3390/vaccines9101145>
- [255] Feikin D, Higdon MM, Abu-Raddad LJ, ... Patel M (2021). Duration of effectiveness of vaccines against SARS-CoV-2 infection and COVID-19 disease: Results of a systematic review and meta-regression [Preprint]. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3961378>
- [256] Mishra SK, Pradhan SK, Pati S, ... Nanda RK (2021). Waning of anti-spike antibodies in AZD1222 (ChAdOx1) vaccinated healthcare providers: A prospective longitudinal study. *Cureus* 13(11), e19879. <https://doi.org/10.7759/cureus.19879>
- [257] Goldberg Y, Mandel M, Bar-On YM, ... Huppert A (2021). Waning immunity after the BNT162b2 vaccine in Israel. *New England Journal of Medicine* 385(24), e85. <https://doi.org/10.1056/nejmoa2114228>
- [258] Pellini R, Venuti A, Pimpinelli F, ... Ciliberto G (2021). Initial observations on age, gender, BMI and hypertension in antibody responses to SARS-CoV-2 BNT162b2 vaccine. *EClinicalMedicine* 36, 100928. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eclinm.2021.100928>

- [259] Pellini R, Venuti A, Pimpinelli F, ... Ciliberto G (2021). Obesity may hamper SARS-CoV-2 vaccine immunogenicity [Preprint]. *medRxiv*. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2021.02.24.21251664>
- [260] Watanabe M, Balena A, Tuccinardi D, ... Gnessi L (2021). Central obesity, smoking habit, and hypertension are associated with lower antibody titres in response to COVID-19 mRNA vaccine. *Diabetes/Metabolism Research and Reviews*, e3465. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1002/dmrr.3465>
- [261] Nomura Y, Sawahata M, Nakamura Y, ... Sugiyama K (2021). Age and smoking predict antibody titres at 3 months after the second dose of the BNT162b2 COVID-19 vaccine. *Vaccines* 9(9), 1042. <https://doi.org/10.3390/vaccines9091042>
- [262] Ledford H (2020). How obesity could create problems for a COVID vaccine. *Nature* 586(7830), 488–489. <https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-020-02946-6>
- [263] Knežević K (2021, February 9). Capakova pomoćnica: ‘Sva cjepiva koja stižu u Hrvatsku 100 posto štite od umiranja’. *Telegram*. <https://www.telegram.hr/politika-kriminal/capakova-pomocnica-sva-cjepiva-koja-stizu-u-hrvatsku-100-posto-stite-od-umiranja>
- [264] Pfizer Media Relations, Pfizer Investor Relations, Alatovic J, Maas S (2021, November 22). Follow-up data from Phase 3 trial of Pfizer-BioNTech COVID-19 vaccine support safety and high efficacy in adolescents 12 through 15 years of age. *Pfizer Inc.* <https://www.pfizer.com/news/press-release/press-release-detail/follow-data-phase-3-trial-pfizer-biontech-covid-19-vaccine>
- [265] Rose A, Stevo C, Alatovic J, Maas S (2021, September 19). Pfizer and BioNTech announce positive topline results from pivotal trial of COVID-19 vaccine in children 5 to 11 years. *Pfizer Inc.* <https://www.pfizer.com/news/press-release/press-release-detail/pfizer-and-biontech-announce-positive-topline-results>
- [266] Fiskens R (2021). How significant is the Ventavia scandal? *BMJ* 375, n2953. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.n2953>
- [267] Lyons-Weiler J (2020). Pathogenic priming likely contributes to serious and critical illness and mortality in COVID-19 via autoimmunity. *Journal of Translational Autoimmunity* 3, 100051. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jtauto.2020.100051>
- [268] Ehrenfeld M, Tincani A, Andreoli L, ... Shoenfeld Y (2020). Covid-19 and autoimmunity. *Autoimmunity Reviews* 19(8), 102597. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.autrev.2020.102597>
- [269] Carter MJ, Fish M, Jennings A, ... Shankar-Hari M (2020). Peripheral immunophenotypes in children with multisystem inflammatory syndrome associated with SARS-CoV-2 infection. *Nature Medicine* 26(11), 1701–1707. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41591-020-1054-6>
- [270] Galeotti C, Bayry J (2020). Autoimmune and inflammatory diseases following COVID-19. *Nature Reviews Rheumatology* 16(8), 413–414. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41584-020-0448-7>
- [271] Gao Z, Zhang H, Liu C, Dong K (2021). Autoantibodies in COVID-19: Frequency and function. *Autoimmunity Reviews* 20(3), 102754. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.autrev.2021.102754>

- [272] Suzuki YJ (2020). The viral protein fragment theory of COVID-19 pathogenesis. *Medical Hypotheses* 144, 110267. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mehy.2020.110267>
- [273] Suzuki YJ, Nikolaienko SI, Dibrova VA, ... Gychka SG (2021). SARS-CoV-2 spike protein-mediated cell signaling in lung vascular cells. *Vascular Pharmacology* 137, 106823. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.vph.2020.106823>
- [274] Buzhdygan TP, DeOre BJ, Baldwin-Leclair A, ... Ramirez SH (2020). The SARS-CoV-2 spike protein alters barrier function in 2D static and 3D microfluidic in-vitro models of the human blood–brain barrier. *Neurobiology of Disease* 146, 105131. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nbd.2020.105131>
- [275] Verma S, Saksena S, Sadri-Ardekani H (2020). ACE2 receptor expression in testes: Implications in coronavirus disease 2019 pathogenesis. *Biology of Reproduction* 103(3), 449–451. <https://doi.org/10.1093/biolre/ioaa080>
- [276] Rhea EM, Logsdon AF, Hansen KM, ... Erickson MA (2020). The S1 protein of SARS-CoV-2 crosses the blood-brain barrier in mice. *Nature Neuroscience* 24(3), 368–378. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41593-020-00771-8>
- [277] Matucci-Cerinic C, Caorsi R, Consolaro A, ... Ravelli A (2021). Multisystem inflammatory syndrome in children: Unique disease or part of the Kawasaki disease spectrum? *Frontiers in Pediatrics* 9, 680813. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fped.2021.680813>
- [278] Farooq A, Alam F, Saeed A, ... Abdullah M (2021). Multisystem inflammatory syndrome in children and adolescents (MIS-C) under the setting of COVID-19: A review of clinical presentation, workup and management. *Infectious Diseases: Research and Treatment* 14, 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1177/117863372111026642>
- [279] Hicar MD (2020). Antibodies and immunity during Kawasaki disease. *Frontiers in Cardiovascular Medicine* 7, 94. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fcvm.2020.00094>
- [280] Nielsen TM, Andersen NH, Torp-Pedersen C, ... Kragholm KH (2020). Kawasaki disease, autoimmune disorders, and cancer: A register-based study. *European Journal of Pediatrics* 180(3), 717–723. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00431-020-03768-4>
- [281] Lei Y, Zhang J, Schiavon CR, ... Shyy JY-J (2021). SARS-CoV-2 spike protein impairs endothelial function via downregulation of ACE 2. *Circulation Research* 128(9), 1323–1326. <https://doi.org/10.1161/circresaha.121.318902>
- [282] Nuovo GJ, Magro C, Shaffer T, ... Tili E (2021). Endothelial cell damage is the central part of COVID-19 and a mouse model induced by injection of the S1 subunit of the spike protein. *Annals of Diagnostic Pathology* 51, 151682. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anndiagpath.2020.151682>
- [283] Avolio E, Carrabba M, Milligan R, ... Madeddu P (2020). The SARS-CoV-2 Spike protein disrupts human cardiac pericytes function through CD147-receptor-mediated signalling: A potential non-infective mechanism of COVID-19 microvascular disease [Preprint]. *medRxiv*. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2020.12.21.423721>

- [284] Avolio E, Gamez M, Gupta K, ... Madeddu P (2020). The SARS-CoV-2 spike protein disrupts the cooperative function of human cardiac pericytes-endothelial cells through CD147 receptor-mediated signalling: A potential non-infective mechanism of COVID-19 microvascular disease [Preprint]. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3751324>
- [285] Asandei A, Mereuta L, Schiopu I, ... Luchian T (2020). Non-receptor-mediated lipid membrane permeabilization by the SARS-CoV-2 spike protein S1 subunit. *ACS Applied Materials & Interfaces* 12(50), 55649–55658. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsami.0c17044>
- [286] Vogel TP, Top KA, Karatzios C, ... Munoz FM (2021). Multisystem inflammatory syndrome in children and adults (MIS-C/A): Case definition & guidelines for data collection, analysis, and presentation of immunization safety data. *Vaccine* 39(22), 3037–3049. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.vaccine.2021.01.054>
- [287] Sharifi-Rad J, Rodrigues CF, Sharopov F, ... Calina D (2020). Diet, lifestyle and cardiovascular diseases: Linking pathophysiology to cardioprotective effects of natural bioactive compounds. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* 17(7), 2326. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17072326>
- [288] Sharifi-Rad M, Anil Kumar NV, Zucca P, ... Sharifi-Rad J (2020). Lifestyle, oxidative stress, and antioxidants: Back and forth in the pathophysiology of chronic diseases. *Frontiers in Physiology* 11, 694. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fphys.2020.00694>
- [289] Kuipers S, Cannegieter SC, Middeldorp S, ... Rosendaal FR (2007). The absolute risk of venous thrombosis after air travel: A cohort study of 8,755 employees of international organisations. *PLoS Medicine* 4(9), e290. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pmed.0040290>
- [290] Gundry SR (2021). Abstract 10712: mRNA COVID vaccines dramatically increase endothelial inflammatory markers and ACS risk as measured by the PULS Cardiac Test: A warning. *Circulation* 144(Suppl_1), A10712. https://doi.org/10.1161/circ.144.suppl_1.10712
- [291] Anonymous (2021). Expression of concern: Abstract 10712: mRNA COVID vaccines dramatically increase endothelial inflammatory markers and ACS risk as measured by the PULS Cardiac Test: A warning. *Circulation*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1161/cir.0000000000001051>
- [292] Ogata AF, Cheng C-A, Desjardins M, ... Walt DR (2021). Circulating severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) vaccine antigen detected in the plasma of mRNA-1273 vaccine recipients. *Clinical Infectious Diseases*, ciab465. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1093/cid/ciab465>
- [293] Bahl K, Senn JJ, Yuzhakov O, ... Ciaramella G (2017). Preclinical and clinical demonstration of immunogenicity by mRNA vaccines against H10N8 and H7N9 influenza viruses. *Molecular Therapy* 25(6), 1316–1327. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ymthe.2017.03.035>
- [294] Stokes A, Pion J, Binazon O, ... Rodriguez L-A (2020). Nonclinical safety assessment of repeated administration and biodistribution of a novel rabies self-amplifying mRNA vaccine in rats. *Regulatory Toxicology and Pharmacology* 113, 104648. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.yrtph.2020.104648>

- [295] Committee for Medicinal Products for Human Use (2021, March 11). Assessment report – COVID-19 vaccine Moderna: Procedure No. EMEA/H/C/005791/0000. *European Medicines Agency*. https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/documents/assessment-report/spikevax-previously-covid-19-vaccine-moderna-epar-public-assessment-report_en.pdf
- [296] Pharmacovigilance Risk Assessment Committee (2021, March 24). Signal assessment report on embolic and thrombotic events (SMQ) with COVID-19 vaccine (ChAdOx1-S [recombinant]): EPITT no:19683. *European Medicines Agency*. https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/documents/prac-recommendation/signal-assessment-report-embolic-thrombotic-events-smq-covid-19-vaccine-chadox1-s-recombinant-covid_en.pdf
- [297] Pfizer (2021). SARS-CoV-2 mRNA vaccine (BNT162, PF-07302048). *Pmda Pharmaceuticals and Medical Devices Agency*. https://www.pmda.go.jp/drugs/2021/P20210212001/672212000_30300AMX00231_I100_1.pdf
- [298] Worldwide Safety, Pfizer (2021, April 30). Cumulative analysis of post-authorization adverse event reports of PF-07302048 (BNT162b2) received through 28-Feb-2021. *Public Health and Medical Professionals for Transparency*. <https://phmpt.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/11/5.3.6-postmarketing-experience.pdf>
- [299] Giubilini A, Gupta S, Heneghan C (2021). A focused protection vaccination strategy: Why we should not target children with COVID-19 vaccination policies. *Journal of Medical Ethics* 47(8), 565–566. <https://doi.org/10.1136/medethics-2021-107700>
- [300] Zimmermann P, Pittet LF, Finn A, ... Curtis N (2021). Should children be vaccinated against COVID-19? *Archives of Disease in Childhood*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1136/archdischild-2021-323040>
- [301] Li G, Finn A, Pollard AJ (2021). Should we be vaccinating children against COVID-19 in high-income countries? *Expert Review of Vaccines* 20(9), 1043–1046. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14760584.2021.1951245>
- [302] Sundborn G, Thornley S, Scott R, ... Bridle B (2021, November 3). Should caution be exercised in the rollout of covid-19 vaccines to NZ children from 5 years old? History indicates rushed decisions lead to regret. *Covid Plan B*. <https://www.covidplanb.co.nz/our-posts/should-caution-be-exercised-in-the-rollout-of-covid-19-vaccines-to-nz-children-from-5-years-old-history-indicates-rushed-decisions-lead-to-regret>
- [303] Banoun H (2021). Clinical trials of Covid vaccines in adolescents: Do the EMA and FDA have access to the same data? [Preprint]. *Qeios*. <https://doi.org/10.32388/kp77nw>
- [304] Ioannidis JPA (2021). COVID-19 vaccination in children and university students. *European Journal of Clinical Investigation* 51(11), e13678. <https://doi.org/10.1111/eci.13678>
- [305] Verd S, Fernández-Bernabeu M, Cardo E (2021). The controversy surrounding vaccination of young people against COVID-19. *Acta Paediatrica*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1111/apa.16156>

- [306] Milota T, Strizova Z, Smetanova J, Sediva A (2021). An immunologist's perspective on anti-COVID-19 vaccines. *Current Opinion in Allergy & Clinical Immunology* 21(6), 545–552. <https://doi.org/10.1097/aci.0000000000000788>
- [307] Palmer M, Bhakdi S (2021, October 4). Expert statement regarding the use of Moderna COVID-19-mRNA-vaccine in children. *Doctors for COVID Ethics*. <https://doctors4covidethics.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/10/expertise-moderna2.pdf>
- [308] Palmer M, Bhakdi S, Hockertz S (2021, July 7). Expert evidence regarding Comirnaty (Pfizer) COVID-19 mRNA vaccine for children. *Doctors for COVID Ethics*. https://doctors4covidethics.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/07/expertise-published_15.07.pdf
- [309] The Israeli Professional Ethics Front (2021, October 21). Professional Ethics Front's letter to FDA concerning the administration of COVID-19 vaccines to children aged 5–11. *Doctors for COVID Ethics*. <https://doctors4covidethics.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/10/FDA-October-21st-letter.pdf>
- [310] Buchhorn R, Meyer C, Schulze-Forster K, ... Heidecke H (2021). Autoantibody release in children after Corona virus mRNA vaccination: A risk factor of multisystem inflammatory syndrome? *Vaccines* 9(11), 1353. <https://doi.org/10.3390/vaccines9111353>
- [311] Doshi P (2018). Pandemrix vaccine: Why was the public not told of early warning signs? *BMJ* 362, k3948. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.k3948>
- [312] Miller NZ (2021). Vaccines and sudden infant death: An analysis of the VAERS database 1990–2019 and review of the medical literature. *Toxicology Reports* 8, 1324–1335. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.toxrep.2021.06.020>
- [313] Miller NZ, Goldman GS (2011). Infant mortality rates regressed against number of vaccine doses routinely given: Is there a biochemical or synergistic toxicity? *Human & Experimental Toxicology* 30(9), 1420–1428. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0960327111407644>
- [314] Juhl Jørgensen K, Auken M, Brinth L, ... Jefferson T (2020). Suspicions of possible vaccine harms must be scrutinised openly and independently to ensure confidence. *npj Vaccines* 5, 55. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41541-020-0202-9>
- [315] Trogen B, Oshinsky D, Caplan A (2020). Adverse consequences of rushing a SARS-CoV-2 vaccine. *JAMA* 323(24), 2460–2461. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.2020.8917>
- [316] Avorn J, Kesselheim A (2020). Regulatory decision-making on COVID-19 vaccines during a public health emergency. *JAMA* 324(13), 1284–1285. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.2020.17101>
- [317] Offit PA (2008). *The Cutter Incident: How America's First Polio Vaccine Led to the Growing Vaccine Crisis*. New Haven, CT: Yale University Press. <https://doi.org/10.12987/9780300130379>
- [318] Offit PA (2005). The Cutter incident, 50 years later. *New England Journal of Medicine* 352(14), 1411–1412. <https://doi.org/10.1056/nejmp048180>

- [319] Brandon WP (2001). In the age of bioterrorism, an affair to remember: The silver anniversary of the swine flu epidemic that never was. *Politics and the Life Sciences* 20(1), 85–90. <https://doi.org/10.1017/s0730938400005207>
- [320] Fineberg HV (2009). Swine flu of 1976: Lessons from the past. *Bulletin of the World Health Organization* 87(6), 414–415. <https://doi.org/10.2471/blt.09.040609>
- [321] Keil U, Schönhöfer P, Spelsberg A (2011). The invention of the swine-flu pandemic. *European Journal of Epidemiology* 26, 187. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10654-011-9573-6>
- [322] Rose J (2021). Critical appraisal of VAERS pharmacovigilance: Is the U.S. Vaccine Adverse Events Reporting System (VAERS) a functioning pharmacovigilance system? *Science, Public Health Policy, and the Law* 3, 100–129. https://cf5e727d-d02d-4d71-89ff-9fe2d3ad957f.filesusr.com/ugd/adf864_0490c898f7514df4b6fbc5935da07322.pdf
- [323] Miller ER, McNeil MM, Moro PL, ... Su JR (2020). The reporting sensitivity of the Vaccine Adverse Event Reporting System (VAERS) for anaphylaxis and for Guillain-Barré syndrome. *Vaccine* 38(47), 7458–7463. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.vaccine.2020.09.072>
- [324] Ausic S (2021, December 10). Pathologie-Konferenz: Corona-Impfung bei 12 von 15 Todesfällen mitursächlich. *The Epoch Times*. <https://www.epochtimes.de/china/china-medizin/pathologie-konferenz-corona-impfung-bei-12-von-15-todesfaellen-mitursaechlich-a3661063.html>
- [325] Ausic S (2021, October 4). Wirbel um Pathologie-Konferenz. *The Epoch Times*. <https://www.epochtimes.de/wissen/forschung/wirbel-um-pathologie-konferenz-a3609398.html>
- [326] Ausic S (2021, December 4). Corona-Impfung: Zweite Pathologie-Konferenz präsentiert Obduktionsergebnisse. *The Epoch Times*. <https://www.epochtimes.de/wissen/forschung/jetzt-live-zweite-pathologie-konferenz-praesentiert-obduktionsergebnisse-von-corona-geimpften-a3658395.html>
- [327] Ndeupen S, Qin Z, Jacobsen S, ... Igyártó BZ (2021). The mRNA-LNP platform’s lipid nanoparticle component used in preclinical vaccine studies is highly inflammatory. *iScience* 24(12), 103479. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.isci.2021.103479>
- [328] Mohamed M, Abu Lila AS, Shimizu T, ... Ishida T (2019). PEGylated liposomes: Immunological responses. *Science and Technology of Advanced Materials* 20(1), 710–724. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14686996.2019.1627174>
- [329] Wenande E, Garvey LH (2016). Immediate-type hypersensitivity to polyethylene glycols: A review. *Clinical & Experimental Allergy* 46(7), 907–922. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cea.12760>
- [330] Stone CA Jr, Liu Y, Relling MV, ... Phillips EJ (2019). Immediate hypersensitivity to polyethylene glycols and polysorbates: More common than we have recognized. *The Journal of Allergy and Clinical Immunology: In Practice* 7(5), P1533–1540.e8. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaip.2018.12.003>
- [331] Sellaturay P, Nasser S, Ewan P (2021). Polyethylene glycol-induced systemic allergic reactions (anaphylaxis). *The Journal of Allergy and Clinical Immunology: In Practice* 9(2), P670–P675. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaip.2020.09.029>

- [332] Kozma GT, Mészáros T, Vashegyi I, ... Szebeni J (2019). Pseudo-anaphylaxis to polyethylene glycol (PEG)-coated liposomes: Roles of anti-PEG IgM and complement activation in a porcine model of human infusion reactions. *ACS Nano* 13(8), 9315–9324. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsnano.9b03942>
- [333] Hamad I, Hunter AC, Szebeni J, Moghimi SM (2008). Poly(ethylene glycol)s generate complement activation products in human serum through increased alternative pathway turnover and a MASP-2-dependent process. *Molecular Immunology* 46(2), 225–232. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.molimm.2008.08.276>
- [334] Zhou Z-H, Stone CA Jr, Jakubovic B, ... Kozlowski S (2021). Anti-PEG IgE in anaphylaxis associated with polyethylene glycol. *The Journal of Allergy and Clinical Immunology: In Practice* 9(4), 1731–1733.e3. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaip.2020.11.011>
- [335] Yang Q, Lai SK (2015). Anti-PEG immunity: Emergence, characteristics, and unaddressed questions. *Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews: Nanomedicine and Nanobiotechnology* 7(5), 655–677. <https://doi.org/10.1002/wnan.1339>
- [336] Abu Lila AS, Shimizu T, Ishida T (2018). PEGylation and anti-PEG antibodies. In: A Parambath (ed.). *Engineering of Biomaterials for Drug Delivery Systems: Beyond Polyethylene Glycol*. Woodhead Publishing, 51–68. <https://doi.org/10.1016/b978-0-08-101750-0.00003-9>
- [337] Hong L, Wang Z, Wei X, ... Li C (2020). Antibodies against polyethylene glycol in human blood: A literature review. *Journal of Pharmacological and Toxicological Methods* 102, 106678. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.vascn.2020.106678>
- [338] Gachoka D (2015). Polyethylene glycol (PEG)-induced anaphylactic reaction during bowel preparation. *ACG Case Reports Journal* 2(1), 216–218. <https://doi.org/10.14309/crj.2015.63>
- [339] Lee SH, Cha JM, Lee JI, ... Cho Y-H (2015). Anaphylactic shock caused by ingestion of polyethylene glycol. *Intestinal Research* 13(1), 90–94. <https://doi.org/10.5217/ir.2015.13.1.90>
- [340] Povsic TJ, Lawrence MG, Lincoff AM, ... Levinson AI (2016). Pre-existing anti-PEG antibodies are associated with severe immediate allergic reactions to pegnivacogin, a PEGylated aptamer. *Journal of Allergy and Clinical Immunology* 138(6), 1712–1715. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaci.2016.04.058>
- [341] Wylon K, Dölle S, Worm M (2016). Polyethylene glycol as a cause of anaphylaxis. *Allergy, Asthma & Clinical Immunology* 12, 67. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13223-016-0172-7>
- [342] Ganson NJ, Povsic TJ, Sullenger BA, ... Hershfield MS (2016). Pre-existing anti-polyethylene glycol antibody linked to first-exposure allergic reactions to pegnivacogin, a PEGylated RNA aptamer. *Journal of Allergy and Clinical Immunology* 137(5), 1610–1613.e7. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaci.2015.10.034>
- [343] Kelso JM (2021). Anaphylactic reactions to novel mRNA SARS-CoV-2/COVID-19 vaccines. *Vaccine* 39(6), 865–867. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.vaccine.2020.12.084>
- [344] Sellaturay P, Nasser S, Islam S, ... Ewan PW (2021). Polyethylene glycol (PEG) is a cause of anaphylaxis to the Pfizer/BioNTech mRNA COVID-19 vaccine. *Clinical & Experimental Allergy* 51(6), 861–863. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cea.13874>

- [345] Hatziantoniou S, Maltezou HC, Tsakris A, ... Anastassopoulou C (2021). Anaphylactic reactions to mRNA COVID-19 vaccines: A call for further study. *Vaccine* 39(19), 2605–2607. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.vaccine.2021.03.073>
- [346] Alhumaid S, Al Mutair A, Al Alawi Z, ... Al-Omari A (2021). Anaphylactic and nonanaphylactic reactions to SARS-CoV-2 vaccines: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Allergy, Asthma & Clinical Immunology* 17, 109. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13223-021-00613-7>
- [347] Arcolaci A, Bronte V, Zanoni G (2021). Immunization practices and risk of anaphylaxis: A current update, comprehensive of COVID-19 vaccination data. *Current Opinion in Allergy & Clinical Immunology* 21(5), 418–425. <https://doi.org/10.1097/aci.0000000000000769>
- [348] Ünsal H, Şekerel BE, Şahiner ÜM (2021). Allergic reactions against Covid-19 vaccines. *Turkish Journal of Medical Sciences* 51, 2233–2242. <https://doi.org/10.3906/sag-2104-329>
- [349] Shukla SC, Pandit S, Soni D, Gogtay NJ (2021). Evaluation of allergic reactions following COVID-19 vaccination in patients with documented allergies. *Journal of the Association of Physicians of India* 69(10), 11–12. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/34781647>
- [350] Frank A, Radparvar S, Manasia A, ... Kohli-Seth R (2021). Prolonged anaphylaxis to Pfizer coronavirus disease 2019 vaccine: A case report and mechanism of action. *Critical Care Explorations* 3(4), e0397. <https://doi.org/10.1097/cce.0000000000000397>
- [351] Blumenthal KG, Robinson LB, Camargo CA Jr, ... Wickner P (2021). Acute allergic reactions to mRNA COVID-19 vaccines. *JAMA* 325(15), 1562. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.2021.3976>
- [352] Garvey LH, Nasser S (2021). Anaphylaxis to the first COVID-19 vaccine: Is polyethylene glycol (PEG) the culprit? *British Journal of Anaesthesia* 126(3), e106–e108. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bja.2020.12.020>
- [353] Shimabukuro TT, Cole M, Su JR (2021). Reports of anaphylaxis after receipt of mRNA COVID-19 vaccines in the US: December 14, 2020–January 18, 2021. *JAMA* 325(11), 1101. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.2021.1967>
- [354] McNeil MM, Weintraub ES, Duffy J, ... DeStefano F (2016). Risk of anaphylaxis after vaccination in children and adults. *Journal of Allergy and Clinical Immunology* 137(3), 868–878. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaci.2015.07.048>
- [355] Su JR, Moro PL, Ng CS, ... Cano MV (2019). Anaphylaxis after vaccination reported to the Vaccine Adverse Event Reporting System, 1990–2016. *Journal of Allergy and Clinical Immunology* 143(4), 1465–1473. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaci.2018.12.1003>
- [356] Vojdani A, Kharrazian D. (2020). Potential antigenic cross-reactivity between SARS-CoV-2 and human tissue with a possible link to an increase in autoimmune diseases. *Clinical Immunology* 217, 108480. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clim.2020.108480>
- [357] Talotta R (2021). Do COVID-19 RNA-based vaccines put at risk of immune-mediated diseases? In reply to “Potential antigenic cross-reactivity between SARS-CoV-2 and human tissue with a possible

link to an increase in autoimmune diseases". *Clinical Immunology* 224, 108665. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clim.2021.108665>

[358] Vojdani A, Vojdani E, Kharrazian D (2021). Reaction of human monoclonal antibodies to SARS-CoV-2 proteins with tissue antigens: Implications for autoimmune diseases. *Frontiers in Immunology* 11, 617089. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fimmu.2020.617089>

[359] Kelleni M (2021). SARS CoV-2 adenovirus and RNA based vaccines potential autoimmune complications: Could we lower the chances? [Preprint]. *Authorea*. <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.160677062.20686503/v3>

[360] Sachinidis A, Garyfallos A (2021). COVID-19 vaccination can occasionally trigger autoimmune phenomena, probably via inducing age-associated B cells. *International Journal of Rheumatic Diseases*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1756-185x.14238>

[361] Pujol A, Gómez L-A, Gallegos C, ... Masmiquel L (2021). Thyroid as a target of adjuvant autoimmunity/inflammatory syndrome due to mRNA-based SARS-CoV2 vaccination: From Graves' disease to silent thyroiditis. *Journal of Endocrinological Investigation*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40618-021-01707-0>

[362] Ratnayake GM, Dworakowska D, Grossman AB (2021). Can COVID-19 immunisation cause subacute thyroiditis? *Clinical Endocrinology*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cen.14555>

[363] Siolos A, Gartzonika K, Tigas S (2021). Thyroiditis following vaccination against COVID-19: Report of two cases and review of the literature. *Metabolism Open* 12, 100136. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.metop.2021.100136>

[364] Das L, Bhadada SK, Sood A (2021). Post-COVID-vaccine autoimmune/inflammatory syndrome in response to adjuvants (ASIA syndrome) manifesting as subacute thyroiditis. *Journal of Endocrinological Investigation*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40618-021-01681-7>

[365] Oyibo SO (2021). Subacute thyroiditis after receiving the adenovirus-vectored vaccine for coronavirus disease (COVID-19). *Cureus* 13(6), e16045. <https://doi.org/10.7759/cureus.16045>

[366] İremli BG, Şendur SN, Ünlütürk U (2021). Three cases of subacute thyroiditis following SARS-CoV-2 vaccine: Postvaccination ASIA syndrome. *The Journal of Clinical Endocrinology & Metabolism* 106(9), 2600–2605. <https://doi.org/10.1210/clinem/dgab373>

[367] Lee KA, Kim YJ, Jin HY (2021). Thyrotoxicosis after COVID-19 vaccination: Seven case reports and a literature review. *Endocrine* 74, 470–472. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12020-021-02898-5>

[368] Chatzi S, Karampela A, Spiliopoulou C, Boutzios G (2021). Subacute thyroiditis after SARS-CoV-2 vaccination: A report of two sisters and summary of the literature. *Hormones*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42000-021-00332-z>

[369] Bornemann C, Woyk K, Bouter C (2021). Case report: Two cases of subacute thyroiditis following SARS-CoV-2 vaccination. *Frontiers in Medicine* 8, 737142. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmed.2021.737142>

- [370] Rebollar AF (2021). Tiroiditis subaguda despues de la vacuna anti SARS-CoV-2 (Ad5-nCoV). *Enfermedades infecciosas y microbiología clínica*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eimc.2021.10.015>
- [371] Vera-Lastra O, Ordinola Navarro A, Cruz Domiguez MP, ... Jara LJ (2021). Two cases of Graves' disease following SARS-CoV-2 vaccination: An autoimmune/inflammatory syndrome induced by adjuvants. *Thyroid* 31(9), 1436–1439. <https://doi.org/10.1089/thy.2021.0142>
- [372] Jeeyavudeen MS, Patrick AW, Gibb FW, Dover AR (2021). COVID-19 vaccine-associated subacute thyroiditis: An unusual suspect for de Quervain's thyroiditis. *BMJ Case Reports* 14, e246425. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bcr-2021-246425>
- [373] Sigstad E, Grøholt KK, Westerheim O (2021). Subakutt tyreoiditt etter vaksinerer mot SARS-CoV-2. *Tidsskrift for den norske legeförening*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.4045/tidsskr.21.0554>
- [374] Plaza-Enriquez L, Khatiwada P, Sanchez-Valenzuela M, Sikha A (2021). A case report of subacute thyroiditis following mRNA COVID-19 vaccine. *Case Reports in Endocrinology* 2021, 8952048. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2021/8952048>
- [375] Mungmunpantipantip R, Wiwanitkit V (2021). Thyrotoxicosis after COVID-19 vaccination. *Endocrine*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12020-021-02922-8>
- [376] Kyriacou A, Ioakim S, Syed AA (2021). COVID-19 vaccination and a severe pain in the neck. *European Journal of Internal Medicine* 94, 95–96. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejim.2021.10.008>
- [377] Patel KR, Cunnane ME, Deschler DG (2022). SARS-CoV-2 vaccine-induced subacute thyroiditis. *American Journal of Otolaryngology* 41(1), 103211. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.amjoto.2021.103211>
- [378] di Filippo L, Castellino L, Giustina A (2021). Occurrence and response to treatment of Graves' disease after COVID vaccination in two male patients. *Endocrine*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12020-021-02919-3>
- [379] Pierman G, Delgrange E, Jonas C (2021). Recurrence of Graves' disease (a Th1-type cytokine disease) following SARS-CoV-2 mRNA vaccine administration: A simple coincidence? *European Journal of Case Reports in Internal Medicine* 8(9), 002807. https://doi.org/10.12890/2021_002807
- [380] Mungmunpantipantip R, Wiwanitkit V (2021). Abnormal thyroid function following COVID-19 vaccination. *Indian Journal of Endocrinology and Metabolism* 25(2), 169. https://doi.org/10.4103/ijem.ijem_286_21
- [381] Rubinstein TJ (2021). Thyroid eye disease following COVID-19 vaccine in a patient with a history Graves' disease: A case report. *Ophthalmic Plastic & Reconstructive Surgery* 37(6), e221–e223. <https://doi.org/10.1097/iop.0000000000002059>
- [382] Sriphrapadang C, Shantavasinkul PC (2021). Graves' disease following SARS-CoV-2 vaccination. *Endocrine* 74, 473–474. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12020-021-02902-y>

- [383] Zettinig G, Krebs M (2021). Two further cases of Graves' disease following SARS-Cov-2 vaccination. *Journal of Endocrinological Investigation*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40618-021-01650-0>
- [384] Sriphrapadang C (2021). Aggravation of hyperthyroidism after heterologous prime-boost immunization with inactivated and adenovirus-vectored SARS-CoV-2 vaccine in a patient with Graves' disease. *Endocrine* 74, 226–227. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12020-021-02879-8>
- [385] Patrizio A, Ferrari SM, Antonelli A, Fallahi P (2021). A case of Graves' disease and type 1 diabetes mellitus following SARS-CoV-2 vaccination. *Journal of Autoimmunity* 125, 102738. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaut.2021.102738>
- [386] Farley S, Ousley R, Van Wagoner N, Bril F (2021). Autoimmunity after coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) vaccine: A case of acquired hemophilia A. *Thrombosis and Haemostasis* 121(12), 1674–1676. <https://doi.org/10.1055/a-1579-5396>
- [387] Harenberg J, Marchetti M, Falanga A (2021). Acquired autoimmune hemophilia following SARS-CoV-2 vaccines: Dual-drug effects on blood coagulation and the Scylla and Charybdis phenomenon. *Thrombosis and Haemostasis* 121(12), 1555–1557. <https://doi.org/10.1055/a-1658-4852>
- [388] Chavez A, Pougner C (2021). A case of COVID-19 vaccine associated new diagnosis myasthenia gravis. *Journal of Primary Care & Community Health* 12, 1–3. <https://doi.org/10.1177/21501327211051933>
- [389] Watad A, De Marco G, Mahajna H, ... McGonagle D (2021). Immune-mediated disease flares or new-onset disease in 27 subjects following mRNA/DNA SARS-CoV-2 vaccination. *Vaccines* 9(5), 435. <https://doi.org/10.3390/vaccines9050435>
- [390] Cecchi N, Giannotta JA, Barcellini W, Fattizzo B (2021). A case of severe aplastic anaemia after SARS-CoV-2 vaccination. *British Journal of Haematology*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bjh.17947>
- [391] Pérez-Lamas L, Moreno-Jiménez G, Tenorio-Núñez MC, ... López-Jiménez JF (2021). Hemolytic crisis due to Covid-19 vaccination in a woman with cold agglutinin disease. *American Journal of Hematology* 96(8), E288–E291. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ajh.26214>
- [392] Fattizzo B, Giannotta JA, Cecchi N, Barcellini W (2021). SARS-CoV-2 vaccination induces breakthrough hemolysis in paroxysmal nocturnal hemoglobinuria on complement inhibitor. *American Journal of Hematology* 96(9), E344–E346. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ajh.26262>
- [393] Lunzer R (2021). Mit der COVID-19-Impfung assoziierte rheumatische Beschwerden. *rheuma plus* 20, 138–139. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12688-021-00439-6>
- [394] Benucci M, Infantino M, Marotto D, ... Sarzi-Puttini P (2021). Vaccination against SARS-CoV-2 in patients with rheumatic diseases: Doubts and perspectives. *Clinical and Experimental Rheumatology* 39(1), 196–202. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/33555252>

- [395] Ishay Y, Kenig A, Tsemach-Toren T, ... Kharouf F (2021). Autoimmune phenomena following SARS-CoV-2 vaccination. *International Immunopharmacology* 99, 107970. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.intimp.2021.107970>
- [396] Unal Enginar A (2021). Arthritis following COVID-19 vaccination: Report of two cases. *International Immunopharmacology* 101(B), 108256. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.intimp.2021.108256>
- [397] Maramattom BV, Philips G, Thomas J, Santhamma SGN (2021). Inflammatory myositis after ChAdOx1 vaccination. *The Lancet Rheumatology* 3(11), e747–e749. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s2665-9913\(21\)00312-x](https://doi.org/10.1016/s2665-9913(21)00312-x)
- [398] Jeon YH, Lim D-H, Choi SW, Choi SJ (2021). A flare of Still’s disease following COVID-19 vaccination in a 34-year-old patient. *Rheumatology International*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00296-021-05052-6>
- [399] Yamamoto S, Nishimura K, Yo K, ... Yokota T (2021). Flare-up of adult-onset Still’s disease after receiving a second dose of BNT162b2 COVID-19 mRNA vaccine. *Clinical and Experimental Rheumatology* 39(5, Suppl. 132), 139–140. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/34622765>
- [400] Leone F, Cerasuolo PG, Bosello SL, ... D’Agostino MA (2021). Adult-onset Still’s disease following COVID-19 vaccination. *The Lancet Rheumatology* 3(10), e678–e680. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s2665-9913\(21\)00218-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/s2665-9913(21)00218-6)
- [401] Baicus C, Delcea C, Pinte L, Dan GA (2021). Hyper-inflammation after COVID-19 mRNA vaccination – At the crossroads of multisystem inflammatory disease and adult-onset Still’s disease: Does terminology matter? *Romanian Journal of Internal Medicine*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.2478/rjim-2021-0035>
- [402] Nune A, Iyengar KP, Ish P, ... Sapkota HR (2021). The emergence of new-onset SLE following SARS-CoV-2 vaccination. *QJM*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1093/qjmed/hcab229>
- [403] Patil S, Patil A (2021). Systemic lupus erythematosus after COVID-19 vaccination: A case report. *Journal of Cosmetic Dermatology* 20(10), 3103–3104. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jocd.14386>
- [404] Zavala-Flores E, Salcedo-Matienzo J, Quiroz-Alva A, Berrocal-Kasay A (2021). Side effects and flares risk after SARS-CoV-2 vaccination in patients with systemic lupus erythematosus. *Clinical Rheumatology*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10067-021-05980-5>
- [405] Hidaka D, Ogasawara R, Sugimura S, ... Ota S (2021). New-onset Evans syndrome associated with systemic lupus erythematosus after BNT162b2 mRNA COVID-19 vaccination. *International Journal of Hematology*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12185-021-03243-2>
- [406] Tagini F, Carrel L, Fallet B, ... Monti M (2021). Behçet’s-like adverse event or inaugural Behçet’s disease after SARS-CoV-2 mRNA-1273 vaccination? *Rheumatology*, keab751. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1093/rheumatology/keab751>

- [407] Conticini E, d'Alessandro M, Bergantini L, ... Frediani B (2021). Relapse of microscopic polyangiitis after vaccination against COVID-19: A case report. *Journal of Medical Virology* 93(12), 6439–6441. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jmv.27192>
- [408] Liang I, Swaminathan S, Lee AYS (2021). Emergence of de novo cutaneous vasculitis post coronavirus disease (COVID-19) vaccination. *Clinical Rheumatology*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10067-021-05948-5>
- [409] Renuka T, Sandeep VT, Shiny PM, Jyothirani ER (2021). Leukocytoclastic vasculitis following coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19): A case report. *Journal of Skin and Sexually Transmitted Diseases* 3, 188–191. https://doi.org/10.25259/jssd_47_2021
- [410] Fritzen M, Funchal GDG, Luiz MO, Durigon GS (2021). Leukocytoclastic vasculitis after exposure to COVID-19 vaccine. *Anais Brasileiros de dermatologia*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.abd.2021.09.003>
- [411] Grossman ME, Appel G, Little AJ, Ko CJ (2021). Post-COVID-19 vaccination IgA vasculitis in an adult. *Journal of Cutaneous Pathology*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cup.14168>
- [412] Cohen SR, Prussick L, Kahn JS, ... Rosmarin D (2021). Leukocytoclastic vasculitis flare following the COVID-19 vaccine. *International Journal of Dermatology* 60(8), 1032–1033. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ijd.15623>
- [413] Berry CT, Eliliwi M, Gallagher S, ... Kallas R (2021). Cutaneous small vessel vasculitis following single-dose Janssen Ad26.COV2.S vaccination. *JAAD Case Reports* 15, 11–14. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jdcr.2021.07.002>
- [414] Kar BR, Singh BS, Mohapatra L, Agrawal I (2021). Cutaneous small-vessel vasculitis following COVID-19 vaccine. *Journal of Cosmetic Dermatology* 20(11), 3382–3383. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jocd.14452>
- [415] Hakroush S, Tampe B (2021) Case report: ANCA-associated vasculitis presenting with rhabdomyolysis and pauci-immune crescentic glomerulonephritis after Pfizer-BioNTech COVID-19 mRNA vaccination. *Frontiers in Immunology* 12, 762006. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fimmu.2021.762006>
- [416] Okuda S, Hirooka Y, Sugiyama M (2021). Propylthiouracil-induced antineutrophil cytoplasmic antibody-associated vasculitis after COVID-19 vaccination. *Vaccines* 9(8), 842. <https://doi.org/10.3390/vaccines9080842>
- [417] Kharkar V, Vishwanath T, Mahajan S, ... Gole P (2021). Asymmetrical cutaneous vasculitis following COVID-19 vaccination with unusual eosinophil preponderance. *Clinical and Experimental Dermatology* 46(8), 1596–1597. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ced.14797>
- [418] Dicks AB, Gray BH (2021). Images in vascular medicine: Leukocytoclastic vasculitis after COVID-19 vaccine booster. *Vascular Medicine*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1358863x211055507>

- [419] Naitlho A, Lahlou W, Bourial A, ... Belyamani L (2021). A rare case of Henoch-Schönlein purpura following a COVID-19 vaccine: Case report. *SN Comprehensive Clinical Medicine* 3, 2618–2621. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42399-021-01025-9>
- [420] Vassallo C, Boveri E, Brazzelli V, ... Gregorini M (2021). Cutaneous lymphocytic vasculitis after administration of COVID -19 mRNA vaccine. *Dermatologic Therapy* 34(5), e15076. <https://doi.org/10.1111/dth.15076>
- [421] Oskay T, Isık M (2021). Leukocytoclastic vasculitis after the third dose of CoronaVac vaccination. *Clinical Rheumatology*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10067-021-05993-0>
- [422] Sandhu S, Bhatnagar A, Kumar H, ... Mitra D (2021). Leukocytoclastic vasculitis as a cutaneous manifestation of ChAdOx1 nCoV-19 corona virus vaccine (recombinant). *Dermatologic Therapy*, e15141. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1111/dth.15141>
- [423] Shahrigharakhoshan S, Gagnon L, Mathieu S (2021). Cutaneous leukocytoclastic vasculitis induction following ChAdOx1 nCoV-19 vaccine. *Cureus* 13(10), e19005. <https://doi.org/10.7759/cureus.19005>
- [424] Manzo C, Natale M, Castagna A (2021). Polymyalgia rheumatica as uncommon adverse event following immunization with COVID-19 vaccine: A case report and review of literature. *Aging Medicine* 4(3), 234–238. <https://doi.org/10.1002/agm2.12171>
- [425] Mettler C, Jonville-Bera A-P, Grandvuillemin A, ... Chouchana L (2021). Risk of giant cell arteritis and polymyalgia rheumatica following COVID-19 vaccination: A global pharmacovigilance study. *Rheumatology*, keab756. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1093/rheumatology/keab756>
- [426] Vanni E, Ciaffi J, Mancarella L, Ursini F (2021). An unusual case of “conjugal” polymyalgia rheumatica after SARS-CoV-2 vaccination. *Rheumato* 1(1), 17–21. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rheumato1010004>
- [427] Parperis K, Constantinou M (2021). Remitting seronegative symmetrical synovitis with pitting oedema following BNT162b2 mRNA COVID-19 vaccination. *BMJ Case Reports* 14(8), e244479. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bcr-2021-244479>
- [428] Eisenberg MT, Tingey C, Fulton O, ... Snyder T (2021). Quadrilateral space region inflammation and other incidental findings on shoulder MRI following recent COVID-19 vaccination: Three case reports. *Radiology Case Reports* 16(10), 3024–3028. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.radcr.2021.07.028>
- [429] Rela M, Jothimani D, Vij M, ... Rammohan A (2021). Auto-immune hepatitis following COVID vaccination. *Journal of Autoimmunity* 123, 102688. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaut.2021.102688>
- [430] Wong CY, Rios EJ (2021). Cutaneous hypersensitivity reaction with acute hepatitis following COVID-19 vaccine. *JAAD Case Reports* 16, 44–46. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jdcr.2021.08.008>
- [431] Vuille-Lessard É, Montani M, Bosch J, Semmo N (2021). Autoimmune hepatitis triggered by SARS-CoV-2 vaccination. *Journal of Autoimmunity* 123, 102710. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaut.2021.102710>

- [432] Avci E, Abasiyanik F (2021). Autoimmune hepatitis after SARS-CoV-2 vaccine: New-onset or flare-up? *Journal of Autoimmunity* 125, 102745. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaut.2021.102745>
- [433] Tun GSZ, Gleeson D, Dube A, Al-Joudeh A (2021). Immune-mediated hepatitis with the Moderna vaccine, no longer a coincidence but confirmed. *Journal of Hepatology*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhep.2021.09.031>
- [434] Torrente S, Castiella A, Garmendia M, Zapata E (2021). Probable autoimmune hepatitis reactivated after COVID-19 vaccination. *Gastroenterología y hepatología*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gastrohep.2021.10.002>
- [435] Bril F, Al Diffalha S, Dean M, Fettig DM (2021). Autoimmune hepatitis developing after coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) vaccine: Causality or casualty? *Journal of Hepatology* 75(1), 222–224. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhep.2021.04.003>
- [436] McShane C, Kiat C, Rigby J, Crosbie Ó (2021). The mRNA COVID-19 vaccine: A rare trigger of autoimmune hepatitis? *Journal of Hepatology* 75(5), 1252–1254. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhep.2021.06.044>
- [437] Lodato F, Larocca A, D’Errico A, Cennamo V (2021). An unusual case of acute cholestatic hepatitis after m-RNABNT162b2 (Comirnaty) SARS-CoV-2 vaccine: Coincidence, autoimmunity or drug-related liver injury. *Journal of Hepatology* 75(5), 1254–1256. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhep.2021.07.005>
- [438] Ghielmetti M, Schaufelberger HD, Mieli-Vergani G, ... Terziroli Beretta-Piccoli B (2021). Acute autoimmune-like hepatitis with atypical anti-mitochondrial antibody after mRNA COVID-19 vaccination: A novel clinical entity? *Journal of Autoimmunity* 123, 102706. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaut.2021.102706>
- [439] Londoño M-C, Gratacós-Ginès J, Sáez-Peñataro J (2021). Another case of autoimmune hepatitis after SARS-CoV-2 vaccination: Still casualty? *Journal of Hepatology* 75(5), 1248–1249. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhep.2021.06.004>
- [440] Zhou T, Fronhoffs F, Dold L, ... Weismüller TJ (2021). New-onset autoimmune hepatitis following mRNA COVID-19 vaccination in a 36-year-old woman with primary sclerosing cholangitis: Should we be more vigilant? *Journal of Hepatology*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhep.2021.08.006>
- [441] Goulas A, Kafiri G, Kranidioti H, Manolakopoulos S (2021). A typical autoimmune hepatitis (AIH) case following Covid-19 mRNA vaccination: More than a coincidence? *Liver International*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1111/liv.15092>
- [442] Garrido I, Lopes S, Simões MS, ... Macedo G (2021). Autoimmune hepatitis after COVID-19 vaccine: More than a coincidence. *Journal of Autoimmunity* 125, 102741. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaut.2021.102741>
- [443] Tan CK, Wong YJ, Wang LM, ... Kumar R (2021). Autoimmune hepatitis following COVID-19 vaccination: True causality or mere association? *Journal of Hepatology* 75(5), 1250–1252. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhep.2021.06.009>

- [444] Shroff H, Satapathy SK, Crawford JM, ... VanWagner LB (2021). Liver injury following SARS-CoV-2 vaccination: A multicenter case series. *Journal of Hepatology*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhep.2021.07.024>
- [445] Palla P, Vergadis C, Sakellariou S, Androutsakos T (2021). Letter to the editor: Response to letter concerning our patient with post-vaccination autoimmune hepatitis like syndrome. *Hepatology*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1002/hep.32248>
- [446] Tsumiyama K, Miyazaki Y, Shiozawa S (2009). Self-organized criticality theory of autoimmunity. *PLoS ONE* 4(12), e8382. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0008382>
- [447] Eleiwa TK, Gaier ED, Haseeb A, ... Elhusseiny AM (2021). Adverse ocular events following COVID-19 vaccination. *Inflammation Research* 70, 1005–1009. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00011-021-01506-6>
- [448] Santovito LS, Pinna G (2021). Acute reduction of visual acuity and visual field after Pfizer-BioNTech COVID-19 vaccine 2nd dose: A case report. *Inflammation Research* 70(9), 931–933. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00011-021-01476-9>
- [449] Girbardt C, Busch C, Al-Sheikh M, ... Rehak M (2021). Retinal vascular events after mRNA and adenoviral-vectored COVID-19 vaccines: A case series. *Vaccines* 9(11), 1349. <https://doi.org/10.3390/vaccines9111349>
- [450] Gabka K, Groselli S, Ulbig M (2021). Flimmernde Skotome nach COVID-Impfung: Eine weitere mögliche Impfnebenwirkung? *Der Ophthalmologe* 118, 735–740. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00347-021-01435-z>
- [451] Ng XL, Betzler BK, Testi I, ... Agrawal R (2021). Ocular adverse events after COVID-19 vaccination. *Ocular Immunology and Inflammation*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09273948.2021.1976221>
- [452] Maleki A, Look-Why S, Manhapra A, Stephen Foster C (2021). COVID-19 recombinant mRNA vaccines and serious ocular inflammatory side effects: Real or coincidence? *Journal of Ophthalmic and Vision Research*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.18502/jovr.v16i3.9443>
- [453] Ikegami Y, Numaga J, Okano N, ... Terada Y (2021). Combined central retinal artery and vein occlusion shortly after mRNA-SARS-CoV-2 vaccination. *QJM*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1093/qjmed/hcab287>
- [454] Nioi M, d'Aloja E, Fossarello M, Napoli PE (2021). Dual corneal-graft rejection after mRNA vaccine (BNT162b2) for COVID-19 during the first six months of follow-up: Case report, state of the art and ethical concerns. *Vaccines* 9(11), 1274. <https://doi.org/10.3390/vaccines9111274>
- [455] Tsukii R, Kasuya Y, Makino S (2021). Nonarteritic anterior ischemic optic neuropathy following COVID-19 vaccination: Consequence or coincidence. *Case Reports in Ophthalmological Medicine* 2021, 5126254. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2021/5126254>

- [456] Honavar S, Sen M (2021). After the storm: Ophthalmic manifestations of COVID-19 vaccines. *Indian Journal of Ophthalmology* 69(12), 3398. https://doi.org/10.4103/ijo.ijo_2824_21
- [457] Testi I, Brandão-de-Resende C, Agrawal R, Pavesio C (2021). Ocular inflammatory events following COVID-19 vaccination: A multinational case series [Preprint]. *Research Square*. <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-1033969/v1>
- [458] García-Estrada C, Gómez-Figueroa E, Alban L, Arias-Cárdenas A (2021). Optic neuritis after COVID-19 vaccine application. *Clinical and Experimental Neuroimmunology*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cen3.12682>
- [459] Vecernji.hr (2021, November 7). Hrvatski liječnici objavili veliki vodič o cijepljenju i trudnoći. *Večernji list*. <https://www.vecernji.hr/vijesti/hrvatski-lijecnici-objavili-veliki-vodic-o-cijepljenju-i-trudnoci-1537303>
- [460] Lewis T (2021, December 2). The benefits of vaccinating kids against COVID far outweigh the risks of myocarditis. *Scientific American*. <https://www.scientificamerican.com/article/the-benefits-of-vaccinating-kids-against-covid-far-outweigh-the-risks-of-myocarditis1>
- [461] Rose J, McCullough PA (2021). A report on myocarditis adverse events in the U.S. Vaccine Adverse Events Reporting System (VAERS) in association with COVID-19 injectable biological products [Withdrawn]. *Current Problems in Cardiology*, 101011. Published online October 1, 2021. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cpcardiol.2021.101011>
- [462] Pillay J, Bialy L, Gaudet L, ... Hartling L (2021). Myocarditis and pericarditis following COVID-19 vaccination: Rapid systematic review of incidence, risk factors, and clinical course [Preprint]. *medRxiv*. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2021.11.19.21266605>
- [463] Høeg TB, Krug A, Stevenson J, Mandrola J. (2021). SARS-CoV-2 mRNA vaccination-associated myocarditis in children ages 12–17: A stratified national database analysis [Preprint]. *medRxiv*. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2021.08.30.21262866>
- [464] Kwan MY, Chua GT, Chow C, ... Ip P (2021). mRNA COVID vaccine and myocarditis in adolescents. *Hong Kong Medical Journal* 27(5), 326–327. <https://doi.org/10.12809/hkmj215120>
- [465] Lane S, Yeomans A, Shakir S (2021). Reports of myocarditis and pericarditis following mRNA COVID-19 vaccines: A systematic review of spontaneously reported data from the UK, Europe, and the US and of the literature [Preprint]. *medRxiv*. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2021.09.09.21263342>
- [466] Mevorach D, Anis E, Cedar N, ... Alroy-Preis S (2021). Myocarditis after BNT162b2 mRNA vaccine against Covid-19 in Israel. *New England Journal of Medicine* 385(23), 2140–2149. <https://doi.org/10.1056/nejmoa2109730>
- [467] Marshall M, Ferguson ID, Lewis P, ... Guzman-Cottrill JA (2021). Symptomatic acute myocarditis in 7 adolescents after Pfizer-BioNTech COVID-19 vaccination. *Pediatrics* 148(3), e2021052478. <https://doi.org/10.1542/peds.2021-052478>

- [468] Li M, Yuan J, Lv G, ... Lu ZK (2021). Myocarditis and pericarditis following COVID-19 vaccination: Inequalities in age and vaccine types. *Journal of Personalized Medicine* 11(11), 1106. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jpm11111106>
- [469] Koizumi T, Awaya T, Yoshioka K, ... Nakamura M (2021). Myocarditis after COVID-19 mRNA vaccines. *QJM*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1093/qjmed/hcab244>
- [470] Sinagra G, Merlo M, Porcari A (2021). Exploring the possible link between myocarditis and mRNA COVID-19 vaccines. *European Journal of Internal Medicine* 92, 28–30. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejim.2021.08.018>
- [471] Nagasaka T, Koitabashi N, Ishibashi Y, ... Kaneko Y (2021). Acute myocarditis associated with COVID-19 vaccination: A case report. *Journal of Cardiology Cases*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jccase.2021.11.006>
- [472] Lazaros G, Anastassopoulou C, Hatziantoniou S, ... Tsioufis C (2021). A case series of acute pericarditis following COVID-19 vaccination in the context of recent reports from Europe and the United States. *Vaccine* 39(45), 6585–6590. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.vaccine.2021.09.078>
- [473] Salah HM, Mehta JL (2021). COVID-19 vaccine and myocarditis. *The American Journal of Cardiology* 157, 146–148. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.amjcard.2021.07.009>
- [474] Long SS (2021). Important insights into myopericarditis after the Pfizer mRNA COVID-19 vaccination in adolescents. *The Journal of Pediatrics* 238, P5. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpeds.2021.07.057>
- [475] Tano GD, Moschini L, Calvaruso EV, Danzi GB (2021). Recurrent myocarditis after the first dose of SARS-CoV-2 mRNA-1273 vaccine [Preprint]. *Research Square*. <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-699585/v1>
- [476] Chiang C-Y, Chen C-Y, Yu W-L, ... Feng Y-H (2021). Myocardial infarction and azygos vein thrombosis after ChAdOx1 nCoV-19 vaccination in a hemodialysis patient. *Cureus* 13(9), e18390. <https://doi.org/10.7759/cureus.18390>
- [477] Kounis NG, Koniari I, Mplani V, ... Tsigkas G (2021). The pathogenesis of potential myocarditis induced by COVID-19 vaccine. *The American Journal of Emergency Medicine*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ajem.2021.11.016>
- [478] Chamling B, Vehof V, Drakos S, ... Yilmaz A (2021). Occurrence of acute infarct-like myocarditis following COVID-19 vaccination: Just an accidental co-incidence or rather vaccination-associated autoimmune myocarditis? *Clinical Research in Cardiology* 110(11), 1850–1854. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00392-021-01916-w>
- [479] Manolis AS, Manolis TA, Melita H (2021). Cardiovascular complications of COVID-19 vaccination. *Rhythmios* 16(4), 73–78. <http://rhythmios.gr/index.php/Rhythmios/article/view/509>
- [480] Singh R, Chakrabarti SS, Gambhir IS, ... Kaur U (2021). Acute cardiac events following ChAdOx1 nCoV-19 corona virus vaccine: Report of three cases [Preprint]. *Research Square*. <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-891077/v2>

- [481] Cari L, Alhosseini MN, Fiore P, ... Nocentini G (2021). Cardiovascular, neurological, and pulmonary events following vaccination with the BNT162b2, ChAdOx1 nCoV-19, and Ad26.COV2.S vaccines: An analysis of European data. *Journal of Autoimmunity* 125, 102742. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaut.2021.102742>
- [482] King WW, Petersen MR, Matar RM, ... Petersen JW (2021). Myocarditis following mRNA vaccination against SARS-CoV-2: A case series. *American Heart Journal Plus: Cardiology Research and Practice* 8, 100042. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ahjo.2021.100042>
- [483] Jain SS, Steele JM, Fonseca B, ... Grosse-Wortmann L (2021). COVID-19 vaccination-associated myocarditis in adolescents. *Pediatrics* 148(5), e2021053427. <https://doi.org/10.1542/peds.2021-053427>
- [484] Dionne A, Sperotto F, Chamberlain S, ... Friedman KG (2021). Association of myocarditis with BNT162b2 messenger RNA COVID-19 vaccine in a case series of children. *JAMA Cardiology*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jamacardio.2021.3471>
- [485] Li C, Chen Y, Zhao Y, ... Yuen K-Y (2021). Intravenous injection of coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) mRNA vaccine can induce acute myopericarditis in mouse model. *Clinical Infectious Diseases*, ciab707. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1093/cid/ciab707>
- [486] O'Leary ST, Maldonado YA (2021). Myocarditis after SARS-CoV-2 vaccination: True, true, and... Related? *Pediatrics* 148(3), e2021052644. <https://doi.org/10.1542/peds.2021-052644>
- [487] Parmar K, Mekraksakit P, Del Rio-Pertuz G, ... Sosa EA (2021). Myocarditis following COVID-19 mRNA vaccination. *Baylor University Medical Center Proceedings*. Online ahead of print.. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08998280.2021.1990743>
- [488] Dorfman AL, Murthy VL (2021). Annals for hospitalists – Inpatient notes: Myocarditis after vaccination for SARS-CoV-2. *Annals of Internal Medicine* 174(11), HO2–HO3. <https://doi.org/10.7326/m21-3871>
- [489] Schauer J, Buddhe S, Colyer J, ... Portman MA (2021). Myopericarditis after the Pfizer messenger ribonucleic acid coronavirus disease vaccine in adolescents. *The Journal of Pediatrics* 238, 317–320. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpeds.2021.06.083>
- [490] Das BB, Moskowitz WB, Taylor MB, Palmer A (2021). Myocarditis and pericarditis following mRNA COVID-19 vaccination: What do we know so far? *Children* 8(7), 607. <https://doi.org/10.3390/children8070607>
- [491] Tano E, San Martin S, Girgis S, ... Sanchez Vegas C (2021). Perimyocarditis in adolescents after Pfizer-BioNTech COVID-19 vaccine. *Journal of the Pediatric Infectious Diseases Society* 10(10), 962–966. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jpids/piab060>
- [492] Levin D, Shimon G, Fadlon-Derai M, ... Gordon B (2021). Myocarditis following COVID-19 vaccination: A case series. *Vaccine* 39(42), 6195–6200. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.vaccine.2021.09.004>
- [493] Khogali F, Abdelrahman R (2021) Unusual presentation of acute perimyocarditis following SARS-COV-2 mRNA-1237 Moderna vaccination. *Cureus* 13(7), e16590. <https://doi.org/10.7759/cureus.16590>

- [494] Kim I-C, Kim H, Lee HJ, ... Kim J-Y (2021). Cardiac imaging of acute myocarditis following COVID-19 mRNA vaccination. *Journal of Korean Medical Science* 36(32), e229. <https://doi.org/10.3346/jkms.2021.36.e229>
- [495] Calcaterra G, Mehta JL, de Gregorio C, ... Bassareo PP (2021). COVID 19 vaccine for adolescents: Concern about myocarditis and pericarditis. *Pediatric Reports* 13(3), 530–533. <https://doi.org/10.3390/pediatric13030061>
- [496] Onderko L, Starobin B, Riviere AE, ... Afari ME (2021). Myocarditis in the setting of recent COVID-19 vaccination. *Case Reports in Cardiology* 2021, 6806500. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2021/6806500>
- [497] Takase B, Hayashi K, Hisada T, ... Nagata M (2022). Chest pain with new abnormal electrocardiogram development after injection of COVID-19 vaccine manufactured by Moderna. *Internal Medicine*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.2169/internalmedicine.8711-21>
- [498] Kaneta K, Yokoi K, Jojima K, ... Node K (2021). Young male with myocarditis following mRNA-1273 vaccination against coronavirus disease-2019 (COVID-19). *Circulation Journal*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1253/circj.cj-21-0818>
- [499] Han T, Ma W, Zhang Y, Wang C (2021). Be alert to the risk of adverse cardiovascular events after COVID-19 vaccination. *Exploratory Research and Hypothesis in Medicine*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.14218/erhm.2021.00033>
- [500] Pepe S, Gregory AT, Denniss AR (2021). Myocarditis, pericarditis and cardiomyopathy after COVID-19 vaccination. *Heart, Lung and Circulation* 30(10), 1425–1429. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hlc.2021.07.011>
- [501] Kounis NG, Koniari I, Mplani V, ... Tsigkas G (2021). Acute myocardial infarction within 24 hours after COVID-19 vaccination: Is Kounis syndrome the culprit? *The American Journal of Cardiology*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.amjcard.2021.09.032>
- [502] Correa H, Soslow JH, Dendy JM, Creech CB (2021). Acute myopericarditis post intravenous injection of COVID-19 mRNA vaccine differs from viral myocarditis. *Clinical Infectious Diseases*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1093/cid/ciab980>
- [503] Patel YR, Louis DW, Atalay M, ... Shah NR (2021). Cardiovascular magnetic resonance findings in young adult patients with acute myocarditis following mRNA COVID-19 vaccination: A case series. *Journal of Cardiovascular Magnetic Resonance* 23, 101. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12968-021-00795-4>
- [504] Aye YN, Mai AS, Zhang A, ... Chew NWS (2021). Acute myocardial infarction and myocarditis following COVID-19 vaccination. *QJM*, hcab252. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1093/qjmed/hcab252>
- [505] Ashaari S, Sohaib HA, Bolger K (2021). A case report: Symptomatic pericarditis post-COVID-19 vaccination. *European Heart Journal: Case Reports* 5(10), ytab375. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ehjcr/ytab375>

- [506] Elhassan M, Ahmad H, Mohamed M, ... Elhassan AE (2021). From muscles to wires: Report of two cases and literature review on COVID-19 vaccination and cardiac conduction disturbance. *Cureus* 13(10), e18805. <https://doi.org/10.7759/cureus.18805>
- [507] Minocha PK, Better D, Singh RK, Hoque T (2021). Recurrence of acute myocarditis temporally associated with receipt of the mRNA coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) vaccine in a male adolescent. *The Journal of Pediatrics* 238, 321–323. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpeds.2021.06.035>
- [508] Miqdad MA, Nasser H, Alshehri A, Mourad AR (2021) Acute myocarditis following the administration of the second BNT162b2 COVID-19 vaccine dose. *Cureus* 13(10), e18880. <https://doi.org/10.7759/cureus.18880>
- [509] Lim Y, Kim MC., Kim KH, ... Lee JE (2021). Case report: Acute fulminant myocarditis and cardiogenic shock after messenger RNA coronavirus disease 2019 vaccination requiring extracorporeal cardiopulmonary resuscitation. *Frontiers in Cardiovascular Medicine* 8, 758996. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fcvm.2021.758996>
- [510] Patel T, Kelleman M, West Z, ... Oster ME (2021). Comparison of MIS-C related myocarditis, classic viral myocarditis, and COVID-19 vaccine related myocarditis in children [Preprint]. *medRxiv*. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2021.10.05.21264581>
- [511] Ambati S, Colon M, Mihic M, ... Bakar A (2021). Acute myopericarditis after COVID-19 vaccine in teenagers. *Case Reports in Cardiology* 2021, 8268755. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2021/8268755>
- [512] Visclosky T, Theyyuni N, Klekowski N, Bradin S (2021). Myocarditis following mRNA COVID-19 vaccine. *Pediatric Emergency Care* 37(11), 583–584. <https://doi.org/10.1097/pec.0000000000002557>
- [513] Tailor PD, Feighery AM, El-Sabawi B, Prasad A (2021). Case report: Acute myocarditis following the second dose of mRNA-1273 SARS-CoV-2 vaccine. *European Heart Journal: Case Reports* 5(8), ytab319. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ehjcr/ytab319>
- [514] Chelala L, Jeudy J, Hossain R, ... White C (2021). Cardiac MRI findings of myocarditis after COVID-19 mRNA vaccination in adolescents. *American Journal of Roentgenology*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.2214/ajr.21.26853>
- [515] Patrignani A, Schicchi N, Calcagnoli F, ... Mariani A (2021). Acute myocarditis following Comirnaty vaccination in a healthy man with previous SARS-CoV-2 infection. *Radiology Case Reports* 16(11), 3321–3325. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.radcr.2021.07.082>
- [516] Das BB, Kohli U, Ramachandran P, ... Khan D (2021). Myopericarditis after messenger RNA coronavirus disease 2019 vaccination in adolescents 12 to 18 years of age. *The Journal of Pediatrics* 238, 26–32.e1. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpeds.2021.07.044>
- [517] Sulemankhil I, Abdelrahman M, Negi SI (2021). Temporal association between the COVID-19 Ad26.COV2.S vaccine and acute myocarditis: A case report and literature review. *Cardiovascular Revascularization Medicine*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.carrev.2021.08.012>

- [518] Kafil T, Lamacie MM, Chenier S, ... Crean AM (2021). mRNA COVID-19 vaccination and development of CMR-confirmed myopericarditis [Preprint]. *medRxiv*. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2021.09.13.21262182>
- [519] Matta A, Kunadharaju R, Osman M, ... Bande D (2021) Clinical presentation and outcomes of myocarditis post mRNA vaccination: A meta-analysis and systematic review. *Cureus* 13(11), e19240. <https://doi.org/10.7759/cureus.19240>
- [520] Hryniewicki AT, Tolia VM, Nene RV (2021). Case report: Cardiac tamponade following COVID-19 vaccination. *The Journal of Emergency Medicine*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jemermed.2021.10.008>
- [521] Shaikh OA, Lal PM, Mohan A, ... Essar MY (2021). Coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) mRNA vaccine and the risk of myocarditis: An increasing concern. *Antimicrobial Stewardship & Healthcare Epidemiology* 1(1), e56. <https://doi.org/10.1017/ash.2021.209>
- [522] Shay DK, Shimabukuro TT, DeStefano F (2021). Myocarditis occurring after immunization with mRNA-based COVID-19 vaccines. *JAMA Cardiology* 6(10), 1115. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jamacardio.2021.2821>
- [523] Hajra A, Gupta M, Ghosh B, ... Lavie CJ (2021). Proposed pathogenesis, characteristics, and management of COVID-19 mRNA vaccine-related myopericarditis. *American Journal of Cardiovascular Drugs*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40256-021-00511-8>
- [524] Switzer C, Loeb M (2021). Evaluating the relationship between myocarditis and mRNA vaccination. *Expert Review of Vaccines*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14760584.2022.2002690>
- [525] Shiravi AA, Ardekani A, Sheikhabaei E, Heshmat-Ghahdarijani K (2021). Cardiovascular complications of SARS-CoV-2 vaccines: An overview. *Cardiology and Therapy*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40119-021-00248-0>
- [526] Foltran D, Delmas C, Flumian C, ... Montastruc F (2021). Myocarditis and pericarditis in adolescents after first and second doses of mRNA COVID-19 vaccines. *European Heart Journal: Quality of Care and Clinical Outcomes*, qcab090. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ehjqcco/qcab090>
- [527] McCullough J, McCullough J P, Korlipara G, Kaell A (2021) Myocarditis post Moderna vaccination: Review of criteria for diagnosis. *Cureus* 13(11), e19633. <https://doi.org/10.7759/cureus.19633>
- [528] Verma AK, Lavine KJ, Lin C-Y (2021). Myocarditis after Covid-19 mRNA vaccination. *New England Journal of Medicine* 385(14), 1332–1334. <https://doi.org/10.1056/nejmc2109975>
- [529] Lane S, Yeomans A, Shakir S (2021). Reports of myocarditis and pericarditis following mRNA COVID-19 vaccines: A systematic review of spontaneously reported data from the UK, Europe, and the US and of the literature [Preprint]. *medRxiv*. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2021.09.09.21263342>

- [530] Wilson H, Norris MD, Frosch O, Agarwal PP (2021). Late gadolinium enhancement after COVID-19 vaccination. *Radiology: Cardiothoracic Imaging* 3(5), e210199. <https://doi.org/10.1148/ryct.2021210199>
- [531] Walters CG, Jaiswal DD, Hu TX, Kim SS (2021). Myopericarditis in a young adult secondary to COVID-19 vaccination. *Methodist DeBakey Cardiovascular Journal* 17(3), 13–17. <https://doi.org/10.14797/mdcvj.847>
- [532] Sanchez Tijmes F, Thavendiranathan P, Udell JA., ... Hanneman K (2021). Cardiac MRI assessment of nonischemic myocardial inflammation: State of the art review and update on myocarditis associated with COVID-19 vaccination. *Radiology: Cardiothoracic Imaging*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1148/ryct.210252>
- [533] Choi S, Lee S, Seo J-W, ... Yeo NS (2021). Myocarditis-induced sudden death after BNT162b2 mRNA COVID-19 vaccination in Korea: Case report focusing on histopathological findings. *Journal of Korean Medical Science* 36(40), e286. <https://doi.org/10.3346/jkms.2021.36.e286>
- [534] Matta A, Kallamadi R, Matta D, Banda D (2021). Post-mRNA COVID-19 vaccination myocarditis. *European Journal of Case Reports in Internal Medicine*. Online ahead of print. https://doi.org/10.12890/2021_002769
- [535] Murakami Y, Shinohara M, Oka Y, ... Ikeda T (2022). Myocarditis following a COVID-19 messenger RNA vaccination: A Japanese case series. *Internal Medicine*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.2169/internalmedicine.8731-21>
- [536] Joob B, Wiwanitkit V (2021). Acute myocarditis after coronavirus disease 2019 vaccination. *The Anatolian Journal of Cardiology* 25(11), 841–842. <https://doi.org/10.5152/anatoljcardiol.2021.689>
- [537] Meyer-Szary J, Bazgier M, Lubocka P, ... Sabiniewicz R (2021). Cardiac magnetic resonance characteristics of acute myocarditis occurring after mRNA-based COVID-19 vaccines immunization. *Cardiology Journal*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.5603/CJ.a2021.0152>
- [538] Gautam N, Saluja P, Fudim M, ... Al'Aref S (2021). A late presentation of COVID-19 vaccine-induced myocarditis. *Cureus*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.7759/cureus.17890>
- [539] Beneki E, Deligiannis G, Zachos P, ... Tsaitsiris K (2021). Pericarditis following mRNA-based COVID-19 vaccination. *Journal of Medicine and Public Health* 2(2), 1018. <http://www.medtextpublications.com/open-access/pericarditis-following-mrna-based-covid-19-vaccination-921.pdf>
- [540] Martín AMG., Martínez-Mateo V (2021). Miopericarditis aguda tras administración de vacunas mRNA frente al virus SARS-CoV-2. *Medicina clínica*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.medcli.2021.10.008>
- [541] Habedank D, Lagast A, Novoa-Usme M, Atmowihardjo I (2021). A case of myocarditis in a 60-year-old man 48 h after mRNA vaccination against SARS-CoV2. *Clinical Research in Cardiology*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00392-021-01946-4>

- [542] Badshah M, Shriver J, Rynders B, ... Rajpurohit N (2021). MODERNA mRNA-1273 vaccine-associated myopericarditis in a patient with a subclinical autoimmune predisposition. *Journal of Cardiology Cases* 24(5), 227–229. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jccase.2021.09.007>
- [543] Eggebrecht H, Breitbart P, Koch A, ... Schmermund A (2021). Trends in ambulatory cardiology consultations for suspected myocarditis after COVID-19 vaccination. *Clinical Research in Cardiology*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00392-021-01974-0>
- [544] Tinoco M, Leite S, Faria B, ... Lourenço A (2021). Perimyocarditis following COVID-19 vaccination. *Clinical Medicine Insights: Cardiology* 15, 1–4. <https://doi.org/10.1177/11795468211056634>
- [545] Istampoulouoglou I, Dimitriou G, Späni S, ... Leuppi-Taegtmeier AB (2021). Myocarditis and pericarditis in association with COVID-19 mRNA-vaccination: Cases from a regional pharmacovigilance centre. *Global Cardiology Science and Practice* 2021(3), e202118. <https://doi.org/10.21542/gcsp.2021.18>
- [546] Chouchana L, Blet A, Al-Khalaf M, ... Liu PP (2021). Cardiac inflammation after COVID-19 mRNA vaccines: A global pharmacovigilance analysis [Preprint]. *medRxiv*. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2021.08.12.21261955>
- [547] AbdelMassih A, Shershaby ME, Gaber H, ... Fouda R (2021). Can sarcopenia index serve as a predictor of myocarditis from mRNA based COVID-19 vaccine: Insights from clustered cases and potential involvement of micro-RNAs in its pathogenesis [Preprint]. *Research Square*. <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-1036153/v2>
- [548] Hendren NS, Carter S, Grodin JL (2021). Severe COVID-19 vaccine associated myocarditis: Zebra or unicorn? *International Journal of Cardiology* 343, 197–198. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijcard.2021.09.036>
- [549] Hajjo R, Sabbah DA, Bardaweel SK, Tropsha A (2021). Shedding the light on post-vaccine myocarditis and pericarditis in COVID-19 and non-COVID-19 vaccine recipients. *Vaccines* 9(10), 1186. <https://doi.org/10.3390/vaccines9101186>
- [550] Bozkurt B, Kamat I, Hotez PJ (2021). Myocarditis with COVID-19 mRNA vaccines. *Circulation* 144(6), 471–484. <https://doi.org/10.1161/circulationaha.121.056135>
- [551] Chua GT, Kwan MYW, Chui CSL, ... Ip P (2021). Epidemiology of acute myocarditis/pericarditis in Hong Kong adolescents following Comirnaty vaccination. *Clinical Infectious Diseases*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1093/cid/ciab989>
- [552] Perez Y, Levy ER, Joshi AY, ... Swift MD (2021). Myocarditis following coronavirus disease 2019 mRNA vaccine: A case series and incidence rate determination. *Clinical Infectious Diseases*, ciab926. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1093/cid/ciab926>
- [553] Habib MB, Hamamyh T, Elyas A, ... Elhassan M (2021). Acute myocarditis following administration of BNT162b2 vaccine. *IDCases* 25, e01197. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.idcr.2021.e01197>
- [554] Alania-Torres E, Morillas-Climent H, García-Escrivá A, ... Valle-Muñoz A (2021) Case report: Probable myocarditis after Covid-19 mRNA vaccine in a patient with arrhythmogenic left ventricular

cardiomyopathy. *Frontiers in Cardiovascular Medicine* 8, 759119. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fcvm.2021.759119>

[555] Chen DH, Arefin AR, Joshi A, Khanji MY (2021). Myopericarditis in a teenager following first mRNA COVID vaccine dose: The role of multi-parametric cardiovascular magnetic resonance. *European Heart Journal: Case Reports* 5(10), ytab371. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ehjcr/ytab371>

[556] Facetti S, Giraldi M, Vecchi AL, ... Nassiacos D (2021). Miocardite acuta in giovane adulto due giorni dopo vaccino Pfizer. *Giornale Italiano di cardiologia* 22(11), 891–893. <https://doi.org/10.1714/3689.36746>

[557] Bautista García J, Peña Ortega P, Bonilla Fernández JA, ... Caballero Dorta E (2021). Miocarditis aguda tras administración de vacuna BNT162b2 contra la COVID-19. *Revista Española de cardiología* 74(9), 812–814. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.recesp.2021.03.009>

[558] Kaul R, Sreenivasan J, Goel A, ... Panza JA (2021). Myocarditis following COVID-19 vaccination. *IJC Heart & Vasculature* 36, 100872. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijcha.2021.100872>

[559] Ramírez-García A, Lozano Jiménez S, Darnaude Ximénez I, ... Segovia Cubero J (2021). Pericarditis tras la administración de la vacuna de ARNm BNT162b2 contra la COVID-19. *Revista Española de cardiología* 74(12), 1121–1123. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.recesp.2021.06.006>

[560] Sharifian-Dorche M, Bahmanyar M, Sharifian-Dorche A, ... Mowla A (2021). Vaccine-induced immune thrombotic thrombocytopenia and cerebral venous sinus thrombosis post COVID-19 vaccination: A systematic review. *Journal of the Neurological Sciences* 428, 117607. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jns.2021.117607>

[561] Ahmed SH, Shaikh TG, Waseem S, ... Ullah I (2021). Vaccine-induced thrombotic thrombocytopenia following coronavirus vaccine: A narrative review. *Annals of Medicine and Surgery*, 102988. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.amsu.2021.102988>

[562] Makris M, Pavord S, Lester W, ... Hunt B (2021). Vaccine-induced immune thrombocytopenia and thrombosis (VITT). *Research and Practice in Thrombosis and Haemostasis* 5(5), e12529. <https://doi.org/10.1002/rth2.12529>

[563] Anonymous (2021). Erratum. *Research and Practice in Thrombosis and Haemostasis* 5(5), e12585. <https://doi.org/10.1002/rth2.12585>

[564] Chang JC, Hawley HB (2021). Vaccine-associated thrombocytopenia and thrombosis: Venous endotheliopathy leading to venous combined micro-macrothrombosis. *Medicina* 57(11), 1163. <https://doi.org/10.3390/medicina57111163>

[565] Di Micco P, Camporese G, Cardillo G, ... Imbalzano E (2021). Pathophysiology of vaccine-induced prothrombotic immune thrombocytopenia (VIPIT) and vaccine-induced thrombocytopenic thrombosis (VITT) and their diagnostic approach in emergency. *Medicina* 57(10), 997. <https://doi.org/10.3390/medicina57100997>

- [566] Dotan A, Shoenfeld Y (2021). Perspectives on vaccine induced thrombotic thrombocytopenia. *Journal of Autoimmunity* 121, 102663. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaut.2021.102663>
- [567] Laporte J-R, Coma E, Fina F, ... Medina M (2021). Vaccines against Covid-19, venous thromboembolism, and thrombocytopenia: A population-based retrospective cohort study [Preprint]. *medRxiv*. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2021.07.23.21261036>
- [568] Chen P-W, Tsai Z-Y, Chao T-H, ... Liu P-Y (2021). Addressing vaccine-induced immune thrombotic thrombocytopenia (VITT) following COVID-19 vaccination: A mini-review of practical strategies. *Acta Cardiologica Sinica* 37(4), 355–364. [https://doi.org/10.6515/ACS.202107_37\(4\).20210628A](https://doi.org/10.6515/ACS.202107_37(4).20210628A)
- [569] Azzarone B, Veneziani I, Moretta L, Maggi E (2021) Pathogenic mechanisms of vaccine-induced immune thrombotic thrombocytopenia in people receiving anti-COVID-19 adenoviral-based vaccines: A proposal. *Frontiers in Immunology* 12, 728513. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fimmu.2021.728513>
- [570] Hunter PR (2021). Thrombosis after covid-19 vaccination. *BMJ* 373, n958. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.n958>
- [571] Merchant HA (2021). CoViD vaccines and thrombotic events: EMA issued warning to patients and healthcare professionals. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Policy and Practice* 14, 32. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40545-021-00315-w>
- [572] Giuffrida G, Condorelli A, Di Giorgio MA, ... Di Raimondo F (2021). Immune-mediated thrombotic thrombocytopenic purpura following Pfizer-BioNTech COVID-19 vaccine. *Haematologica*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.3324/haematol.2021.279535>
- [573] David P, Dotan A, Mahroum N, Shoenfeld Y (2021). Immune thrombocytopenic purpura (ITP) triggered by COVID-19 infection and vaccination. *The Israel Medical Association Journal* 23(6), 378–380. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/34155853>
- [574] Gresele P, Momi S, Marcucci R, ... Tripodi A (2021). Interactions of adenoviruses with platelets and coagulation and the vaccine-associated autoimmune thrombocytopenia thrombosis syndrome. *Haematologica* 106(12), 3034–3045. <https://doi.org/10.3324/haematol.2021.279289>
- [575] Chittal A, Rao S, Lakra P, ... Haas C (2021). A case of COVID-19 vaccine-induced thrombotic thrombocytopenia. *Journal of Community Hospital Internal Medicine Perspectives* 11(6), 776–778. <https://doi.org/10.1080/20009666.2021.1980966>
- [576] Rizk JG, Gupta A, Sardar P, ... Lavie CJ (2021). Clinical characteristics and pharmacological management of COVID-19 vaccine-induced immune thrombotic thrombocytopenia with cerebral venous sinus thrombosis. *JAMA Cardiology*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jamacardio.2021.3444>
- [577] Yamamoto K (2021). Risk of heparinoid use in cosmetics and moisturizers in individuals vaccinated against severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2. *Thrombosis Journal* 19, 67. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12959-021-00320-8>

- [578] Kragholm K, Sessa M, Mulvad T, ... Sogaard P (2021). Thrombocytopenia after COVID-19 vaccination. *Journal of Autoimmunity* 123, 102712. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaut.2021.102712>
- [579] Finsterer J, Redzic Z (2021). Symptomatic peduncular, cavernous bleeding following SARS-CoV-2 vaccination induced immune thrombocytopenia. *Brain Hemorrhages*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hest.2021.09.001>
- [580] Iba T, Levy JH (2021). The roles of platelets in COVID-19-associated coagulopathy and vaccine-induced immune thrombotic thrombocytopenia. *Trends in Cardiovascular Medicine*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tcm.2021.08.012>
- [581] Alalwan AA, Abou Trabeh A, Premchandran D, Razeem M (2021). COVID-19 vaccine-induced thrombotic thrombocytopenia: A case series. *Cureus* 13(9), e17862. <https://doi.org/10.7759/cureus.17862>
- [582] Leenaerts V, Staes M, Callens J, Monballyu P (2021). Pulmonary embolism in vaccine-induced thrombotic thrombocytopenia: Under-reported? *EMJ Respiratory* 9(1), 79–85. <https://doi.org/10.33590/emjrespir/21-00160>
- [583] Rodriguez-Pardo J, Gilo-Arrojo F de A, Ruiz-Ares G, ... Díez-Tejedor E (2021). Thrombosis and thrombocytopenia syndrome causing isolated symptomatic carotid occlusion after Ad26.COV2.S (Janssen) COVID-19 vaccine. *Thrombosis and Haemostasis*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1055/a-1674-0341>
- [584] Lin W, Ko C-A, Sung Y-F, ... Lin Y-K (2021). Cerebral venous sinus thrombosis, pulmonary embolism, and thrombocytopenia after COVID-19 vaccination in a Taiwanese man: A case report and literature review. *Frontiers in Neurology* 12, 738329. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fneur.2021.738329>
- [585] Reuben RC, Adogo LY (2021). SARS-CoV-2 vaccines-induced thrombotic thrombocytopenia: Should we consider immuno-hypersensitivity? *Revista de saúde pública* 55, 70. <https://doi.org/10.11606/s1518-8787.2021055003855>
- [586] Connors JM (2021). Thromboinflammatory findings and clinical predictors of mortality in vaccine-induced immune thrombotic thrombocytopenia. *European Heart Journal* 42(39), 4073–4076. <https://doi.org/10.1093/eurheartj/ehab585>
- [587] Crea F (2021). Thrombosis in peripheral artery disease and thrombotic thrombocytopenia after adenoviral COVID-19 vaccination. *European Heart Journal* 42(39), 3995–3999. <https://doi.org/10.1093/eurheartj/ehab712>
- [588] Mungmunpantipantip R, Wiwanitkit V (2021). Comment on: Thrombocytopenia in a teen with sickle cell disease following COVID-19 vaccination. *Pediatric Blood & Cancer* 69(1), e29303. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pbc.29303>
- [589] Mannucci PM (2021). Thrombotic thrombocytopenic purpura and other immune mediated blood disorders following SARS-CoV-2 vaccination. *Haematologica*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.3324/haematol.2021.279649>

- [590] Su P-H, Yu Y-C, Chen W-H, ... Huang Y-M (2021). Case report: Vaccine-induced immune thrombotic thrombocytopenia in a pancreatic cancer patient after vaccination with messenger RNA-1273. *Frontiers in Medicine* 8, 772424. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmed.2021.772424>
- [591] Gaunt ER, Mabbott NA (2021). The clinical correlates of vaccine-induced immune thrombotic thrombocytopenia after immunisation with adenovirus vector-based SARS-CoV-2 vaccines. *Immunotherapy Advances* 1(1), ltab019. <https://doi.org/10.1093/immadv/ltab019>
- [592] Lindhoff-Last E, Schoenborn L, Piorkowski M, ... Warkentin T (2021). Heterogeneity of vaccine-induced immune thrombotic thrombocytopenia after ChAdOx1 nCov-19 vaccination and safety of second vaccination with BNT162b2. *Thrombosis and Haemostasis*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1055/a-1701-2926>
- [593] Nicolson PLR, Montague SJ, Smith CW, ... Lester WA (2021). Anti-PF4 levels of patients with VITT do not reduce 4 months following AZD1222 vaccination [Preprint]. *medRxiv*. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2021.08.17.21262138>
- [594] Giovane R, Campbell J (2021). Bilateral thalamic stroke: A case of COVID-19 vaccine-induced immune thrombotic thrombocytopenia (VITT) or a coincidence due to underlying risk factors? *Cureus* 13(10), e18977. <https://doi.org/10.7759/cureus.18977>
- [595] Grady D, Mazzei P (2021, January 12). Doctor's death after COVID vaccine is being investigated. *The New York Times*. <https://www.nytimes.com/2021/01/12/health/covid-vaccine-death.html>
- [596] Grady D (2021, February 8). A few Covid vaccine recipients developed a rare blood disorder. *The New York Times*. <https://www.nytimes.com/2021/02/08/health/immune-thrombocytopenia-covid-vaccine-blood.html>
- [597] See I, Lale A, Marquez P, ... Shay DK (2021). Case series of thrombosis with thrombocytopenia syndrome following COVID-19 vaccination: United States, December 2020–August 2021 [Preprint]. *medRxiv*. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2021.11.10.21266063>
- [598] Kim G, Choi E-J, Park H-S, ... Lee K-H (2021). A case report of immune thrombocytopenia after ChAdOx1 nCoV-19 vaccination. *Journal of Korean Medical Science* 36(43), e306.. <https://doi.org/10.3346/jkms.2021.36.e306>
- [599] Monagle P, Ng AP, Linden M, ... Torresi J (2021). Vaccine-induced immune thrombosis and thrombocytopenia syndrome following adenovirus-vectored severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 vaccination: A novel hypothesis regarding mechanisms and implications for future vaccine development. *Immunology & Cell Biology* 99(10), 1006–1010. <https://doi.org/10.1111/imcb.12505>
- [600] De Michele M, Piscopo P, Crestini A, ... Toni D (2021). Vaccine-induced immune thrombotic thrombocytopenia and spike protein [Preprint]. *Research Square* <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-887779/v1>

- [601] Major A, Carll T, Chan CW, ... Cohen KS (2021). Refractory vaccine-induced immune thrombotic thrombocytopenia (VITT) managed with delayed therapeutic plasma exchange (TPE). *Journal of Clinical Apheresis*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jca.21945>
- [602] Chong B, Leung H, Perdomo J, ... Chong J (2021). NETosis and thrombosis in vaccine-induced immune thrombotic thrombocytopenia [Preprint]. *Research Square*. <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-753825/v1>
- [603] Marchandot B, Carmona A, Morel O (2021). Time to consider neuroinflammation as a booster effect of cerebral venous sinus thrombosis in vaccine-induced immune thrombotic thrombocytopenia? *Journal of Thrombosis and Thrombolysis*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11239-021-02580-7>
- [604] Hwang J, Park SH, Lee SW, ... Smith L (2021). Predictors of mortality in thrombotic thrombocytopenia after adenoviral COVID-19 vaccination: The FAPIC score. *European Heart Journal* 42(39), 4053–4063. <https://doi.org/10.1093/eurheartj/ehab592>
- [605] Rodriguez EVC, Bouazza F-Z, Dauby N, ... Cliquennois M (2021). Fatal vaccine-induced immune thrombotic thrombocytopenia (VITT) post Ad26.COV2.S: First documented case outside US. *Infection*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s15010-021-01712-8>
- [606] Makris M, Pavord S (2022). Most cases of thrombosis and thrombocytopenia syndrome (TTS) post ChAdOx-1 nCov-19 are vaccine-induced immune thrombotic thrombocytopenia (VITT). *The Lancet Regional Health: Europe* 12, 100274. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lanepe.2021.100274>
- [607] Maraziti G, Becattini C (2021). Eltrombopag for refractory vaccine-induced immune thrombotic thrombocytopenia. *Journal of Thrombosis and Thrombolysis*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11239-021-02604-2>
- [608] Okada Y, Sakai R, Sato-Fitoussi M, ... Amano K (2021). Potential triggers for thrombocytopenia and/or hemorrhage by the BNT162b2 vaccine, Pfizer-BioNTech. *Frontiers in Medicine* 8, 751598. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmed.2021.751598>
- [609] Pavord S, Scully M, Hunt BJ, ... Makris M (2021). Clinical features of vaccine-induced immune thrombocytopenia and thrombosis. *New England Journal of Medicine* 385(18), 1680–1689. <https://doi.org/10.1056/nejmoa2109908>
- [610] Abou-Ismaïl MY, Moser KA, Smock KJ, Lim MY (2021). Vaccine-induced thrombotic thrombocytopenia following Ad26.COV2.S vaccine in a man presenting as acute venous thromboembolism. *American Journal of Hematology* 96(9), E346–E349. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ajh.26265>
- [611] Marchandot B, Curtiaud A, Trimaille A, ... Morel O (2021). Vaccine-induced immune thrombotic thrombocytopenia: Current evidence, potential mechanisms, clinical implications, and future directions. *European Heart Journal Open* 1(2), oeab014. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ehjopen/oeab014>

- [612] Thaler J, Jilma P, Samadi N, ... Ay C (2021). Long-term follow-up after successful treatment of vaccine-induced prothrombotic immune thrombocytopenia. *Thrombosis Research* 207, 126–130. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.thromres.2021.09.017>
- [613] Thachil J (2021). COVID-19 vaccine-induced immune thrombosis with thrombocytopenia (VITT) and the shades of grey in thrombus formation. *Seminars in Thrombosis and Hemostasis*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1055/s-0041-1735453>
- [614] Toh C-H (2021). The art and science of the thrombosis with thrombocytopenia syndrome. *Clinical Medicine* 21(6), e603–e603. <https://doi.org/10.7861/clinmed.2021-0525>
- [615] Pitkänen HH, Jouppila A, Helin T, ... Lassila R (2021). COVID-19 adenovirus vaccine triggers antibodies against PF4 complexes to activate complement and platelets. *Thrombosis Research* 208, 129–137. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.thromres.2021.10.027>
- [616] Cleaver J, Ibitoye R, Morrison H, ... Mortimer A (2021). Endovascular treatment for vaccine-induced cerebral venous sinus thrombosis and thrombocytopenia following ChAdOx1 nCoV-19 vaccination: A report of three cases. *Journal of NeuroInterventional Surgery*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1136/neurintsurg-2021-018238>
- [617] Huang C-T, Hsu S-Y, Wang C-H, ... Cheng M-H (2021). Double high-dose immunoglobulin for ChAdOx1 nCoV-19 vaccine-induced immune thrombotic thrombocytopenia. *Thrombosis Research* 206, 14–17. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.thromres.2021.07.017>
- [618] Marchandot B, Carmona A, Trimaille A, ... Morel O (2021). Procoagulant microparticles: A possible link between vaccine-induced immune thrombocytopenia (VITT) and cerebral sinus venous thrombosis. *Journal of Thrombosis and Thrombolysis* 52(3), 689–691. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11239-021-02505-4>
- [619] Swan D, Enright H, Desmond R, ... O’Connell N (2021). Vaccine-induced thrombosis and thrombocytopenia (VITT) in Ireland: A review of cases and current practices. *Thrombosis Update* 5, 100086. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tru.2021.100086>
- [620] Klok FA, Pai M, Huisman MV, Makris M (2021). Vaccine-induced immune thrombotic thrombocytopenia. *The Lancet Haematology*. Online ahead of print. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s2352-3026\(21\)00306-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/s2352-3026(21)00306-9)
- [621] John C, Kumar R, Sivan AK, ... Philip CC (2021). Vaccine induced thrombotic thrombocytopenia (VITT): First report from India and utility of risk score for diagnosis in resource limited settings [Preprint]. *Research Square*. <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-906280/v1>
- [622] Favalaro EJ (2021). Laboratory testing for suspected COVID-19 vaccine-induced (immune) thrombotic thrombocytopenia. *International Journal of Laboratory Hematology* 43(4), 559–570. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ijlh.13629>

- [623] Haime M (2021). Concern about the adverse effects of thrombocytopenia and thrombosis after adenovirus-vectored COVID-19 vaccination. *Clinical and Applied Thrombosis/Hemostasis* 27, 1–5. <https://doi.org/10.1177/10760296211040110>
- [624] Rzymiski P, Perek B, Flisiak R (2021). Thrombotic thrombocytopenia after COVID-19 vaccination: In search of the underlying mechanism. *Vaccines* 9(6), 559. <https://doi.org/10.3390/vaccines9060559>
- [625] Tobaiqy M, MacLure K, Elkout H, Stewart D (2021). Thrombotic adverse events reported for Moderna, Pfizer and Oxford-AstraZeneca COVID-19 vaccines: Comparison of occurrence and clinical outcomes in the EudraVigilance database. *Vaccines* 9(11), 1326. <https://doi.org/10.3390/vaccines9111326>
- [626] Baldi I, Azzolina D, Francavilla A, ... Gregori D (2021). Thrombotic events after COVID-19 vaccination in the over-50s: Results from a population-based study in Italy. *Vaccines* 9(11), 1307. <https://doi.org/10.3390/vaccines9111307>
- [627] Gardellini A, Guidotti F, Maino E, ... Turrini M (2021). Severe immune thrombocytopenia after COVID-19 vaccination: Report of four cases and review of the literature. *Blood Cells, Molecules, and Diseases* 92, 102615. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bcmd.2021.102615>
- [628] Gardellini A, Guidotti F, Maino E, ... Turrini M (2021). Severe immune thrombocytopenia after COVID-19 vaccination: Report of four cases and review of the literature. *Blood Cells, Molecules, and Diseases* 92, 102615. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bcmd.2021.102615>
- [629] Szóstek-Mioduchowska A, Kordowitzki P (2021). Shedding light on the possible link between ADAMTS13 and vaccine-induced thrombotic thrombocytopenia. *Cells* 10(10), 2785. <https://doi.org/10.3390/cells10102785>
- [630] Günther A, Brämer D, Pletz MW, ... Thiele T (2021). Complicated long term vaccine induced thrombotic immune thrombocytopenia: A case report. *Vaccines* 9(11), 1344. <https://doi.org/10.3390/vaccines9111344>
- [631] Strobel D, Haberkamp S, Zundler S (2021). Portal vein thrombosis due to vaccine-induced immune thrombotic thrombocytopenia (VITT) after Covid vaccination with ChAdOx1 nCoV-19. *Ultraschall in der Medizin* 42(5), 551–552. <https://doi.org/10.1055/a-1579-9303>
- [632] Thant LZ, Kyi Phyu N (2021). A case report: COVID vaccine-induced immune thrombocytopenia. *Clinics of Surgery* 5(12), 1–3. <https://doi.org/10.47829/cos.2021.51201>
- [633] Ramírez C, Hernández RJS, Durón RM (2021). Challenges managing COVID vaccine-induced immune thrombotic thrombocytopenia in low-middle income countries. *Clinical and Experimental Vaccine Research* 10(3), 290–291. <https://doi.org/10.7774/cevr.2021.10.3.290>
- [634] Yoshida K, Sakaki A, Matsuyama Y, ... Tamura S (2021). Acquired thrombotic thrombocytopenic purpura following BNT162b2 mRNA coronavirus disease vaccination in a Japanese patient. *Internal Medicine*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.2169/internalmedicine.8568-21>

- [635] Montiel Jarolin D, Torres E, Jarolin M, ... Sánchez L (2021). Reporte de un caso de plaquetopenia y trombosis secundaria a la vacuna chAdOx1 nCov-19. *Revista científica ciencias de la salud* 3(2), 120–125. <https://doi.org/10.53732/rccsalud/03.02.2021.120>
- [636] Sumi T, Nagahisa Y, Matsuura K, ... Chiba H (2021). Lung squamous cell carcinoma with hemoptysis after vaccination with tozinameran (BNT162b2, Pfizer-BioNTech). *Thoracic Cancer* 12(22), 3072–3075. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1759-7714.14179>
- [637] Mungmunpantipantip R, Wiwanitkit V (2021). Thrombosis after adenovirus-vectored COVID-19 vaccination: A concern on underlying illness. *Clinical and Applied Thrombosis/Hemostasis* 27, 1–2. <https://doi.org/10.1177/10760296211060446>
- [638] Chen Y, Huang H, Wu S, Huang T (2021). Thrombosis of the palmar digital vein after Oxford-AstraZeneca COVID-19 vaccination. *International Journal of Dermatology* 60(11), e469–e471. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ijd.15897>
- [639] Aghabaklou S, Razavi S-M, Mohammadi P, ... Mowla A (2021). Cerebral coagulation complications following COVID-19 adenoviral vector vaccines: A systematic review. *Journal of Neurology Research* 11(5), 69–76. <https://doi.org/10.14740/jnr700>
- [640] Gürtler L, Seitz R, Schramm W (2021). Cerebral venous thrombosis after COVID-19 vaccination: Is the risk of thrombosis increased by intravascular application of the vaccine? *Infection* 49(5), 1071–1074. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s15010-021-01658-x>
- [641] Palaiodimou L, Stefanou M-I, Katsanos AH, ... Tsivgoulis G (2021). Cerebral venous sinus thrombosis and thrombotic events after vector-based COVID-19 vaccines. *Neurology* 97(21), e2136–e2147. <https://doi.org/10.1212/wnl.00000000000012896>
- [642] Gangat N, Guglielmelli P, Betti S, ... Tefferi A (2021). Cerebral venous thrombosis and myeloproliferative neoplasms: A three-center study of 74 consecutive cases. *Blood* 138(Supplement 1), 1493. <https://doi.org/10.1182/blood-2021-149772>
- [643] Lippi G, Favaloro EJ (2021). Cerebral venous thrombosis developing after COVID-19 vaccination: VITT, VATT, TTS, and more. *Seminars in Thrombosis and Hemostasis*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1055/s-0041-1736168>
- [644] Mazzeo AT, Noto A, Asmundo A, ... Ferlazzo G (2021). Cerebral venous sinus thrombosis (CVST) associated with SARS-CoV-2 vaccines: Clues for an immunopathogenesis common to CVST observed in COVID-19. *Journal of Anesthesia, Analgesia and Critical Care* 1, 15. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s44158-021-00020-9>
- [645] Chamarti K, Dar K, Reddy A, ... Bajaj K (2021). Thrombotic thrombocytopenic purpura presentation in an elderly gentleman following COVID vaccine circumstances. *Cureus* 13(7), e16619. <https://doi.org/10.7759/cureus.16619>

- [646] Paulsen F-O, Schaefers C, Langer F, ... Seidel C (2021). Immune thrombocytopenic purpura after vaccination with COVID-19 vaccine (ChAdOx1 nCov-19). *Blood* 138(11), 996–999. <https://doi.org/10.1182/blood.2021012790>
- [647] Hann A, Hartog H, Lester W, ... Perera T (2021). Early adverse outcomes of liver allografts from donors with COVID vaccine induced thrombosis and thrombocytopenia syndrome. *HPB* 23(S3), S975. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hpb.2021.08.656>
- [648] Jargin SV (2021). COVID-19 vaccination with special reference to adenoviral vectors, clotting disorders and old age. *Journal of Geriatrics and Palliative Care* 7(1), 2. <https://www.avensonline.org/wp-content/uploads/JGPC-2373-1133-07-0023.pdf>
- [649] Cari L, Fiore P, Naghavi Alhosseini M, ... Nocentini G (2021). Blood clots and bleeding events following BNT162b2 and ChAdOx1 nCoV-19 vaccine: An analysis of European data. *Journal of Autoimmunity* 122, 102685. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaut.2021.102685>
- [650] Bachmann P, Mardin CY, Bartsch AJ, Weller JM (2021). Akute unilaterale Sehstörung nach COVID-Impfung. *Der Ophthalmologe*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00347-021-01498-y>
- [651] Anonymous (2021, December 2). COVID-19: ‘Trigger’ behind extremely rare AstraZeneca vaccine blood clots may have been discovered. *Sky News*. <https://news.sky.com/story/covid-19-trigger-behind-extremely-rare-astrazeneca-vaccine-blood-clots-may-have-been-discovered-12484255>
- [652] Borić R, Brakus I, Cigić L, ... Zajc I (2015). *Hrvatsko stomatološko nazivlje*. Zagreb: Institut za hrvatski jezik i jezikoslovlje. <https://www.bib.irb.hr/926009>
- [653] Sriwastava S, Shrestha AK, Khalid SH, ... Srivastava S (2021). Spectrum of neuroimaging findings in post-COVID-19 vaccination: A case series and review of literature. *Neurology International* 13(4), 622–639. <https://doi.org/10.3390/neurolint13040061>
- [654] Khayat-Khoei M, Bhattacharyya S, Katz J, ... Bakshi R (2021). COVID-19 mRNA vaccination leading to CNS inflammation: A case series. *Journal of Neurology*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00415-021-10780-7>
- [655] Finsterer J (2021). Neurological side effects of SARS-CoV-2 vaccinations. *Acta Neurologica Scandinavica*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ane.13550>
- [656] Garg RK, Paliwal VK (2021). Spectrum of neurological complications following COVID-19 vaccination. *Neurological Sciences*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10072-021-05662-9>
- [657] Koh JS, Hoe RHM, Yong MH, ... Umapathi T (2021). Hospital-based observational study of neurological disorders in patients recently vaccinated with COVID-19 mRNA vaccines. *Journal of the Neurological Sciences* 430, 120030. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jns.2021.120030>
- [658] Takeyama R, Fukuda K, Kouzaki Y, ... Inoue T (2021). Intracerebral hemorrhage due to vasculitis following COVID-19 vaccination: A case report. *Acta Neurochirurgica*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00701-021-05038-0>

- [659] Perez-Lloret S, Petrovsky N, Alami A, ... Krewski D (2021). Disproportionality analysis of adverse neurological and psychiatric reactions with the ChAdOx1 (Oxford-AstraZeneca) and BNT162b2 (Pfizer-BioNTech) COVID-19 vaccines in the United Kingdom [Preprint]. *medRxiv*. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2021.09.28.21264245>
- [660] Loo LK, Salim O, Liang D, ... Rajabally YA (2021). Acute-onset polyradiculoneuropathy after SARS-CoV2 vaccine in the West and North Midlands, United Kingdom. *Muscle & Nerve*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1002/mus.27461>
- [661] Chakrabarti SS, Tiwari A, Jaiswal S, ... Chakrabarti S (2021). Rapidly progressive dementia with asymmetric rigidity following ChAdOx1 nCoV-19 vaccination. *Aging and Disease*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.14336/AD.2021.1102>
- [662] Classen JB (2021). Review of COVID-19 vaccines and the risk of chronic adverse events including neurological degeneration. *Journal of Medical-Clinical Research & Reviews* 5(3), 1–7. <https://www.scivisionpub.com/abstract-display.php?id=1746>
- [663] Ismail II, Salama S (2021). A systematic review of cases of CNS demyelination following COVID-19 vaccination. *Journal of Neuroimmunology*, 577765. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jneuroim.2021.577765>
- [664] Finsterer J, Scorza FA (2021). Letter to the editor: Ischemic stroke of the corpus callosum after SARS-CoV-2 vaccination. *Journal of Korean Medical Science* 36(40), e288. <https://doi.org/10.3346/jkms.2021.36.e288>
- [665] Ahmad SA, Salih BK, Hama Hussein KF, ... Salih AM (2021). Aseptic meningoencephalitis after COVID-19 vaccination: A case report. *Annals of Medicine and Surgery* 71, 103028. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.amsu.2021.103028>
- [666] Reis Carneiro D, Matos A, Morgadinho A (2021). Steroid-responsive aseptic meningitis after BNT162b2 SARS-CoV-2 vaccine. *Revue neurologique*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neurol.2021.10.002>
- [667] Nosedá R, Ripellino P, Ghidossi S, ... Ceschi A (2021). Reporting of acute inflammatory neuropathies with COVID-19 vaccines: Subgroup disproportionality analyses in VigiBase. *Vaccines* 9(9), 1022. <https://doi.org/10.3390/vaccines9091022>
- [668] Kanabar G, Wilkinson P (2021). Guillain-Barré syndrome presenting with facial diplegia following COVID-19 vaccination in two patients. *BMJ Case Reports* 14(10), e244527. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bcr-2021-244527>
- [669] Nagalli S, Kikkeri NS (2021). ‘Subacute’ onset of Guillain Barré syndrome post mRNA-1273 vaccination: A case report [Preprint]. *Research Square*. <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-922568/v1>
- [670] Gao J-J, Tseng H-P, Lin C-L, ... Liu C-H (2021). Acute transverse myelitis following COVID-19 vaccination. *Vaccines* 9(9), 1008. <https://doi.org/10.3390/vaccines9091008>

- [671] Azdaki N, Farzad M (2021). Long QT interval and syncope after a single dose of COVID-19 vaccination: A case report. *Pan African Medical Journal* 40, 67 <https://doi.org/10.11604/pamj.2021.40.67.31546>
- [672] Finsterer J, Korn M (2021). Aphasia seven days after second dose of an mRNA-based SARS-CoV-2 vaccine. *Brain Hemorrhages*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hest.2021.06.001>
- [673] Cellina M, D'Arrigo A, Floridi C, ... Carrafiello G (2022). Left Bell's palsy following the first dose of mRNA-1273 SARS-CoV-2 vaccine: A case report. *Clinical Imaging* 82, 1–4. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clinimag.2021.10.010>
- [674] Moghimi S, Wilson D, Martineau P (2021). FDG PET findings post-COVID vaccinations. *Clinical Nuclear Medicine* 46(5), 437–438. <https://doi.org/10.1097/rlu.0000000000003636>
- [675] Sharma A, Drachtman R, Capozzoli G (2021). Abnormal PET scan result after recent COVID vaccination. *Pediatric Blood & Cancer* 68(12), e29262. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pbc.29262>
- [676] Bauckneht M, Aloè T, Tagliabue E, ... Barisione E (2021). Beyond Covid-19 vaccination-associated pitfalls on [¹⁸F]Fluorodeoxyglucose (FDG) PET: A case of a concomitant sarcoidosis. *European Journal of Nuclear Medicine and Molecular Imaging* 48(8), 2661–2662. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00259-021-05360-w>
- [677] Treglia G, Cuzzocrea M, Giovanella L, ... Muoio B (2021). Prevalence and significance of hypermetabolic lymph nodes detected by 2-[¹⁸F]FDG PET/CT after COVID-19 vaccination: A systematic review and a meta-analysis. *Pharmaceuticals* 14(8), 762. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ph14080762>
- [678] Orevi M, Chicheportiche A, Ben-Haim S (2021). Lessons learned from post-COVID-19 vaccination PET/CT studies. *Journal of Nuclear Medicine*. Published ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.2967/jnumed.121.262348>
- [679] Laudicella R, Burger IA, Panasiti F, ... Alongi P (2021). Subcutaneous uptake on [18F]florbetaben PET/CT: A case report of possible amyloid-beta immune-reactivity after COVID-19 vaccination. *SN Comprehensive Clinical Medicine* 3, 2626–2628. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42399-021-01058-0>
- [680] Iwanaga J, Fukuoka H, Fukuoka N, ... Tubbs RS (2021). A narrative review and clinical anatomy of herpes zoster infection following COVID-19 vaccination. *Clinical Anatomy*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ca.23790>
- [681] Katsikas Triantafyllidis K, Giannos P, Mian IT, ... Kechagias KS (2021). Varicella zoster virus reactivation following COVID-19 vaccination: A systematic review of case reports. *Vaccines* 9(9), 1013. <https://doi.org/10.3390/vaccines9091013>
- [682] Ayatollahi A, Robati RM, Firooz A (2021). Plantar herpes zoster following heterologous recombinant adenovirus-based COVID-19 vaccine. *Journal of Cosmetic Dermatology*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jocd.14605>
- [683] Eid E, Abdullah L, Kurban M, Abbas O (2021). Herpes zoster emergence following mRNA COVID-19 vaccine. *Journal of Medical Virology* 93(9), 5231–5232. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jmv.27036>

- [684] Maldonado MD, Romero-Aibar J (2021). The Pfizer-BNT162b2 mRNA-based vaccine against SARS-CoV-2 may be responsible for awakening the latency of herpes varicella-zoster virus. *Brain, Behavior, & Immunity: Health* 18, 100381. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bbih.2021.100381>
- [685] Fukuoka H, Fukuoka N, Kibe T, ... Iwanaga J (2021). Oral herpes zoster infection following COVID-19 vaccination: A report of five cases. *Cureus* 13(11), e19433. <https://doi.org/10.7759/cureus.19433>
- [686] Mishra SB, Mahendradas P, Kawali A, ... Shetty R (2021). Reactivation of varicella zoster infection presenting as acute retinal necrosis post COVID 19 vaccination in an Asian Indian male. *European Journal of Ophthalmology*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1177/11206721211046485>
- [687] Thimmanagari K, Veeraballi S, Roach D, ... Slim J (2021). Ipsilateral zoster ophthalmicus post COVID-19 vaccine in healthy young adults. *Cureus* 13(7), e16725. <https://doi.org/10.7759/cureus.16725>
- [688] Alkhalifah MI, Alsobki HE, Alwael HM, ... Al-Mezaine HS (2021). Herpes simplex virus keratitis reactivation after SARS-CoV-2 BNT162b2 mRNA vaccination: A report of two cases. *Ocular Immunology and Inflammation*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09273948.2021.1986548>
- [689] Iwai S, Takayama K, Sora D, Takeuchi M (2021). A case of acute retinal necrosis associated with reactivation of varicella zoster virus after COVID-19 vaccination. *Ocular Immunology and Inflammation*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09273948.2021.2001541>
- [690] Puri P, Parnami P, Athwal PSS, ... Suri Y (2021). COVID-19 rekindling herpes zoster in an immunocompetent patient. *Cureus* 13(9), e18049. <https://doi.org/10.7759/cureus.18049>
- [691] Bernardini N, Skroza N, Mambrin A, ... Potenza C (2021). Herpes zoster ophthalmicus in two women after Pfizer–BioNTech (BNT162b2) vaccine. *Journal of Medical Virology*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jmv.27366>
- [692] Desai HD, Sharma K, Shah A, ... Goldust M (2021). Can SARS-CoV-2 vaccine increase the risk of reactivation of Varicella zoster? A systematic review. *Journal of Cosmetic Dermatology* 20(11), 3350–3361. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jocd.14521>
- [693] Song MY, Koh KM, Hwang KY, ... Kim KY (2021). Relapsed disciform stromal herpetic keratitis following mRNA COVID-19 vaccination. *Korean Journal of Ophthalmology*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.3341/kjo.2021.0150>
- [694] Mungmunpantipantip R, Wiwanitkit V (2021). Ramsay Hunt syndrome and mRNA SARS-COV-2 vaccination. *Enfermedades infecciosas y microbiología clínica*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eimc.2021.08.002>
- [695] Kluger N, Klimenko T, Bosonnet S (2021). Herpes simplex, herpes zoster and periorbital erythema flares after SARS-CoV-2 vaccination: 4 cases. *Annales de dermatologie et de vénéréologie*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.annder.2021.07.009>

- [696] Jia S, Luong T (2021). Atypical presentation of aseptic meningitis due to varicella zoster: A case report. *Clinical Practice and Cases in Emergency Medicine* 5(4), 440–442. <https://doi.org/10.5811/cpcem.2021.7.53596>
- [697] Maranini B, Ciancio G, Cultrera R, Govoni M (2021). Herpes zoster infection following mRNA COVID-19 vaccine in a patient with ankylosing spondylitis. *Reumatismo* 73(3), 174–176. <https://doi.org/10.4081/reumatismo.2021.1445>
- [698] Rodríguez-Martín M, Corriols-Noval P, López-Simón E, Morales-Angulo C (2021). Ramsay Hunt syndrome following mRNA SARS-COV-2 vaccine. *Enfermedades infecciosas y microbiología clínica (English ed.)*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eimce.2021.06.003>
- [699] Chiu H-H, Wei K-C, Chen A, Wang W-H (2021). Herpes zoster following COVID-19 vaccine: A report of three cases. *QJM* 114(7), 531–532. <https://doi.org/10.1093/qjmed/hcab208>
- [700] Park E, Mays C (2021). Herpes zoster ophthalmicus following Covid-19 vaccination: A case report. *Journal of Infectious Diseases & Case Reports* 2(3), 1–5. [https://doi.org/10.47363/jidscr/2021\(2\)143](https://doi.org/10.47363/jidscr/2021(2)143)
- [701] Santiano J (2021, October 7). Shingles after COVID-19 vaccination. *Dr. Jesse Santiano*. <https://drjessesantiano.com/shingles-after-covid-19-vaccination>
- [702] Santovito LS, Pinna G (2021). A case of reactivation of varicella-zoster virus after BNT162b2 vaccine second dose? *Inflammation Research* 70, 935–937. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00011-021-01491-w>
- [703] Henry D, Henry D (2021). Herpes zoster following ChAdOx1 nCoV-19 corona virus vaccine (recombinant): A case report. *Journal of Skin and Sexually Transmitted Diseases*. Online ahead of print. https://doi.org/10.25259/jsstd_73_2021
- [704] Psychogiou M, Samarkos M, Mikos N, Hatzakis A (2021). Reactivation of varicella zoster virus after vaccination for SARS-CoV-2. *Vaccines* 9(6), 572. <https://doi.org/10.3390/vaccines9060572>
- [705] van Dam CS, Lede I, Schaar J, ... Smits M (2021). Herpes zoster after COVID vaccination. *International Journal of Infectious Diseases* 111, 169–171. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijid.2021.08.048>
- [706] Vastarella M, Picone V, Martora F, Fabbrocini G (2021). Herpes zoster after ChAdOx1 nCoV-19 vaccine: A case series. *Journal of the European Academy of Dermatology and Venereology* 35(12), e845–e846. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jdv.17576>
- [707] Koumaki D, Krueger-Krasagakis S-E, Papadakis M, ... Krasagakis K (2021). Herpes zoster viral infection after AZD1222 and BNT162b2 coronavirus disease 2019 mRNA vaccines: A case series. *Journal of the European Academy of Dermatology and Venereology*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jdv.17720>
- [708] Furer V, Zisman D, Elkayam O (2021). Comment on “Herpes zoster following BNT162b2 mRNA Covid-19 vaccination in patients with autoimmune inflammatory rheumatic diseases: A case series”: Reply. *Rheumatology*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1093/rheumatology/keab702>

- [709] Furer V, Zisman D, Kibari A, ... Elkayam O (2021). Herpes zoster following BNT162b2 mRNA COVID-19 vaccination in patients with autoimmune inflammatory rheumatic diseases: A case series. *Rheumatology* 60(SI), SI90–SI95. <https://doi.org/10.1093/rheumatology/keab345>
- [710] Abu-Rumeileh S, Mayer B, Still V, ... Senel M (2021). Varicella zoster virus-induced neurological disease after COVID-19 vaccination: A retrospective monocentric study. *Journal of Neurology*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00415-021-10849-3>
- [711] Föhse FK, Geckin B, Overheul GJ, ... Netea MG (2021). The BNT162b2 mRNA vaccine against SARS-CoV-2 reprograms both adaptive and innate immune responses [Preprint]. *medRxiv*. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2021.05.03.21256520>
- [712] Tagliaferri AR, Horani G, Stephens K, Michael P (2021). A rare presentation of undiagnosed multiple sclerosis after the COVID-19 vaccine. *Journal of Community Hospital Internal Medicine Perspectives* 11(6), 772–775. <https://doi.org/10.1080/20009666.2021.1979745>
- [713] Classen JB (2021). COVID-19 RNA based vaccines and the risk of prion disease. *Microbiology & Infectious Diseases* 5(1), 1–3. <https://doi.org/10.33425/2639-9458.1109>
- [714] Tetz G, Tetz V (2020). SARS-CoV-2 prion-like domains in spike proteins enables higher affinity to ACE2 [Preprint]. *Preprints*. <https://doi.org/10.20944/preprints202003.0422.v1>
- [715] Lim J, Lee SA, Khil EK, ... Choi J-A (2021). COVID-19 vaccine-related axillary lymphadenopathy in breast cancer patients: Case series with a review of literature. *Seminars in Oncology*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1053/j.seminoncol.2021.10.002>
- [716] Keshavarz P, Yazdanpanah F, Rafiee F, Mizandari M (2021). Lymphadenopathy following COVID-19 vaccination: Imaging findings review. *Academic Radiology* 28(8), 1058–1071. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.acra.2021.04.007>
- [717] Hagen C, Nowack M, Messerli M, ... Bode PK (2021). Fine needle aspiration in COVID-19 vaccine-associated lymphadenopathy. *Swiss Medical Weekly* 151, w20557. <https://doi.org/10.4414/smw.2021.20557>
- [718] Shin M, Hyun CY, Choi YH, ... Cho YS (2021). COVID-19 vaccination-associated lymphadenopathy on FDG PET/CT. *Clinical Nuclear Medicine* 46(10), 814–819. <https://doi.org/10.1097/rlu.0000000000003800>
- [719] Cohen D, Hazut Krauthammer S, Cohen YC, ... Even-Sapir E (2021). Correlation between BNT162b2 mRNA Covid-19 vaccine-associated hypermetabolic lymphadenopathy and humoral immunity in patients with hematologic malignancy. *European Journal of Nuclear Medicine and Molecular Imaging* 48(11), 3540–3549. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00259-021-05389-x>
- [720] Tan HM, Hue SS-S, Wee A, See KC (2021). Kikuchi-Fujimoto disease post COVID-19 vaccination: Case report and review of literature. *Vaccines* 9(11), 1251. <https://doi.org/10.3390/vaccines9111251>

- [721] Özütemiz C, Potter DA, Özütemiz AÖ, Steinberger D (2021). Lymphadenopathy after the third Covid-19 vaccine. *Current Problems in Cancer: Case Reports* 4, 100127. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cpcpr.2021.100127>
- [722] Tan NJH, Tay KXJ, Wong SBJ, Nga ME (2021). COVID-19 post-vaccination lymphadenopathy: Report of cytological findings from fine needle aspiration biopsy. *Diagnostic Cytopathology* 49(12), E467–E470. <https://doi.org/10.1002/dc.24863>
- [723] Lane DL, Neelapu SS, Xu G, Weaver O (2021). COVID-19 vaccine-related axillary and cervical lymphadenopathy in patients with current or prior breast cancer and other malignancies: Cross-sectional imaging findings on MRI, CT, and PET-CT. *Korean Journal of Radiology* 22(12), 1938. <https://doi.org/10.3348/kjr.2021.0350>
- [724] Garver K (2021). Managing the risk of delayed breast cancer screening versus COVID-19 vaccination associated axillary lymphadenopathy. *Academic Radiology* 28(9), 1198–1199. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.acra.2021.07.022>
- [725] Soub HA, Ibrahim W, Maslamani MA, ... Abu-Dayeh A (2021). Kikuchi-Fujimoto disease following SARS CoV2 vaccination: Case report. *IDCases* 25, e01253. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.idcr.2021.e01253>
- [726] von Tresckow J, von Tresckow B, Reinhardt HC, ... Berliner C (2021). Thymic hyperplasia after mRNA based Covid-19 vaccination. *Radiology Case Reports* 16(12), 3744–3745. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.radcr.2021.08.050>
- [727] Rademacher J-G, Tampe B, Korsten P (2021). First report of two cases of Löfgren's syndrome after SARS-CoV-2 vaccination: Coincidence or causality? *Vaccines* 9(11), 1313. <https://doi.org/10.3390/vaccines9111313>
- [728] Sahin O (2021). Hypermetabolic axillary lymphadenopathy on FDG PET/CT due to COVID-19 vaccination. *Selcuk Medical Journal* 3(37), 269–275. <https://doi.org/10.30733/std.2021.01517>
- [729] Faermann R, Nissan N, Halshtok-Neiman O, ... Sklair-Levy M (2021). COVID-19 vaccination induced lymphadenopathy in a specialized breast imaging clinic in Israel: Analysis of 163 cases. *Academic Radiology* 28(9), 1191–1197. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.acra.2021.06.003>
- [730] Goldman S, Bron D, Tousseyn T, ... Goldman M (2021). Rapid progression of angioimmunoblastic T cell lymphoma following BNT162b2 mRNA vaccine booster shot: A case report. *Frontiers in Medicine* 8, 798095. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmed.2021.798095>
- [731] Park JY, Yi SY (2021). Rare case of contralateral supraclavicular lymphadenopathy after COVID-19 vaccination: Computed tomography and ultrasonography findings. *Radiology Case Reports* 16(12), 3879–3881. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.radcr.2021.09.042>
- [732] Raj S, Ogola G, Han J (2021). COVID-19 vaccine-associated subclinical axillary lymphadenopathy on screening mammogram. *Academic Radiology*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.acra.2021.11.010>

- [733] Teo SP (2021). Ipsilateral axillary adenopathy from mRNA COVID-19 vaccines. *Annals of Geriatric Medicine and Research* 25(3), 229–230. <https://doi.org/10.4235/agmr.21.0057>
- [734] Gambichler T, Boms S, Hessam S, ... Stranzenbach R (2021). Primary cutaneous anaplastic large-cell lymphoma with marked spontaneous regression of organ manifestation after SARS-CoV-2 vaccination. *British Journal of Dermatology*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bjd.20630>
- [735] Baek DW, Hwang S, Kim J, ... Sohn SK (2021). Patients presenting high fever with lymphadenopathy after COVID-19 vaccination were diagnosed with hemophagocytic lymphohistiocytosis. *Infectious Diseases*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23744235.2021.2010801>
- [736] Ashoor A, Shephard J, Lissidini G, Nicosia L (2021). Axillary adenopathy in patients with recent Covid-19 vaccination: A new diagnostic dilemma. *Korean Journal of Radiology* 22(12), 2124–2126. <https://doi.org/10.3348/kjr.2021.0635>
- [737] Ajmera KM (2021). Fatal case of rhabdomyolysis post-COVID-19 vaccine. *Infection and Drug Resistance* 14, 3929–3935. <https://doi.org/10.2147/idr.s331362>
- [738] Tan A, Stepien KM, Narayana STK (2021). Carnitine palmitoyltransferase II deficiency and post-COVID vaccination rhabdomyolysis. *QJM* 114(8), 596–597. <https://doi.org/10.1093/qjmed/hcab077>
- [739] Nassar M, Chung H, Dhayaparan Y, ... Kimball E (2021). COVID-19 vaccine induced rhabdomyolysis: Case report with literature review. *Diabetes & Metabolic Syndrome: Clinical Research & Reviews* 15(4), 102170. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dsx.2021.06.007>
- [740] Mack M, Nichols L, Guerrero DM (2021). Rhabdomyolysis secondary to COVID-19 vaccination. *Cureus* 13(5), e15004. <https://doi.org/10.7759/cureus.15004>
- [741] Elias C, Cardoso P, Gonçalves D, ... Cardoso L (2021). Rhabdomyolysis following administration of Comirnaty®. *European Journal of Case Reports in Internal Medicine* 8(8), 002796. https://doi.org/10.12890/2021_002796
- [742] Gelbenegger G, Cacioppo F, Firbas C, Jilma B (2021). Rhabdomyolysis following Ad26.COV2.S COVID-19 vaccination. *Vaccines* 9(9), 956. <https://doi.org/10.3390/vaccines9090956>
- [743] Faissner S, Richter D, Ceylan U, ... Gold R (2021). COVID-19 mRNA vaccine induced rhabdomyolysis and fasciitis. *Journal of Neurology*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00415-021-10768-3>
- [744] Cieśliewicz A, Dudek M, Krela-Kaźmierczak I, ... Korzeniowska K (2021). Pancreatic injury after COVID-19 vaccine: A case report. *Vaccines* 9(6), 576. <https://doi.org/10.3390/vaccines9060576>
- [745] Walter T, Connor S, Stedman C, Doogue M (2021). A case of acute necrotising pancreatitis following the second dose of Pfizer-BioNTech COVID-19 mRNA vaccine. *British Journal of Clinical Pharmacology*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bcp.15039>
- [746] Serazin NA, Edem B, Williams SR, ... Bastero P (2021). Acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS) as an adverse event following immunization: Case definition & guidelines for data collection,

analysis, and presentation of immunization safety data. *Vaccine* 39(22), 3028–3036. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.vaccine.2021.01.053>

[747] Colaneri M, De Filippo M, Licari A, ... Bruno R (2021). COVID vaccination and asthma exacerbation: Might there be a link? *International Journal of Infectious Diseases* 112, 243–246. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijid.2021.09.026>

[748] Ifeanyi N, Chinenye N, Oladiran O, ... Ogbonna-Nwosu C (2021). Isolated pulmonary embolism following COVID vaccination: 2 case reports and a review of post-acute pulmonary embolism complications and follow-up. *Journal of Community Hospital Internal Medicine Perspectives* 11(6), 877–879. <https://doi.org/10.1080/20009666.2021.1990825>

[749] Shimizu T, Watanabe S, Yoneda T, ... Kasahara K (2021). Interstitial pneumonitis after COVID-19 vaccination: A report of three cases. *Allergology International*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.alit.2021.10.003>

[750] Stoyanov DA, Thompson DG, Lee DM, Katelaris PC (2021). Delayed hypersensitivity to the Comirnaty COVID-19 vaccine presenting with pneumonitis and rash. *Annals of Allergy, Asthma & Immunology*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anai.2021.11.014>

[751] Klomjit N, Alexander MP, Fervenza FC, ... Zand L (2021). COVID-19 vaccination and glomerulonephritis. *Kidney International Reports*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ekir.2021.09.008>

[752] Masset C, Kervella D, Kandel-Aznar C, ... Hamidou M (2021). Relapse of IgG4-related nephritis following mRNA COVID-19 vaccine. *Kidney International* 100(2), 465–466. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.kint.2021.06.002>

[753] Kronbichler A, Jung SY, Kim MS, Shin JI (2021). Distinct glomerular disease association after vaccination with BNT162b2 and mRNA-1273: A Vigibase analysis. *Kidney International*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.kint.2021.11.013>

[754] De Fabritiis M, Angelini ML, Fabbrizio B, ... Mosconi G (2021). Renal thrombotic microangiopathy in concurrent COVID-19 vaccination and infection. *Pathogens* 10(8), 1045. <https://doi.org/10.3390/pathogens10081045>

[755] Wu HHL, Kalra PA, Chinnadurai R (2021). New-onset and relapsed kidney histopathology following COVID-19 vaccination: A systematic review. *Vaccines* 9(11), 1252. <https://doi.org/10.3390/vaccines9111252>

[756] Hassanzadeh S, Djamali A, Mostafavi L, & Pezeshgi A (2021). Kidney complications following COVID-19 vaccination: A review of the literature. *Journal of Nephro pharmacology* 11(1), e01. <https://doi.org/10.34172/npj.2022.01>

[757] Caza TN, Cassol CA, Messias N, H ... Larsen CP (2021). Glomerular disease in temporal association with SARS-CoV-2 vaccination: A series of 29 cases. *Kidney360* 2(11), 1770–1780. <https://doi.org/10.34067/kid.0005372021>

- [758] Liu F, Feng C, Mao J, Fu H (2021). New-onset and relapsing glomerular diseases related to COVID-19 vaccination. *Journal of Zhejiang University (Medical Sciences)* 50(4), 524–528. <https://doi.org/10.3724/zdxbyxb-2021-0156>
- [759] Mira FS, Costa Carvalho J, Almeida PA de, ... Alves R (2021). A case of acute interstitial nephritis after two doses of the BNT162b2 SARS-CoV-2 vaccine. *International Journal of Nephrology and Renovascular Disease* 14, 421–426. <https://doi.org/10.2147/ijnrd.s345898>
- [760] Feghali E, Zafar M, Abid S, ... Mehta S (2021) De-novo antineutrophil cytoplasmic antibody-associated vasculitis following the mRNA-1273 (Moderna) vaccine for COVID-19. *Cureus* 13(11), e19616. <https://doi.org/10.7759/cureus.19616>
- [761] Coto-Segura P, Fernández-Prada M, Mir-Bonafé M, ... Martín-Torres F (2021). Vesiculobullous skin reactions induced by COVID-19 mRNA vaccine: Report of four cases and review of the literature. *Clinical and Experimental Dermatology*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ced.14835>
- [762] Shamsabadi A, Golezar MH, Mardani A, ... Qaderi K (2021). Cutaneous adverse reactions of COVID-19 vaccines: A systematic review [Preprint]. *Research Square*. <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-1000625/v1>
- [763] Temiz SA, Abdelmaksoud A, Wollina U, ... Vestita M (2021). Cutaneous and allergic reactions due to COVID-19 vaccinations: A review. *Journal of Cosmetic Dermatology*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jocd.14613>
- [764] Bataille V, Puig S (2021). COVID-19 vaccines and skin manifestations. *British Journal of Dermatology*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bjd.20807>
- [765] Wollina U, Chiriac A, Kocic H, ... Brzezinski P (2021). Cutaneous and hypersensitivity reactions associated with COVID-19 vaccination: A narrative review. *Wiener Medizinische Wochenschrift*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10354-021-00876-0>
- [766] Burlando M, Herzum A, Micalizzi C, ... Parodi A (2021). Cutaneous reactions to COVID-19 vaccine at the dermatology primary care. *Immunity, Inflammation and Disease*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1002/iid3.568>
- [767] Falkenhain-López D, Gutiérrez-Collar C, Arroyo-Andrés J, ... Sánchez-Velázquez A (2021). Widespread purpura annularis telangiectodes following mRNA SARS-CoV-2 vaccine. *Journal of the European Academy of Dermatology and Venereology* 35(11), e719–e721. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jdv.17497>
- [768] Gambichler T, Boms S, Susok L, ... Kasakovski D (2021). Cutaneous findings following COVID-19 vaccination: Review of world literature and own experience. *Journal of the European Academy of Dermatology and Venereology*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jdv.17744>
- [769] Atak MF, Farabi B, Kalelioglu MB, Rao BK (2021). Pigmented purpuric dermatosis after BNT162B2 mRNA COVID-19 vaccine administration. *Journal of Cosmetic Dermatology*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jocd.14607>

[770]

[771] Bellinato F, Maurelli M, Gisondi P, Girolomoni G (2021). Cutaneous adverse reactions associated with SARS-CoV-2 vaccines. *Journal of Clinical Medicine* 10(22), 5344. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jcm10225344>

[772] Pourani MR, Shahidi Dadras M, Salari M, ... Abdollahimajd F (2021). Cutaneous adverse events related to COVID-19 vaccines: A cross-sectional questionnaire-based study of 867 patients. *Dermatologic Therapy*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1111/dth.15223>

[773] Pacheco-Ambriz D, Félix-Guerrero LL, Olivas-Cárdenas GA, ... Díaz-Amezquita L (2021). Síndrome de Stevens-Johnson asociado con la administración de vacuna Janssen Ad26.COVS2.S COVID-19 en Tijuana, Baja California, México. *Dermatología* 65(5), 804–808. <https://doi.org/10.24245/dermatolrevmex.v65i5.6913>

[774] Freeman EE, Sun Q, McMahon DE, ... Fox LP (2021). Skin reactions to COVID-19 vaccines: An AAD/ILDS registry update on reaction location and COVID vaccine type. *Journal of the American Academy of Dermatology*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaad.2021.11.016>

[775] Niebel D, Wenzel J, Wilsmann-Theis D, ... Braegelmann C (2021). Single-center clinicopathological case study of 19 patients with cutaneous adverse reactions following COVID-19 vaccines. *Dermatopathology* 8(4), 463–476. <https://doi.org/10.3390/dermatopathology8040049>

[776] Niebel D, Novak N, Wilhelmi J, ... Braegelmann C (2021). Cutaneous adverse reactions to COVID-19 vaccines: Insights from an immuno-dermatological perspective. *Vaccines* 9(9), 944. <https://doi.org/10.3390/vaccines9090944>

[777] Català A, Muñoz-Santos C, Galván-Casas C, ... Guilabert A (2021). Cutaneous reactions after SARS-CoV-2 vaccination: A cross-sectional Spanish nationwide study of 405 cases. *British Journal of Dermatology*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bjd.20639>

[778] Hussain K, Kawsar A, Weir J, ... Fearfield L (2021). Severe cutaneous adverse reaction following COVID-19 vaccination and immunotherapy: A second hit? *Clinical and Experimental Dermatology*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ced.14852>

[779] Agarwal A, Panda M, Behera BK, Jena AK (2021). Benign cutaneous reactions post-COVID-19 vaccination: A case series of 16 patients from a tertiary care center in India. *Journal of Cosmetic Dermatology*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jocd.14592>

[780] Pedrazini MC, Silva MH (2021). Pityriasis rosea-like cutaneous eruption as a possible dermatological manifestation after Oxford-AstraZeneca vaccine: Case report and brief literature review. *Dermatologic Therapy*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1111/dth.15129>

[781] Temiz SA, Abdelmaksoud A, Dursun R, ... Hasan A (2021). Pityriasis rosea following SARS-CoV-2 vaccination: A case series. *Journal of Cosmetic Dermatology* 20(10), 3080–3084. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jocd.14372>

- [782] Shin SH, Hong JK, Hong SA, ... Yoo KH (2022). Pityriasis rosea shortly after mRNA-1273 COVID-19 vaccination. *International Journal of Infectious Diseases* 114, 88–89. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijid.2021.10.055>
- [783] Adya KA, Inamadar AC, Albadri W (2021). Post Covid-19 vaccination papulovesicular pityriasis rosea-like eruption in a young male. *Dermatologic Therapy* 34(5), e15040. <https://doi.org/10.1111/dth.15040>
- [784] Leerunyakul K, Pakornphadungsit K, Suchonwanit P (2021). Case report: Pityriasis rosea-like eruption following COVID-19 vaccination. *Frontiers in Medicine* 8, 752443. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmed.2021.752443>
- [785] Bostan E, Jarbou A (2021). Atypical pityriasis rosea associated with mRNA COVID-19 vaccine. *Journal of Medical Virology*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jmv.27364>
- [786] Sirufo MM, Raggiunti M, Magnanimiti LM, ... De Martinis M (2021). Henoch-Schönlein purpura following the first dose of COVID-19 viral vector vaccine: A case report. *Vaccines* 9(10), 1078. <https://doi.org/10.3390/vaccines9101078>
- [787] Piccolo V, Mazzatenta C, Bassi A, ... Russo T (2021). COVID vaccine-induced lichen planus on areas previously affected by vitiligo. *Journal of the European Academy of Dermatology and Venereology*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jdv.17687>
- [788] Gregoriou S, Kleidona IA, Tsimpidakis A, ... Rigopoulos D (2021). ‘COVID vaccine arm’ may present after both mRNA vaccines vaccination. *Journal of the European Academy of Dermatology and Venereology* 35(12), e867–e868. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jdv.17614>
- [789] Ricke DO, Malone RW (2021). COVID-19 arm: Delayed post-vaccination cutaneous hypersensitivity. *Clinical Dermatology and Investigations* 3(1), 004. <https://scientonline.org/abstract/21975>
- [790] Komiya H, Harada K, Morishita R, ... Tanaka F (2021). “COVID arm” detected by MR neurography. *eNeurologicalSci* 25, 100377. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ensci.2021.100377>
- [791] Baffa ME, Maglie R, Giovannozzi N, ... Antiga E (2021). Sweet syndrome following SARS-CoV2 vaccination. *Vaccines* 9(11), 1212. <https://doi.org/10.3390/vaccines9111212>
- [792] Krüger K (2021). Erythema-chronicum-migrans-artiges Bild als Folge der COVID-Impfung. *Zeitschrift für Rheumatologie*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00393-021-01024-0>
- [793] Kim JC, Lee SY, Kang SY, ... Chung BY (2021). Erythema annulare centrifugum induced by COVID-19 vaccination. *Clinical and Experimental Dermatology*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ced.15002>
- [794] Iwasawa O, Kamiya K, Okada H, ... Ohtsuki M (2021). A case of erythroderma with elevated serum immunoglobulin E and thymus and activation-regulated chemokine levels following coronavirus disease 2019 vaccination. *The Journal of Dermatology*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1346-8138.16257>

- [795] Fang W, Chiu L, Hu SC (2021). Psoriasis exacerbation after first dose of AstraZeneca coronavirus disease 2019 vaccine. *The Journal of Dermatology* 48(11), e566–e567. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1346-8138.16137>
- [796] Khan TA, Sidhu N, Khan L, ... Gupta N (2021). Bilateral immune-mediated keratolysis after immunization with SARS-CoV-2 recombinant viral vector vaccine. *Cornea*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1097/ico.0000000000002844>
- [797] Essam R, Ehab R, Al-Razzaz R, ... Moustafa EA (2021). Alopecia areata after ChAdOx1 nCoV-19 vaccine (Oxford/AstraZeneca): A potential triggering factor? *Journal of Cosmetic Dermatology* 20(12), 3727–3729. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jocd.14459>
- [798] Gambichler T, Hamdani N, Budde H, ... Becker JC (2021). Bullous pemphigoid after SARS-CoV-2 vaccination: Spike protein-directed immunofluorescence confocal microscopy and T cell receptor studies. *British Journal of Dermatology*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bjd.20890>
- [799] Ciccarese G, Drago F, Boldrin S, ... Parodi A (2021). Sudden onset of vitiligo after COVID-19 vaccine. *Dermatologic Therapy*, e15196. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1111/dth.15196>
- [800] Nik Muhamad Affendi NA, Ravindran S, Siam TS, ... Hilmi I (2021). Jaundice in a primary sclerosing cholangitis patient: A new cause in a new era. *Inflammatory Bowel Diseases*, izab250. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ibd/izab250>
- [801] Hatem T, Rii ER (2021). Real concerns over COVID-19 variants of concern [Preprint]. *OSF Preprints*. <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/v5b4k>
- [802] Mackinnon MJ, Gandon S, Read AF (2008). Virulence evolution in response to vaccination: The case of malaria. *Vaccine* 26(Supplement 3), C42–C52. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.vaccine.2008.04.012>
- [803] Wang R, Chen J, Wei G-W (2021). Mechanisms of SARS-CoV-2 evolution revealing vaccine-resistant mutations in Europe and America. *The Journal of Physical Chemistry Letters* 12(XXX), 11850–11857. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jpcclett.1c03380>
- [804] Eroshenko N, Gill T, Keaveney MK, ... Rajaniemi H (2020). Implications of antibody-dependent enhancement of infection for SARS-CoV-2 countermeasures. *Nature Biotechnology* 38(7), 789–791. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41587-020-0577-1>
- [805] Lee WS, Wheatley AK, Kent SJ, DeKosky BJ (2020). Antibody-dependent enhancement and SARS-CoV-2 vaccines and therapies. *Nature Microbiology* 5(10), 1185–1191. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41564-020-00789-5>
- [806] Arvin AM, Fink K, Schmid MA, ... Virgin HW (2020). A perspective on potential antibody-dependent enhancement of SARS-CoV-2. *Nature* 584(7821), 353–363. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-020-2538-8>
- [807] Liu L, Wei Q, Lin Q, ... Chen Z (2019). Anti-spike IgG causes severe acute lung injury by skewing macrophage responses during acute SARS-CoV infection. *JCI Insight* 4(4), e123158. <https://doi.org/10.1172/jci.insight.123158>

- [808] Tinari S (2021). The EMA covid-19 data leak, and what it tells us about mRNA instability. *BMJ* 372, n627. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.n627>
- [809] Ishay Y, Kenig A, Tsemach-Toren T, ... Kharouf F (2021). Autoimmune phenomena following SARS-CoV-2 vaccination. *International Immunopharmacology* 99, 107970. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.intimp.2021.107970>
- [810] Park JW, Yu SN, Chang SH, ... Jeon MH (2021). Multisystem inflammatory syndrome in an adult after COVID-19 vaccination: A case report and literature review. *Journal of Korean Medical Science* 36(45), e312. <https://doi.org/10.3346/jkms.2021.36.e312>
- [811] McCullough PA, Bernstein I, Jovanovic S, ... Stricker RB (2021, July 30). Lack of compelling safety data for mRNA COVID vaccines in pregnant women. *TrialSiteNews*. <https://trialsitenews.com/lack-of-compelling-safety-data-for-mrna-covid-vaccines-in-pregnant-women>
- [812] Navarra A, Albani E, Castellano S, ... Levi-Setti PE (2020). Coronavirus disease-19 infection: Implications on male fertility and reproduction. *Frontiers in Physiology* 11, 574761. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fphys.2020.574761>
- [813] Wang Z, Xu X (2020). scRNA-seq profiling of human testes reveals the presence of the ACE2 receptor, a target for SARS-CoV-2 infection in spermatogonia, Leydig and Sertoli cells. *Cells* 9(4), 920. <https://doi.org/10.3390/cells9040920>
- [814] Karrow NA, Shandilya UK, Pelech S, ... Mallard BA (2021). Maternal COVID-19 vaccination and its potential impact on fetal and neonatal development. *Vaccines* 9(11), 1351. <https://doi.org/10.3390/vaccines9111351>
- [815] Odell J (2021, June 30). Syncytin: Viruses, vaccines, and infertility. *Bioregulatory Medicine Institute*. <https://www.biologicalmedicineinstitute.com/post/syncytin-viruses-vaccines-and-infertility>
- [816] Van Spall HGC (2021). Exclusion of pregnant and lactating women from COVID-19 vaccine trials: A missed opportunity. *European Heart Journal* 42(28), 2724–2726. <https://doi.org/10.1093/eurheartj/ehab103>
- [817] Shimabukuro TT, Kim SY, Myers TR, ... Meaney-Delman DM (2021). Preliminary findings of mRNA Covid-19 vaccine safety in pregnant persons. *New England Journal of Medicine* 384(24), 2273–2282. <https://doi.org/10.1056/nejmoa2104983>
- [818] Sun H (2021). On preliminary findings of mRNA Covid-19 vaccine safety in pregnant persons. *New England Journal of Medicine* 385(16), 1535–1536. <https://doi.org/10.1056/nejmc2113516>
- [819] Anonymous (2021). Preliminary findings of mRNA Covid-19 vaccine safety in pregnant persons. *New England Journal of Medicine* 385(16), 1536. <https://doi.org/10.1056/nejmx210016>
- [820] Ahmed AKK, Elkazzaz M (2021). Are babies of vaccinated pregnant and lactating mothers with ChAdOx1 AstraZeneca covid vaccine more risk for zinc deficiency and SCID disease [Preprint]. *ScienceOpen Preprints*. <https://doi.org/10.14293/s2199-1006.1.sor-.pp3sfae.v1>

- [821] Palmer M, Bhakdi S (2021, July 23). The Pfizer mRNA vaccine: Pharmacokinetics and toxicity. *Doctors for COVID Ethics*. <https://doctors4covidethics.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/07/Pfizer-pharmacokinetics-and-toxicity.pdf>
- [822] Nordin MM, Musa H (2021). Will the mRNA vaccines interfere with one's DNA? *Bangladesh Journal of Medical Science* 20(2), 463–464. <https://doi.org/10.3329/bjms.v20i2.51567>
- [823] Zhang L, Richards A, Barrasa MI, ... Jaenisch R (2021). Reverse-transcribed SARS-CoV-2 RNA can integrate into the genome of cultured human cells and can be expressed in patient-derived tissues. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America* 118(21), e2105968118. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2105968118>
- [824] McLachlan S, Osman M, Dube K, ... Fenton N (2021). Analysis of COVID-19 vaccine death reports from the Vaccine Adverse Events Reporting System (VAERS) database [Preprint]. *ResearchGate*. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.26987.26402>
- [825] Torjesen I (2021). Covid-19: Pfizer-BioNTech vaccine is “likely” responsible for deaths of some elderly patients, Norwegian review finds. *BMJ* 373, n1372. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.n1372>
- [826] Torjesen I (2021). Covid-19: Norway investigates 23 deaths in frail elderly patients after vaccination. *BMJ* 372, n149. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.n149>
- [827] Schneider J, Sottmann L, Greinacher A, ... Schmeling A (2021). Postmortem investigation of fatalities following vaccination with COVID-19 vaccines. *International Journal of Legal Medicine* 135, 2335–2345. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00414-021-02706-9>
- [828] Classen JB (2021). US COVID-19 vaccines proven to cause more harm than good based on pivotal clinical trial data analyzed using the proper scientific endpoint, “all cause severe morbidity”. *Trends in Internal Medicine* 1(1), 1–6. <https://www.scivisionpub.com/abstract-display.php?id=1811>
- [829] Pantazatos SP, Seligmann H (2021). COVID vaccination and age-stratified all-cause mortality risk [Preprint]. *ResearchGate*. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.28257.43366>
- [830] Walach H, Klement RJ, Aukema W (2021). The safety of COVID-19 vaccinations: We should rethink the policy [Retracted]. *Vaccines* 9(7), 693. <https://doi.org/10.3390/vaccines9070693>
- [831] Vaccines Editorial Office (2021). Expression of concern: Walach et al. The safety of COVID-19 vaccinations: We should rethink the policy. *Vaccines* 2021, 9, 693. *Vaccines* 9(7), 705. <https://doi.org/10.3390/vaccines9070705>
- [832] Vaccines Editorial Office (2021). Retraction: Walach et al. The safety of COVID-19 vaccinations: We should rethink the policy. *Vaccines* 2021, 9, 693. *Vaccines* 9(7), 729. <https://doi.org/10.3390/vaccines9070729>
- [833] Walach K, Klement RJ, Aukema W (2021). The safety of COVID-19 vaccinations: Should we rethink the policy? *Science, Public Health Policy, and the Law* 3, 87–99. https://www.publichealthpolicyjournal.com/files/ugd/adf864_8c97b2396c2842b3b05975bfbfd8254cb.pdf

- [834] Index Vijesti (2021, November 19). Liječnik iz Dubrave: Ljudi koji ne vjeruju u virus i cjepiva su kao ravnozemljaši. *Index.hr*. <https://www.index.hr/vijesti/clanak/lijecnik-iz-dubrave-ljudi-koji-ne-vjeruju-u-virus-i-cjepiva-su-kao-ravnozemljasi/2319467.aspx>
- [835] N1 Hrvatska (2021, December 8). Infektolog: mRNA cjepivo protiv korone je jedno od najsigurnijih cjepiva. *N1 info*. <https://hr.n1info.com/vijesti/infektolog-mrna-cjepivo-protiv-korone-je-jedno-od-najsigurnijih-cjepiva-ikd>
- [836] Barišić I (2021, October 25). Imunolog objasnio koje su najčešće ozbiljne nuspojave cijepljenja kod djece: Postoji veliki šum u komunikaciji. *tportal*. <https://www.tportal.hr/vijesti/clanak/imunolog-objasnio-koje-su-najcesce-ozbiljne-nuspojave-cijepljenja-kod-djece-upozorio-i-da-se-covid-potvrde-sire-trebaju-koristiti-foto-20211025>
- [837] Jarić Dauenhauer N (2021, June 6). Nuspojave nakon cijepljenja su dobar znak: Je li problem ako ih nemate? *Index.hr*. <https://www.index.hr/vijesti/clanak/nuspojave-nakon-cijepljenja-su-dobar-znak-je-li-problem-ako-ih-nemate/2281136.aspx>
- [838] RTL Vijesti (2021, November 3). Cijepljenje djece u školama? Naša epidemiologinja kaže da je moguće da do toga dođe, ali samo pod jednim uvjetom. *RTL.hr*. <https://www.rtl.hr/vijesti-hr/novosti/hrvatska/4132768>
- [839] Index Vijesti (2020, December 22). Liječnica iz HZJZ-a: Cjepivo je sigurno, a ovo su moguće nuspojave. *Index.hr*. <https://www.index.hr/vijesti/clanak/lijecnica-iz-hzjz-a-opisala-koje-su-moguće-nuspojave-cjepiva-protiv-korone/2240859.aspx>
- [840] Index Vijesti (2021, October 9). Capakova pomoćnica: Prije ćete dobiti jackpot nego dobiti tešku nuspojavu na cjepivo. *Index.hr*. <https://www.index.hr/vijesti/clanak/bubas-prije-cete-dobiti-jackpot-nego-dobiti-tesku-nuspojavu-na-cjepivo/2317133.aspx>
- [841] Trobonjača Z, Marković S, Korajlija A, Dejanović R (2021, November 14). Imunolog, farmaceut, psihologinja i novinar za Index objašnjavaju zašto se cijepiti. *Index.hr*. <https://www.index.hr/vijesti/clanak/imunolog-farmaceut-psihologinja-i-novinar-pisu-za-index-zasto-se-cijepiti/2318107.aspx>
- [842] Sell TK, Hosangadi D, Trotochaud M (2020). Misinformation and the US Ebola communication crisis: Analyzing the veracity and content of social media messages related to a fear-inducing infectious disease outbreak. *BMC Public Health* 20, 550. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-020-08697-3>
- [843] Štrkalj Despot K, Ostroški Anić A (2021). A war on war metaphor: Metaphorical framings in Croatian discourse on COVID-19. *Rasprave Instituta za hrvatski jezik i jezikoslovlje* 47(1), 173–208. <https://doi.org/10.31724/rihjj.47.1.6>
- [844] Rutović Ž (2021). Medijska prodaja straha (COVID 19 – Infodemija – Sociologija promjene). *In medias res* 10(19), 3009–3020. <https://doi.org/10.46640/imr.10.19.4>
- [845] Pavelić K (2021). Današnji mediji: Problemi i manipulacije. *In medias res* 10(19), 2959–2968. <https://doi.org/10.46640/imr.10.19.1>

- [846] Fejzić-Čengić F (2021). Medijsko praćenje ponašanja religijskih hijerarhija u doba epidemije. *In medias res* 10(19), 3021–3031. <https://doi.org/10.46640/imr.10.19.5>
- [847] Broudy D (2021). Vaccine development and social control: A psychopathology of impaired reasoning in the global push for mass compliance. *International Journal of Vaccine Theory, Practice, and Research* 2(1), 93–124. <https://ijvtpr.com/index.php/IJVTPR/article/view/29>
- [848] Broudy D, Hoop D (2021). Messianic mad men, medicine, and the media war on empirical reality: Discourse analysis of mainstream Covid-19 propaganda. *International Journal of Vaccine Theory, Practice, and Research* 2(1), 1–24. <https://www.ijvtpr.com/index.php/IJVTPR/article/view/22>
- [849] Bulatović LL, Bulatović G (2021). Media frames of COVID-19 pandemic. *In medias res* 10(19), 2969–2986. <https://doi.org/10.46640/imr.10.19.2>
- [850] Quinn GA, Óh Aiseadha C, Connolly R, Hynds P (2021). A tale of two scientific paradigms: Conflicting scientific opinions on what “following the science” means for SARS-CoV-2 and the COVID-19 pandemic [Preprint]. *OSF Preprints*. <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/s9z2p>
- [851] Vlajki E (2021). Coronavirus in light of philosophy. *Media, Culture and Public Relations* 12(1), 6–32. <https://doi.org/10.32914/mcpr.12.1.1>
- [852] Vlajki E (2021). End of history, COVID 19, and New Leviathan: The broken communication between modernism and postmodernism. *Media, Culture and Public Relations* 12(2), 124–156. <https://doi.org/10.32914/mcpr.12.2.1>
- [853] Vujić J (2021). Simulacija kolektivne tjeskobe i medijske fobo-strategije politike straha. *In medias res* 10(19), 3033–3042. <https://doi.org/10.46640/imr.10.19.6>
- [854] O’Keefe J (2022). *American Muckraker: Rethinking Journalism for the 21st Century*. New York, NY: Post Hill Press. <https://www.worldcat.org/title/american-muckraker-rethinking-journalism-for-the-21st-century/oclc/1260663950>
- [855] Di Domenico L, Pullano G, Sabbatini CE, ... Colizza V (2020). Impact of lockdown on COVID-19 epidemic in Île-de-France and possible exit strategies. *BMC Medicine* 18, 240. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12916-020-01698-4>
- [856] Lau H, Khosrawipour V, Kocbach P, ... Khosrawipour T (2020). The positive impact of lockdown in Wuhan on containing the COVID-19 outbreak in China. *Journal of Travel Medicine* 27(3), 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jtm/taaa037>
- [857] Siqueira CA dos S, Freitas YNL de, Cancela M de C, ... de Souza DLB (2020). The effect of lockdown on the outcomes of COVID-19 in Spain: An ecological study. *PLoS ONE* 15(7), e0236779. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0236779>
- [858] Alfano V, Ercolano S (2020). The efficacy of lockdown against COVID-19: A cross-country panel analysis. *Applied Health Economics and Health Policy* 18(4), 509–517. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40258-020-00596-3>

- [859] Farsalinos K, Poulas K, Kouretas D, ... Tsatsakis A (2021). Improved strategies to counter the COVID-19 pandemic: Lockdowns vs. primary and community healthcare. *Toxicology Reports* 8, 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.toxrep.2020.12.001>
- [860] Chaudhry R, Dranitsaris G, Mubashir T, ... Riazi S (2020). A country level analysis measuring the impact of government actions, country preparedness and socioeconomic factors on COVID-19 mortality and related health outcomes. *EClinicalMedicine* 25, 100464. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eclinm.2020.100464>
- [861] Bendavid E, Oh C, Bhattacharya J, Ioannidis JPA (2021). Assessing mandatory stay-at-home and business closure effects on the spread of COVID-19. *European Journal of Clinical Investigation* 51(4), e13484. <https://doi.org/10.1111/eci.13484>
- [862] Bendavid E, Oh C, Bhattacharya J, Ioannidis JPA (2021). Authors response to letters to the editor regarding: ‘Assessing mandatory stay-at-home and business closure effects on the spread of COVID-19’. *European Journal of Clinical Investigation* 51(6), e13553. <https://doi.org/10.1111/eci.13553>
- [863] De Laroche Lambert Q, Marc A, Antero J, ... Toussaint J-F (2020). Covid-19 mortality: A matter of vulnerability among nations facing limited margins of adaptation. *Frontiers in Public Health* 8, 604339. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2020.604339>
- [864] Loewenthal G, Abadi S, Avram O, ... Pupko T (2020). COVID-19 pandemic-related lockdown: Response time is more important than its strictness. *EMBO Molecular Medicine* 12, e13171. <https://doi.org/10.15252/emmm.202013171>
- [865] Berry CR, Fowler A, Glazer T, ... MacMillen A (2021). Evaluating the effects of shelter-in-place policies during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America* 118(15), e2019706118. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2019706118>
- [866] Agrawal V, Cantor J, Sood N, Whaley C (2021). The impact of the COVID-19 pandemic and policy responses on excess mortality. *National Bureau of Economic Research* 2021, 28930. <https://doi.org/10.3386/w28930>
- [867] He E (2020, May 20). The results of Europe’s lockdown experiment are in. *Bloomberg*. <https://www.bloomberg.com/graphics/2020-opinion-coronavirus-europe-lockdown-excess-deaths-recession>
- [868] Hunter PR, Colón-González FJ, Brainard J, Rushton S (2021). Impact of non-pharmaceutical interventions against COVID-19 in Europe in 2020: A quasi-experimental non-equivalent group and time series design study. *Eurosurveillance* 26(28), 2001401. <https://doi.org/10.2807/1560-7917.es.2021.26.28.2001401>
- [869] Savaris RF, Pumi G, Dalzochio J, Kunst R (2021). Stay-at-home policy is a case of exception fallacy: An internet-based ecological study. *Scientific Reports* 11, 5313. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-021-84092-1>

- [870] Letizia AG, Ramos I, Obla A, ... Sealfon SC (2020). SARS-CoV-2 transmission among marine recruits during quarantine. *New England Journal of Medicine* 383(25), 2407–2416. <https://doi.org/10.1056/nejmoa2029717>
- [871] Ben-Israel D (2020, April 19). The end of exponential growth: The decline in the spread of coronavirus. *The Times of Israel*. <https://www.timesofisrael.com/the-end-of-exponential-growth-the-decline-in-the-spread-of-coronavirus>
- [872] Bjørnskov C (2021). Did lockdown work? An economist's cross-country comparison. *CESifo Economic Studies* 67(3), 318–331. <https://doi.org/10.1093/cesifo/ifab003>
- [873] Kepp KP, Bjørnskov C (2021). Lockdown effects on Sars-CoV-2 transmission: The evidence from Northern Jutland [Preprint]. *medRxiv*. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2020.12.28.20248936>
- [874] Kepp KP, Bjørnskov C (2020). Lockdown effects on Sars-CoV-2 transmission: The evidence from Northern Jutland [Preprint]. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3756920>
- [875] Joffe AR (2021). COVID-19: Rethinking the lockdown groupthink. *Frontiers in Public Health* 9, 625778. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2021.625778>
- [876] Melnick ER, Ioannidis JPA (2020). Should governments continue lockdown to slow the spread of covid-19? *BMJ* 369, m1924. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.m1924>
- [877] Herby J (2021). A first literature review: Lockdowns only had a small effect on COVID-19 [Preprint]. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3764553>
- [878] Allen DW (2021). Covid lockdown cost/benefits: A critical assessment of the literature [Unpublished]. *Simon Fraser University*. <http://www.sfu.ca/~allen/LockdownReport.pdf>
- [879] Spiegel M, Tookes H (2021). Business restrictions and COVID-19 fatalities. *The Review of Financial Studies* 34(11), 5266–5308. <https://doi.org/10.1093/rfs/hhab069>
- [880] Coccia M (2021). The relation between length of lockdown, numbers of infected people and deaths of Covid-19, and economic growth of countries: Lessons learned to cope with future pandemics similar to Covid-19 and to constrain the deterioration of economic system. *Science of the Total Environment* 775, 145801. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2021.145801>
- [881] Joffe AR, Redman D (2021). The SARS-CoV-2 pandemic in high income countries such as Canada: A better way forward without lockdowns [Preprint]. *OSF Preprints*. <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/r8d6f>
- [882] Dainton C, Hay A (2021). Quantifying the relationship between lockdowns, mobility, and effective reproduction number (Rt) during the COVID-19 pandemic in the greater Toronto area [Preprint]. *Research Square*. <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-378425/v1>
- [883] Bjørnskov C, Voigt S (2021). This time is different? On the use of emergency measures during the corona pandemic. *European Journal of Law and Economics*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10657-021-09706-5>

- [884] Wittkowsky K (2021, March 22). The lockdowns are creating a new virus – Then we have a new epidemic. *Dryburgh.com*. <https://dryburgh.com/knut-wittkowski-lockdowns-are-creating-a-new-virus>
- [885] Nicola M, Alsafi Z, Sohrabi C, ... Agha R (2020). The socio-economic implications of the coronavirus pandemic (COVID-19): A review. *International Journal of Surgery* 78, 185–193. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijssu.2020.04.018>
- [886] Atar S, Atar I (2020). An invited commentary on “The socio-economic implications of the coronavirus and COVID-19 pandemic: A review”. *International Journal of Surgery* 78, 122. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijssu.2020.04.054>
- [887] Sardar S, Abdul-Khaliq I, Ingar A, ... Mansour N (2020). COVID-19 lockdown – A protective measure or exacerbator of health inequalities? A comparison between the United Kingdom and India: A commentary on “The socio-economic implications of the coronavirus and COVID-19 pandemic: A review”. *International Journal of Surgery* 83, 189–191. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijssu.2020.09.044>
- [888] Cheng SO (2020). Xenophobia due to the coronavirus outbreak: A letter to the editor in response to “The socio-economic implications of the coronavirus pandemic (COVID-19): A review”. *International Journal of Surgery* 79, 13–14. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijssu.2020.05.017>
- [889] Hussain S, Ibrar M, Shah NH (2020). Corona disease (COVID-19) and its impacts on society: A review of the existing literature. *International Review of Social Sciences* 8(7), 127–134. https://irss.academyirmbr.com/paper_details.php?id=535
- [890] Simon J, Helder TM, White RG, ... Łaszewska A (2021). Impacts of the Covid-19 lockdown and relevant vulnerabilities on capability well-being, mental health and social support: An Austrian survey study. *BMC Public Health* 21, 314. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-021-10351-5>
- [891] Tokić A, Gusar I, Nikolić Ivanišević M (2021). Zadovoljstvo poslom i mentalno zdravlje zdravstvenih djelatnika u Hrvatskoj u vrijeme pandemije COVID-19. *Društvena istraživanja* 30(2), 401–421. <https://doi.org/10.5559/di.30.2.11>
- [892] Roška V, Buneta A, Papić M (2021). The effect of the COVID-19 pandemic on the Croatian economy. *Zbornik Veleučilišta u Rijeci* 9(1), 59–78. <https://doi.org/10.31784/zvr.9.1.4>
- [893] Rugole V, Pucarín-Cvetković J, Milošević M (2021). Food supplements in healthcare professionals’ diet during COVID-19 pandemic. *Sestrinski glasnik* 26(2), 82–91. <https://doi.org/10.11608/sgnj.26.2.1>
- [894] Clemente-Suárez VJ, Dalamitros AA, Beltran-Velasco AI, ... Tornero-Aguilera JF (2020). Social and psychophysiological consequences of the COVID-19 pandemic: An extensive literature review. *Frontiers in Psychology* 11, 580225. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2020.580225>
- [895] Angioha PU, Ogar JA, Eteng EE, ... Ibioro FE (2021). Quantitative analysis of the income, mental health effect of SARS COV-2 pandemic in Calabar. *Daengku* 1(1), 29–39. <https://doi.org/10.35877/454ri.daengku386>

- [896] Liu YL, Zhu K, Chen QY, ... Liao HP (2021). Impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on farm households' vulnerability to multidimensional poverty in rural China. *Sustainability* 13(4), 1842. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13041842>
- [897] Guo Y, Shen M, Zhang X, ... Su J (2020). Association of socioeconomic changes due to the COVID-19 pandemic with health outcomes in patients with skin diseases: Cross-sectional survey study. *Journal of Medical Internet Research* 22(9), e22288. <https://doi.org/10.2196/22288>
- [898] Bilić A, Mokrović D (2021). Očuvanje radnih mjesta u vrijeme krize izazvane pandemijom COVID-a 19. *Zbornik radova Pravnog fakulteta u Splitu* 58(2), 525–552. <https://doi.org/10.31141/zrpf.2021.58.140.525>
- [899] Weber A, Schneeweiss Z (2021, November 5). Europe's unemployment rate set to increase next year. *Bloomberg*. <https://www.bloomberg.com/news/articles/2020-11-05/europe-s-unemployment-rate-set-to-increase-next-year-map>
- [900] Matković T, Lucić M (2021). All in the same boat? Differences in employment experience and risks during the first wave of the COVID-19 pandemic in Croatia. *Sociologija i prostor* 59(219), 153–186. <https://doi.org/10.5673/sip.59.0.6>
- [901] Rughoobur-Seetah S (2021). The unprecedented lockdown: The consequences of job loss. *Zagreb International Review of Economics & Business* 24(2), 1–23. <https://doi.org/10.2478/zireb-2021-0008>
- [902] Béland L-P, Brodeur A, Haddad J, Mikola D (2021). Determinants of family stress and domestic violence: Lessons from the COVID-19 outbreak. *Canadian Public Policy* 47(3), 439–459. <https://doi.org/10.3138/cpp.2020-119>
- [903] Nef HM, Elsässer A, Möllmann H, ... Dörr O (2020). Impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on cardiovascular mortality and catheterization activity during the lockdown in central Germany: An observational study. *Clinical Research in Cardiology* 110(2), 292–301. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00392-020-01780-0>
- [904] De Filippo O, D'Ascenzo F, Angelini F, ... De Ferrari GM (2020). Reduced rate of hospital admissions for ACS during Covid-19 outbreak in Northern Italy. *New England Journal of Medicine* 383, 88–89. <https://doi.org/10.1056/nejmc2009166>
- [905] Metzler B, Siostrzonek P, Binder RK, ... Reinstadler SJ (2020). Decline of acute coronary syndrome admissions in Austria since the outbreak of COVID-19: The pandemic response causes cardiac collateral damage. *European Heart Journal* 41(19), 1852–1853. <https://doi.org/10.1093/eurheartj/ehaa314>
- [906] Choudhary R, Gautam D, Mathur R, Choudhary D (2020). Management of cardiovascular emergencies during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Emergency Medicine Journal* 37, 778–780. <https://doi.org/10.1136/emmermed-2020-210231>
- [907] Garzon S, Lemos PA (2021). Postponing cardiac procedures during the pandemic: The balance between elective and selective! *Catheterization and Cardiovascular Interventions* 97(5), 938–939. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ccd.29670>

- [908] Christensen DM, Butt JH, Fosbøl E, ... Phelps M (2021). Nationwide cardiovascular disease admission rates during a second COVID-19 lockdown. *American Heart Journal* 241, 35–37. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ahj.2021.07.001>
- [909] Cho D-H (2021). The impact of COVID-19 on heart failure: What happened to the patients with heart failure who could not visit our clinic amid the COVID-19 pandemic? *International Journal of Heart Failure* 3(2), 125. <https://doi.org/10.36628/ijhf.2021.0014>
- [910] Burgos LM, Benzadón M, Candiello A, ... Diez M (2020). Telehealth in heart failure care during COVID-19 pandemic lockdown in Argentina. *International Journal of Heart Failure* 2(4), 247. <https://doi.org/10.36628/ijhf.2020.0025>
- [911] Sud A, Jones ME, Broggio J, ... Turnbull C (2020). Collateral damage: The impact on outcomes from cancer surgery of the COVID-19 pandemic. *Annals of Oncology* 31(8), 1065–1074. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.annonc.2020.05.009>
- [912] Franjić D, Marjanović I (2020). Prevencija i rano otkrivanje karcinoma debelog crijeva u vrijeme pandemije COVID-19. *Zdravstveni glasnik* 6(2), 96–104. <https://doi.org/10.47960/2303-8616.2020.12.96>
- [913] Shubber N, Sheppard J, Alradhawi M, Ali Y (2020). The impacts of the novel SARS-CoV-2 outbreak on surgical oncology: A letter to the editor on “The socio-economic implications of the coronavirus and COVID-19 pandemic: A review”. *International Journal of Surgery* 79, 109–110. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijso.2020.05.032>
- [914] Matošević P, Biošić V, Brkić L, ... Kinda E (2021). COVID-19 and colorectal cancer – Signs of a toxic relationship and how to break the cycle: A single institution, tertiary centre experience. *Libri Oncologici* 49(1), 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.20471/lo.2021.49.01.01>
- [915] Vrdoljak Mozetič D, Savić Vuković A, Avirović M, ... Jonjić N (2021). Utjecaj pandemije COVID-19 na rad patologije i citologije u Kliničkom bolničkom centru Rijeka. *Liječnički vjesnik* 143(3–4), 81–89. <https://doi.org/10.26800/LV-143-3-4-1>
- [916] Donnelly L (2021, December 1). ‘Biggest cancer catastrophe ever’ to hit NHS as up to 740,000 potential cases missed. *The Telegraph*. <https://www.telegraph.co.uk/news/2021/12/01/biggest-cancer-catastrophe-ever-hit-nhs-740000-potential-cases>
- [917] Lamparter U (2020). Corona, Corona, Corona. *Forum der Psychoanalyse* 36, 333–335. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00451-020-00402-9>
- [918] Saini MK, Kumar H, Saini K, ... Kumar H M (2021). Impact of lockdown on medical emergency visits during the COVID-19 pandemic in India. *Postgraduate Medical Journal*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1136/postgradmedj-2021-140850>
- [919] Bartolomeo N, Giotta M, Trerotoli P (2021). In-hospital mortality in non-COVID-19-related diseases before and during the pandemic: A regional retrospective study. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* 18(20), 10886. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph182010886>

- [920] Cannata A, Bromage DI, McDonagh TA (2021). The collateral cardiovascular damage of COVID-19: Only history will reveal the depth of the iceberg. *European Heart Journal* 42(15), 1524–1527. <https://doi.org/10.1093/eurheartj/ehab097>
- [921] Lechner I, Reindl M, Tiller C, ... & Reinstadler SJ (2021). Impact of COVID-19 pandemic restrictions on ST-elevation myocardial infarction: A cardiac magnetic resonance imaging study. *European Heart Journal*, ehab621. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1093/eurheartj/ehab621>
- [922] De Rosa S, Spaccarotella C, Basso C, ... Bolognese L (2020). Reduction of hospitalizations for myocardial infarction in Italy in the COVID-19 era. *European Heart Journal* 41(22), 2083–2088. <https://doi.org/10.1093/eurheartj/ehaa409>
- [923] Wu J, Mamas MA, Mohamed MO, ... Gale CP (2020). Place and causes of acute cardiovascular mortality during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Heart* 107(2), 113–119. <https://doi.org/10.1136/heartjnl-2020-317912>
- [924] Bérard E, Huo Yung Kai S, Coley N, ... Ferrières J (2021). Lockdown-related factors associated with the worsening of cardiovascular risk and anxiety or depression during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Preventive Medicine Reports* 21, 101300. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pmedr.2020.101300>
- [925] Burger AL, Kaufmann CC, Jäger B, ... Huber K (2021). Direct cardiovascular complications and indirect collateral damage during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Wiener klinische Wochenschrift*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00508-021-01956-2>
- [926] Kostev K, Kumar S, Konrad M, Bohlken J (2020). Prescription rates of cardiovascular and diabetes therapies prior to and during the COVID-19 lockdown in Germany. *International Journal of Clinical Pharmacology and Therapeutics* 58(9), 475–481. <https://doi.org/10.5414/cp203849>
- [927] Ta Anyu A, Badawy L, Cannata A, ... McDonagh TA (2021). Long-term outcomes after heart failure hospitalization during the COVID-19 pandemic: A multisite report from heart failure referral centers in London. *ESC Heart Failure*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ehf2.13579>
- [928] Muhammad DG, Abubakar IA (2021). COVID-19 lockdown may increase cardiovascular disease risk factors. *The Egyptian Heart Journal* 73, 2. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s43044-020-00127-4>
- [929] van Bakel BMA, Bakker EA, de Vries F, ... Eijsvogels TMH (2021). Impact of COVID-19 lockdown on physical activity and sedentary behaviour in Dutch cardiovascular disease patients. *Netherlands Heart Journal* 29(5), 273–279. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12471-021-01550-1>
- [930] Freiberg A, Schubert M, Romero Starke K, ... Seidler A (2021). A rapid review on the influence of COVID-19 lockdown and quarantine measures on modifiable cardiovascular risk factors in the general population. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* 18(16), 8567. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph18168567>
- [931] Butt JH, Fosbøl EL, Gerds TA, ... Schou M (2021). All-cause mortality and location of death in patients with established cardiovascular disease before, during, and after the COVID-19 lockdown: A

Danish Nationwide Cohort Study. *European Heart Journal* 42(15), 1516–1523. <https://doi.org/10.1093/eurheartj/ehab028>

[932] Delić-Brkljačić D, Golubić K (2020). Staying focused on cardiovascular patients during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Cardiologia Croatica* 15(11–12), 312–315. <https://doi.org/10.15836/ccar2020.312>

[933] Karatas S, Yesim T, Beysel S (2021). Impact of lockdown COVID-19 on metabolic control in type 2 diabetes mellitus and healthy people. *Primary Care Diabetes* 15(3), 424–427. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pcd.2021.01.003>

[934] Benke C, Autenrieth LK, Asselmann E, Pané-Farré CA (2020). Lockdown, quarantine measures, and social distancing: Associations with depression, anxiety and distress at the beginning of the COVID-19 pandemic among adults from Germany. *Psychiatry Research* 293, 113462. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psychres.2020.113462>

[935] Ciuffreda G, Cabanillas-Barea S, Carrasco-Uribarren A, ... Marcén-Román Y (2021). Factors associated with depression and anxiety in adults ≥ 60 years old during the COVID-19 pandemic: A systematic review. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* 18(22), 11859. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph182211859>

[936] McLafferty M, Brown N, McHugh R, ... Murray EK (2021). Depression, anxiety and suicidal behaviour among college students: Comparisons pre-COVID-19 and during the pandemic. *Psychiatry Research Communications* 1(2), 100012. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psycom.2021.100012>

[937] Moser DA, Glaus J, Frangou S, Schechter DS (2020). Years of life lost due to the psychosocial consequences of COVID-19 mitigation strategies based on Swiss data. *European Psychiatry* 63(1), e58. <https://doi.org/10.1192/j.eurpsy.2020.56>

[938] Grubb R (2021). *Systematic Review on Depression and Anxiety in Young People in High Income Countries during the Coronavirus Pandemic*. M.A. thesis: University of Southern Maine, Gorham, ME, United States. <https://digitalcommons.usm.maine.edu/etd/405>

[939] Arënlju A, Bërxulli D, Perolli-Shehu B, ... Hyseni F (2021). Anxiety and depression among Kosovar university students during the initial phase of outbreak and lockdown of COVID-19 pandemic. *Health Psychology and Behavioral Medicine* 9(1), 239–250. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21642850.2021.1903327>

[940] Fountoulakis KN, Apostolidou MK, Atsiova MB, ... Chrousos GP (2021). Self-reported changes in anxiety, depression and suicidality during the COVID-19 lockdown in Greece. *Journal of Affective Disorders* 279, 624–629. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jad.2020.10.061>

[941] McIntyre RS, Lee Y (2020). Projected increases in suicide in Canada as a consequence of COVID-19. *Psychiatry Research* 290, 113104. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psychres.2020.113104>

[942] Efstathiou V, Stefanou M-I, Siafakas N, ... Rizos E (2021). Suicidality and COVID-19: Suicidal ideation, suicidal behaviors and completed suicides amidst the COVID-19 pandemic (review). *Experimental and Therapeutic Medicine* 23(1), 107. <https://doi.org/10.3892/etm.2021.11030>

- [943] Abbott A (2021). COVID's mental-health toll: How scientists are tracking a surge in depression. *Nature* 590(7845), 194–195. <https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-021-00175-z>
- [944] Rehman U, Shah Nawaz MG, Khan NH, ... Uniyal R (2020). Depression, anxiety and stress among Indians in times of Covid-19 lockdown. *Community Mental Health Journal* 57, 42–48. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10597-020-00664-x>
- [945] Murphy E, Svob C, Van Dijk M, ... Talati A (2021). The effects of the pandemic on mental health in persons with and without a psychiatric history. *Psychological Medicine*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1017/s0033291721004372>
- [946] Korte C, Friedberg RD, Wilgenbusch T, ... Leykin Y (2021). Intolerance of uncertainty and health-related anxiety in youth amid the COVID-19 pandemic: Understanding and weathering the continuing storm. *Journal of Clinical Psychology in Medical Settings*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10880-021-09816-x>
- [947] Naumann E, von den Driesch E, Schumann A, Thönnissen C (2021). Anstieg depressiver Symptome bei Jugendlichen und jungen Erwachsenen während des ersten Lockdowns in Deutschland. *Bundesgesundheitsblatt – Gesundheitsforschung – Gesundheitsschutz*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00103-021-03451-5>
- [948] Shala M, Jetishi Çollaku P, Hoxha F, ... Preteni D (2021). One year after the first cases of COVID-19: Factors influencing the anxiety among Kosovar university students. *Journal of Health and Social Sciences* 6(2), 241–254. <https://doi.org/10.19204/2021/nyrf10>
- [949] Brečić P, Jendričko T, Vidović D, ... Čelić I (2020). Utjecaj pandemije COVID-19 na pacijente s anksioznim i depresivnim poremećajima. *Medicus* 29(2), 237–242. <https://hrcak.srce.hr/244341>
- [950] Adam M, Urbančić-Rak T, Crnić T (2021). Dental students' discomfort and anxiety during the first and the second lockdown due to COVID-19 pandemic at the School of Dental Medicine, University of Zagreb. *Acta stomatologica Croatica* 55(2), 186–197. <https://doi.org/10.15644/asc55/2/8>
- [951] Garg A, Gaur V, Salvi D, Garg A (2021). The impact of the COVID-19 pandemic and lockdown on anxiety in the elderly population: A cross sectional study. *Archives of Psychiatry Research* 57(2), 139–146. <https://doi.org/10.20471/dec.2021.57.02.02>
- [952] Padrón I, Fraga I, Vieitez L, ... Romero E (2021). A study on the psychological wound of COVID-19 in university students. *Frontiers in Psychology* 12, 589927. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.589927>
- [953] Wolf S, Seiffer B, Zeibig J-M, ... Schuch FB (2021). Is physical activity associated with less depression and anxiety during the COVID-19 pandemic? A rapid systematic review. *Sports Medicine* 51, 1771–1783. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40279-021-01468-z>
- [954] Brühlhart M, Klotzbücher V, Lalive R, Reich SK (2021). Mental health concerns during the COVID-19 pandemic as revealed by helpline calls. *Nature*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-021-04099-6>

- [955] Armbruster S, Klotzbücher V (2020). Lost in lockdown? COVID-19, social distancing, and mental health in Germany. *Diskussionsbeiträge 2020*, 04. <http://hdl.handle.net/10419/218885>
- [956] Armbruster S, Klotzbücher V (2020). Lost in lockdown? COVID-19, social distancing, and mental health in Germany [Preprint]. *ResearchGate*. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.17900.39043>
- [957] Brugarolas P (2021). *The Impact of Stay-at-Home Orders on Mental Health: Evidence from Search-Based Symptoms*. M.A. thesis: University of Barcelona, Barcelona, Spain. <http://hdl.handle.net/2445/180475>
- [958] Peitl V, Golubić Zatezalo V, Karlović D (2020). Mental health issues and psychological crisis interventions during the COVID-19 pandemic and earthquakes in Croatia. *Archives of Psychiatry Research* 56(2), 193–198. <https://doi.org/10.20471/dec.2020.56.02.07>
- [959] Torales J, O’Higgins M, Castaldelli-Maia JM, Ventriglio A (2020). The outbreak of COVID-19 coronavirus and its impact on global mental health. *International Journal of Social Psychiatry* 66(4), 317–320. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0020764020915212>
- [960] Alradhawi M, Shubber N, Sheppard J, Ali Y (2020). Effects of the COVID-19 pandemic on mental well-being amongst individuals in society: A letter to the editor on “The socio-economic implications of the coronavirus and COVID-19 pandemic: A review”. *International Journal of Surgery* 78, 147–148. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijso.2020.04.070>
- [961] Morrey LB, Roberts WO, Wichser L (2020). Exercise-related mental health problems and solutions during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Current Sports Medicine Reports* 19(6), 194–195. <https://doi.org/10.1249/jsr.0000000000000725>
- [962] Talapko J, Perić I, Vulić P, ... Škrlec I (2021). Mental health and physical activity in health-related university students during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Healthcare* 9(7), 801. <https://doi.org/10.3390/healthcare9070801>
- [963] Begić D, Lauri Korajlija A, Jokić-Begić N (2020). Psihičko zdravlje liječnika u Hrvatskoj za vrijeme pandemije COVID-19. *Liječnički vjesnik* 142(7–8), 189–198. <https://doi.org/10.26800/LV-142-7-8-32>
- [964] Gül İ, Yeşiltaş A (2021). Mental wellbeing and perception of health in the era of COVID-19 pandemic: A cross-sectional study in the general population. *Perspectives in Psychiatric Care*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ppc.12818>
- [965] Maalouf FT, Mdawar B, Meho LI, Akl EA (2021). Mental health research in response to the COVID-19, Ebola, and H1N1 outbreaks: A comparative bibliometric analysis. *Journal of Psychiatric Research* 132, 198–206. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpsychires.2020.10.018>
- [966] Martínez-Pérez JR, Rivas-Laguna Y, Bermudez-Cordoví LL, ... Rivero-Rodríguez I (2020). Efectos de la COVID-19 sobre estados afectivos emocionales de la población adulta de Puerto Padre. *Revista Electrónica Dr. Zoilo E. Marinello Vidaurreta* 45(6), 1–9. <http://revzoiломarinello.sld.cu/index.php/zmv/article/view/2388>

- [967] Ben Salah A, DeAngelis BN, al'Absi M (2021). Resilience and the role of depressed and anxious mood in the relationship between perceived social isolation and perceived sleep quality during the COVID-19 pandemic. *International Journal of Behavioral Medicine* 28, 277–285. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12529-020-09945-x>
- [968] Sinawi HA, Al Balushi N, Al-Mahrouqi T, ... Al-Alawi M (2020). Predictors of psychological distress among the public in Oman amid coronavirus disease 2019 pandemic: A cross-sectional analytical study. *Psychology, Health & Medicine* 26(1), 131–144. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13548506.2020.1842473>
- [969] Shoaib M, Abdullah F (2021). COVID-19 backlash: Psycho-social impacts of outbreak in Pakistan. *Health Education* 121(3), 265–274. <https://doi.org/10.1108/HE-07-2020-0047>
- [970] Nath A (2020). Impact of COVID-19 pandemic lockdown on mental well-being amongst individuals in society. *International Journal of Scientific Research in Network Security and Communication* 8(4), 6–9. https://www.ijrnsc.org/pub_paper/IJSRNSC/2-IJSRNSC-00567.pdf
- [971] Purdhani S, Saxena T (2020). Spirituality, wellbeing and anxiety: Correlates of corona pandemic. *Expressions India* 6(2), 51–55. <https://expressionsindia.org/images/journals/chapters/2020/dec20/11.pdf>
- [972] Antičević V (2021). Učinci pandemija na mentalno zdravlje. *Društvena istraživanja* 30(2), 423–443. <https://doi.org/10.5559/di.30.2.12>
- [973] Miloš D, Nezirević E (2020). Grad Poreč: Mentalno zdravlje u doba COVID epidemije. *Epoha zdravlja* 13(1), 9–11. <https://hrcak.srce.hr/244149>
- [974] Folayan MO, Ibigbami OI, Oloniniyi IO, ... Aloba O (2021). Associations between psychological wellbeing, depression, general anxiety, perceived social support, tooth brushing frequency and oral ulcers among adults resident in Nigeria during the first wave of the COVID-19 pandemic. *BMC Oral Health* 21, 520. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12903-021-01871-y>
- [975] Sousa AR de, Carvalho ES de S, Santana T da S, ... Pereira Á (2020). Sentimento e emoções de homens no enquadramento da doença Covid-19. *Ciência & saúde coletiva* 25(9), 3481–3491. <https://doi.org/10.1590/1413-81232020259.18772020>
- [976] Gaur V, Jain A, Purohit G, Gaur K (2021). Psychological impact of the corona virus lockdown on the general population: A cross sectional online survey. *Archives of Psychiatry Research* 57(2), 157–166. <https://doi.org/10.20471/dec.2021.57.02.04>
- [977] Drmić S, Murin L (2021). Sindrom sagorijevanja među zdravstvenim radnicima u pandemiji bolesti COVID-19. *Hrvatski časopis zdravstvenih znanosti* 1(1), 25–29. <https://doi.org/10.48188/hczz.1.1.6>
- [978] Blaži A, Uljančić S (2021). Utjecaj Covid-19 pandemije na mentalno zdravlje primalja. *Primaljski vjesnik* 31, 12–28. <https://hrcak.srce.hr/265549>
- [979] Basanić Čuš N (2020). Grad Poreč: Zaštita mentalnog zdravlja Porečana u vrijeme COVID-19 krize. *Epoha zdravlja* 13(1), 12–14. <https://hrcak.srce.hr/244150>

- [980] Mučnjak D, Novosel V (2021). Dva volana – Mentalno zdravlje djelatnika i upravljanje u knjižnicama pogođenim pandemijom i potresom: Studija slučaja jedne visokoškolske knjižnice. *Vjesnik bibliotekara Hrvatske* 64(1), 81–94. <https://doi.org/10.30754/vbh.64.1.854>
- [981] Đogaš Z, Lušić Kalcina L, Pavlinac Dodig I, ... Pecotić R (2020). The effect of COVID-19 lockdown on lifestyle and mood in Croatian general population: A cross-sectional study. *Croatian Medical Journal* 61(4), 309–318. <https://doi.org/10.3325/cmj.2020.61.309>
- [982] La Rosa VL, Gori A, Faraci P, ... Craparo G (2021). Traumatic distress, alexithymia, dissociation, and risk of addiction during the first wave of COVID-19 in Italy: Results from a cross-sectional online survey on a non-clinical adult sample. *International Journal of Mental Health and Addiction*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11469-021-00569-0>
- [983] Jaguga F, Kwobah E, Mwangi A, ... Atwoli L (2021). Harmful alcohol use among healthcare workers at the beginning of the COVID-19 pandemic in Kenya [Preprint]. *Research Square*. <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-403929/v1>
- [984] Koopmann A, Georgiadou E, Kiefer F, Hillemacher T (2020). Did the general population in Germany drink more alcohol during the COVID-19 pandemic lockdown? *Alcohol and Alcoholism* 55(6), 698–699. <https://doi.org/10.1093/alcalc/agaa058>
- [985] Sorić I, Penezić Z (2021). Osobni i kontekstualni čimbenici emocionalne iscrpljenosti školskih ravnatelja tijekom pandemije COVID-19. *Društvena istraživanja* 30(2), 203–225. <https://doi.org/10.5559/di.30.2.02>
- [986] Živčić-Bećirević I, Smojver-Ažić S, Martinac Dorčić T, Birovljević G (2021). Izvori stresa, depresivnost i akademsko funkcioniranje studenata za vrijeme pandemije COVID-19. *Društvena istraživanja* 30(2), 291–312. <https://doi.org/10.5559/di.30.2.06>
- [987] Uzelac E, Čepulić D-B, Pavić P (2021). We are All in This Together: Usporedba iskustava pandemije koronavirusa u Hrvatskoj i ostalim europskim zemljama. *Društvena istraživanja* 30(2), 333–358. <https://doi.org/10.5559/di.30.2.08>
- [988] Vulić-Prtorić A, Bodrožić Selak M, Sturnela P (2020). The psychological distress in students during the COVID-19 crisis: An 8-wave longitudinal study [Preprint]. *PsyArXiv*. <https://doi.org/10.31234/osf.io/vtfxg>
- [989] Vulić-Prtorić A (2021). PSIHOVID-20: Uvid u psihologijska istraživanja u vrijeme pandemije COVID-19. *Društvena istraživanja* 30(2), 447–451. <https://doi.org/10.5559/di.30.2.13>
- [990] Smoljo-Dobrovoljski S (2021). Skrb za svoju ranjivost i otpornost u vrijeme pandemije COVID-a 19. *Crkva u svijetu* 56(3), 455–471. <https://doi.org/10.34075/cs.56.3.6>
- [991] Petrov E, Markulin Š (2021). Transcendentalno iskustvo skrbi za samoga sebe u kontekstu pandemije COVID-a 19. *Crkva u svijetu* 56(3), 507–526. <https://doi.org/10.34075/cs.56.3.9>
- [992] Babić D, Babić M (2020). Kako se sačuvati od stresa za vrijeme pandemije koronom. *Zdravstveni glasnik* 6(1), 25–32. <https://doi.org/10.47960/2303-8616.2020.11.25>

- [993] Ivanović M, Šimić N (2021). Psihopatološki distres kod muškaraca i žena mlađe odrasle dobi tijekom COVID-19 pandemije. *Medica Jadertina* 51(3), 253–259. <https://hrcak.srce.hr/263202>
- [994] Nakano T, Chiang K-C, Chen C-C, ... Goto S (2021). Sunlight exposure and phototherapy: Perspectives for healthy aging in an era of COVID-19. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* 18(20), 10950. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph182010950>
- [995] Chee SY (2020). COVID-19 pandemic: The lived experiences of older adults in aged care homes. *Millennial Asia* 11(3), 299–317. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0976399620958326>
- [996] Nyenhuis SM, Greiwe J, Zeiger JS, Nanda A, Cooke A (2020). Exercise and fitness in the age of social distancing during the COVID-19 pandemic. *The Journal of Allergy and Clinical Immunology: In Practice* 8(7), 2152–2155. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaip.2020.04.039>
- [997] Hargreaves EA, Lee C, Jenkins M, ... Houge Mackenzie S (2021). Changes in physical activity pre-, during and post-lockdown COVID-19 restrictions in New Zealand and the explanatory role of daily hassles. *Frontiers in Psychology* 12, 642954. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.642954>
- [998] Mutz M, Gerke M (2020). Sport and exercise in times of self-quarantine: How Germans changed their behaviour at the beginning of the Covid-19 pandemic. *International Review for the Sociology of Sport* 56(3), 305–316. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1012690220934335>
- [999] Kaur H, Singh T, Arya YK, Mittal S (2020). Physical fitness and exercise during the COVID-19 pandemic: A qualitative enquiry. *Frontiers in Psychology* 11, 590172. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2020.590172>
- [1000] Hofman A, Limpens MAM, de Crom TOE, ... Voortman T (2021). Trajectories and determinants of physical activity during COVID-19 pandemic: A population-based study of middle-aged and elderly individuals in the Netherlands. *Nutrients* 13(11), 3832. <https://doi.org/10.3390/nu13113832>
- [1001] Huršidić Radulović A, Žaja R, Milošević M, ... Božić T (2021). Work from home and musculoskeletal pain in telecommunications workers during COVID-19 pandemic: A pilot study. *Arhiv za higijenu rada i toksikologiju* 72(3), 232–239. <https://doi.org/10.2478/aiht-2021-72-3559>
- [1002] Khan MA, Moverley Smith JE (2020). “Covibesity”, a new pandemic. *Obesity Medicine* 19, 100282. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.obmed.2020.100282>
- [1003] O’Regan D, Jackson ML, Young AH, Rosenzweig I (2021). Understanding the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic, lockdowns and social isolation on sleep quality. *Nature and Science of Sleep* 113, 2053–2064. <https://doi.org/10.2147/nss.s266240>
- [1004] Docherty KF, Butt JH, de Boer RA, ... Jhund PS (2020). Excess deaths during the Covid-19 pandemic: An international comparison [Preprint]. *medRxiv*. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2020.04.21.20073114>
- [1005] Brown E, Ba Tran A, Reinhard B, Ulmanu M (2020, April 27). U.S. deaths soared in early weeks of pandemic, far exceeding number attributed to covid-19. *The Washington Post*. <https://www.washingtonpost.com/investigations/2020/04/27/covid-19-death-toll-undercounted>

- [1006] The Lancet (2020). India under COVID-19 lockdown. *The Lancet* 395(10233), P1315. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736\(20\)30938-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736(20)30938-7)
- [1007] Bignardi G, Dalmaijer ES, Anwyll-Irvine AL, Astle DE (2021). Longitudinal increases in childhood depression symptoms during the COVID-19 lockdown. *Archives of Disease in Childhood* 106, 791–797. <https://doi.org/10.1136/archdischild-2020-320372>
- [1008] Panchal U, Salazar de Pablo G, Franco M, ... Fusar-Poli P (2021). The impact of COVID-19 lockdown on child and adolescent mental health: Systematic review. *European Child & Adolescent Psychiatry*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00787-021-01856-w>
- [1009] Chadi N, Spinoso-Di Piano C, Osmanlliu E, ... Drouin O (2021). Mental health-related emergency department visits in adolescents before and during the COVID-19 pandemic: A multicentric retrospective study. *Journal of Adolescent Health* 69(5), 847–850. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jadohealth.2021.07.036>
- [1010] Ravens-Sieberer U, Kaman A, Otto C, ... Hurrelmann K (2021). Seelische Gesundheit und psychische Belastungen von Kindern und Jugendlichen in der ersten Welle der COVID-19-Pandemie: Ergebnisse der COPSY-Studie. *Bundesgesundheitsblatt – Gesundheitsforschung – Gesundheitsschutz*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00103-021-03291-3>
- [1011] McArthur BA, Racine N, McDonald S, ... Madigan S (2021). Child and family factors associated with child mental health and well-being during COVID-19. *European Child & Adolescent Psychiatry*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00787-021-01849-9>
- [1012] Nijman RG (2021). The impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on child health. *Journal of Laboratory Medicine* 45(6), 249–258. <https://doi.org/10.1515/labmed-2021-0128>
- [1013] Ravens-Sieberer U, Kaman A, Erhart M, ... Otto C (2021). Quality of life and mental health in children and adolescents during the first year of the COVID-19 pandemic in Germany: Results of a two-wave nationally representative study [Preprint]. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3798710>
- [1014] Yang X, Harrison P, Huang J, ... Zahn R (2021). The impact of COVID-19-related lockdown on adolescent mental health in China: A prospective study [Preprint]. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3792956>
- [1015] Hafstad GS, Sætren SS, Wentzel-Larsen T, Augusti E-M (2021). Adolescents' symptoms of anxiety and depression before and during the Covid-19 outbreak: A prospective population-based study of teenagers in Norway. *The Lancet Regional Health: Europe* 5, 100093. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lanepe.2021.100093>
- [1016] Hafstad GS, Augusti E-M (2021). A lost generation? COVID-19 and adolescent mental health. *The Lancet Psychiatry* 8(8), 640–641. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s2215-0366\(21\)00179-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/s2215-0366(21)00179-6)
- [1017] Zolopa C, Burack JA, O'Connor R, ... Wendt DC (2021). Changes in youth mental health, psychological wellbeing, and substance use during the COVID-19 pandemic: A rapid review [Preprint]. *PsyArXiv*. <https://doi.org/10.31234/osf.io/yuthm>

- [1018] Wu Z, Liu Z, Zou Z, ... Long Y (2021). Changes of psychotic-like experiences and their association with anxiety/depression among young adolescents before COVID-19 and after the lockdown in China. *Schizophrenia Research* 237, 40–46. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.schres.2021.08.020>
- [1019] Dabravolskaj J, Khan MKA, Veugelers PJ, Maximova K (2021). Mental health and wellbeing of 9–12-year-old children in northern Canada before the COVID-19 pandemic and after the first lockdown. *International Journal of Public Health* 66, 1604219. <https://doi.org/10.3389/ijph.2021.1604219>
- [1020] Önal G, Güney G, Huri M (2021). Quality of life and occupational performance of children with cancer in the era of the COVID-19 pandemic in terms of rehabilitation. *Quality of Life Research* 30, 2783–2794. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11136-021-02857-7>
- [1021] Huang HC-H, Ougrin D (2021). Impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on child and adolescent mental health services. *BJPsych Open* 7(5), E145. <https://doi.org/10.1192/bjo.2021.976>
- [1022] Gul MK, Demirci E (2021). Psychiatric disorders and symptoms in children and adolescents during the COVID-19 pandemic: A review. *EJMO* 5(1), 20–36. <https://doi.org/10.14744/ejmo.2021.14105>
- [1023] Loades ME, Chatburn E, Higson-Sweeney N, ... Crawley E (2020). Rapid systematic review: The impact of social isolation and loneliness on the mental health of children and adolescents in the context of COVID-19. *Journal of the American Academy of Child & Adolescent Psychiatry* 59(11), P1218–P1239.e3. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaac.2020.05.009>
- [1024] Pietrobelli A, Pecoraro L, Ferruzzi A, ... Heymsfield SB (2020). Effects of COVID-19 lockdown on lifestyle behaviors in children with obesity living in Verona, Italy: A longitudinal study. *Obesity* 28(8), 1382–1385. <https://doi.org/10.1002/oby.22861>
- [1025] Ravens-Sieberer U, Kaman A, Erhart M, ... Otto C (2021). Impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on quality of life and mental health in children and adolescents in Germany. *European Child & Adolescent Psychiatry*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00787-021-01726-5>
- [1026] Zhou S-J, Zhang L-G, Wang L-L, ... Chen J-X (2020). Prevalence and socio-demographic correlates of psychological health problems in Chinese adolescents during the outbreak of COVID-19. *European Child & Adolescent Psychiatry* 29(6), 749–758. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00787-020-01541-4>
- [1027] Xie X, Xue Q, Zhou Y, ... Song R (2020). Mental health status among children in home confinement during the coronavirus disease 2019 outbreak in Hubei Province, China. *JAMA Pediatrics* 174(9), 898. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jamapediatrics.2020.1619>
- [1028] Jiao WY, Wang LN, Liu J, ... Somekh E (2020). Behavioral and emotional disorders in children during the COVID-19 epidemic. *The Journal of Pediatrics* 221, P264–266.e1. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpeds.2020.03.013>
- [1029] Singh S, Roy D, Sinha K, ... Joshi G (2020). Impact of COVID-19 and lockdown on mental health of children and adolescents: A narrative review with recommendations. *Psychiatry Research* 293, 113429. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psychres.2020.113429>

- [1030] Ćurković N, Lukačin L, Katavić I (2021). Životne navike djece i mladih tijekom socijalne izolacije uzrokovane pandemijom bolesti COVID-19. *Društvena istraživanja* 30(2), 271–290. <https://doi.org/10.5559/di.30.2.05>
- [1031] Bistrić M (2020). Načini provođenja slobodnoga vremena djece predškolske dobi prije i tijekom prvoga vala bolesti COVID-19 te procjena roditelja o utjecaju novonastale situacije na dijete. *Magistra Iadertina* 15(2), 111–134. <https://doi.org/10.15291/magistra.3380>
- [1032] Tonković A, Pongračić L, Vrsalović P (2020). Djelovanje pandemije Covid-19 na obrazovanje diljem svijeta. *Foo2rama* 4(4), 121–134. <https://hrcak.srce.hr/251672>
- [1033] Šunda M, Babić V, Andrijašević M (2020). Nastava tjelesne i zdravstvene kulture na daljinu učenika Gimnazije Antuna Gustava Matoša tijekom COVID-19 pandemije. *Napredak* 161(3–4), 315–323. <https://hrcak.srce.hr/249641>
- [1034] Bolčević Novak V, Dvekar-Bešenić G (2021). Mentalno zdravlje učenika. *Varaždinski učitelj* 4(6), 533–543. <https://hrcak.srce.hr/255578>
- [1035] Kosi U (2021). Kako potaknuti kretanje učenika i njihovih roditelja. *Varaždinski učitelj* 4(7), 678–687. <https://hrcak.srce.hr/264516>
- [1036] Višnjić-Jevtić A, Visković I (2021). Roditeljstvo u vrijeme pandemije COVID-19. *Metodički ogledi* 28(1), 11–38. <https://doi.org/10.21464/mo.28.1.4>
- [1037] Hao Y, Zhang S, Conner A, Lee NY (2021). The evolution of telepractice use during the COVID-19 pandemic: Perspectives of pediatric speech-language pathologists. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* 18(22), 12197. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph182212197>
- [1038] The Lancet (2020). Generation coronavirus? *The Lancet* 395(10242), P1949. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736\(20\)31445-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736(20)31445-8)
- [1039] Starić R (2021). *Organizacija prijelaza iz obitelji u dječji vrtić tijekom pandemije Koronavirusa: Perspektiva djece, roditelja i odgajatelja*. M.A. thesis: University of Rijeka, Rijeka, Croatia. <https://urn.nsk.hr/urn:nbn:hr:189:276119>
- [1040] Román López I, Zayas Fajardo ML, Román López MY, ... Fonseca Rivero Y (2021). Alteraciones psicológicas en niños y adolescentes durante confinamiento social por COVID-19: Policlínico René Vallejo Ortiz. *Multimed* 25(2), e2095. <http://www.revmultimed.sld.cu/index.php/mtm/article/view/2095>
- [1041] Sugand K, Park C, Morgan C, ... Harrison A (2020). Impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on paediatric orthopaedic trauma workload in central London: A multi-centre longitudinal observational study over the “golden weeks.” *Acta Orthopaedica* 91(6), 633–638. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17453674.2020.1807092>
- [1042] Bailey LC, Razzaghi H, Burrows EK, ... Forrest CB (2021). Assessment of 135 794 pediatric patients tested for severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 across the United States. *JAMA Pediatrics* 175(2), 176. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jamapediatrics.2020.5052>

- [1043] Tönshoff B, Müller B, Elling R, ... Kräusslich H-G (2021). Prevalence of SARS-CoV-2 infection in children and their parents in Southwest Germany. *JAMA Pediatrics* 175(6), 586. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jamapediatrics.2021.0001>
- [1044] Bhopal SS, Bagaria J, Olabi B, Bhopal R (2021). Children and young people remain at low risk of COVID-19 mortality. *The Lancet Child & Adolescent Health* 5(5), e12–e13. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s2352-4642\(21\)00066-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/s2352-4642(21)00066-3)
- [1045] Stringhini S, Wisniak A, Piumatti G, ... Guessous I (2020). Seroprevalence of anti-SARS-CoV-2 IgG antibodies in Geneva, Switzerland (SEROCoV-POP): A population-based study. *The Lancet* 396(10247), 313–319. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736\(20\)31304-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736(20)31304-0)
- [1046] Pollán M, Pérez-Gómez B, Pastor-Barriuso R, ... Vázquez de la Villa A (2020). Prevalence of SARS-CoV-2 in Spain (ENE-COVID): A nationwide, population-based seroepidemiological study. *The Lancet* 396(10250), 535–544. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736\(20\)31483-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736(20)31483-5)
- [1047] Sorg A-L, Hufnagel M, Doenhardt M, ... Armann JP (2021). Risk of hospitalization, severe disease, and mortality due to COVID-19 and PIMS-TS in children with SARS-CoV-2 infection in Germany [Preprint]. *medRxiv*. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2021.11.30.21267048>
- [1048] Ludvigsson JF, Engerström L, Nordenhäll C, Larsson E (2021). Open schools, Covid-19, and child and teacher morbidity in Sweden. *New England Journal of Medicine* 384(7), 669–671. <https://doi.org/10.1056/nejmc2026670>
- [1049] Lavezzo E, Franchin E, Ciavarella C, ... Crisanti A (2020). Suppression of a SARS-CoV-2 outbreak in the Italian municipality of Vo'. *Nature* 584(7821), 425–429. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-020-2488-1>
- [1050] Lavezzo E, Franchin E, Ciavarella C, ... Crisanti A (2021). Author correction: Suppression of a SARS-CoV-2 outbreak in the Italian municipality of Vo'. *Nature* 590(7844), E11. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-020-2956-7>
- [1051] Kheiroddin P, Schöberl P, Althammer M, ... Kabesch M (2021). Results of WICOVIR gargle pool PCR testing in German schools based on the first 100,000 tests. *Frontiers in Pediatrics* 9, 721518. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fped.2021.721518>
- [1052] Kang S-J, Jung SI (2020). Age-related morbidity and mortality among patients with COVID-19. *Infection & Chemotherapy* 52(2), 154. <https://doi.org/10.3947/ic.2020.52.2.154>
- [1053] Kim L, Whitaker M, O'Halloran A, ... Garg S (2020). Hospitalization rates and characteristics of children aged <18 years hospitalized with laboratory-confirmed COVID-19: COVID-NET, 14 States, March 1–July 25, 2020. *Morbidity and Mortality Weekly Report* 69(32), 1081–1088. <https://doi.org/10.15585/mmwr.mm6932e3>
- [1054] Hoch M, Vogel S, Kolberg L, ... von Both U (2021). Weekly SARS-CoV-2 sentinel surveillance in primary schools, kindergartens, and nurseries, Germany, June–November 2020. *Emerging Infectious Diseases* 27(8), 2192–2196. <https://doi.org/10.3201/eid2708.204859>

- [1055] Gudbjartsson DF, Helgason A, Jonsson H, ... Stefansson K (2020). Spread of SARS-CoV-2 in the Icelandic population. *New England Journal of Medicine* 382(24), 2302–2315. <https://doi.org/10.1056/nejmoa2006100>
- [1056] Gold JAW, Rossen LM, Ahmad FB, ... Jackson BR (2020). Race, ethnicity, and age trends in persons who died from COVID-19: United States, May–August 2020. *Morbidity and Mortality Weekly Report* 69(42), 1517–1521. <https://doi.org/10.15585/mmwr.mm6942e1>
- [1057] Götzinger F, Santiago-García B, Noguera-Julían A, ... Riordan A (2020). COVID-19 in children and adolescents in Europe: A multinational, multicentre cohort study. *The Lancet Child & Adolescent Health* 4(9), 653–661. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s2352-4642\(20\)30177-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/s2352-4642(20)30177-2)
- [1058] Blekić M, Miškić B, Kljaić Bukvić B (2020). COVID-19 i djeca. *Liječnički vjesnik* 142(3–4), 64–74. <https://doi.org/10.26800/LV-142-3-4-12>
- [1059] Stemberger Marić L, Roglić S (2020). Infekcija SARS-CoV-2 (COVID-19) u djece. *Paediatrica Croatica* 64(2), 94–99. <https://doi.org/10.13112/PC.2020.13>
- [1060] Dodig S, Čepelak I, Pavić I (2020). Dob i infekcija virusom SARS-CoV-2. *Acta medica Croatica* 74(2), 135–143. <https://hrcak.srce.hr/244545>
- [1061] Lenicek Krleza J, Lukic-Grlic A, Vilibic-Cavlek T, ... Zrinski Topic R (2021). Seroprevalence of SARS-CoV-2 infection among children in Children’s Hospital Zagreb during the initial and second wave of COVID-19 pandemic in Croatia. *Biochemia medica* 31(2), 283–294. <https://doi.org/10.11613/bm.2021.020706>
- [1062] Paduano S, Facchini MC, Greco A, ... Filippini T (2021). Characteristics and risk factors of isolated and quarantined children and adolescents during the first wave of SARS-CoV-2 pandemic: A cross-sectional study in Modena, Northern Italy: SARS-CoV-2 in Modena children. *Acta Biomedica* 92(S6), e2021449. <https://doi.org/10.23750/abm.v92iS6.12225>
- [1063] Nikolopoulou GB, Maltezou HC (2021). COVID-19 in children: Where do we stand? *Archives of Medical Research*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.arcmed.2021.07.002>
- [1064] Thacker D (2021). Low burden of COVID-19 disease in children with cancer and hematologic illnesses. *Cancer Research, Statistics and Treatment* 4(3), 590–591. https://doi.org/10.4103/crst.crst_174_21
- [1065] O’Leary ST (2021). To spread or not to spread SARS-CoV-2: Is that the question? *JAMA Pediatrics* 175(6), 559. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jamapediatrics.2021.0006>
- [1066] Busa F, Bardanzellu F, Pintus MC, ... Marcialis MA (2021). COVID-19 and school – To open or not to open, that is the question: The first review on current knowledge. *Pediatric Reports* 13(2), 257–278. <https://doi.org/10.3390/pediatric13020035>
- [1067] Jung J, Hong MJ, Kim EO, ... Kim S-H (2020). Investigation of a nosocomial outbreak of coronavirus disease 2019 in a paediatric ward in South Korea: Successful control by early detection and

extensive contact tracing with testing. *Clinical Microbiology and Infection* 26(11), 1574–1575. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cmi.2020.06.021>

[1068] Zhao Y, Guo Y, Xiao Y, ... Wu J-L (2020). The effects of online homeschooling on children, parents, and teachers of grades 1–9 during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Medical Science Monitor* 26, e925591. <https://doi.org/10.12659/msm.925591>

[1069] Ozturk Eyimaya A, Yalçın Irmak A (2021). Relationship between parenting practices and children's screen time during the COVID-19 pandemic in Turkey. *Journal of Pediatric Nursing* 56, 24–29. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pedn.2020.10.002>

[1070] Pombo A, Luz C, Rodrigues LP, Cordovil R (2020). COVID-19 confinement in Portugal: Effects on the household routines of children under 13 [Preprint]. *Research Square*. <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-45764/v1>

[1071] Wang J, Li Y, Musch DC, ... Qian X (2021). Progression of myopia in school-aged children after COVID-19 home confinement. *JAMA Ophthalmology* 139(3), 293. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jamaophthalmol.2020.6239>

[1072] van der Velde M, Sense F, Spijkers R, ... van Rijn H (2021) Lockdown learning: Changes in online foreign-language study activity and performance of Dutch secondary school students during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Frontiers in Education* 6, 712987. <https://doi.org/10.3389/educ.2021.712987>

[1073] Kotrla Topić M, Varga V, Jelovčić S (2021). Digital technology use during the COVID-19 pandemic and its relations to sleep quality and life satisfaction in children and parents. *Društvena istraživanja* 30(2), 249–269. <https://doi.org/10.5559/di.30.2.04>

[1074] Ristić Dedić Z, Jokić B (2021). Croatian pupils' perspectives on remote teaching and learning during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Društvena istraživanja* 30(2), 227–247. <https://doi.org/10.5559/di.30.2.03>

[1075] Wößmann L (2020). Folgekosten ausbleibenden Lernens: Was wir über die Corona-bedingten Schulschließungen aus der Forschung lernen können. *ifo Schnelldienst* 73(6), 38–44. <http://hdl.handle.net/10419/225139>

[1076] Couzin-Frankel J, Vogel G, Weiland M (2020). Not open and shut. *Science* 369(6501), 241–245. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.369.6501.241>

[1077] Yamamura E, Tsustsui Y (2021). School closures and mental health during the COVID-19 pandemic in Japan. *Journal of Population Economics* 34, 1261–1298. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00148-021-00844-3>

[1078] Ivanković I, Igić I (2021). Stavovi roditelja osnovnoškolskih učenika grada Zagreba o uporabi IKT u nastavi na daljinu tijekom pandemije bolesti COVID-19. *Metodički ogledi* 28(1), 39–62. <https://doi.org/10.21464/mo.28.1.5>

[1079] Rogošić S, Baranović B, Šabić J (2021). Primjena IKT-a u procesu učenja, poučavanja i vrednovanja u srednjim strukovnim školama. *Metodički ogledi* 28(1), 63–88. <https://doi.org/10.21464/mo.28.1.6>

- [1080] Bušljeta Kadrum R, Jurić Vukelić D (2021). The challenges and issues on the University of Zagreb during COVID-19 crisis. *Interdisciplinary Description of Complex Systems* 19(3), 357–365. <https://doi.org/10.7906/indec.19.3.1>
- [1081] Jurkić Sviben T, Jambrošić NS (2021). (Ne)Pjevanje za vrijeme pandemije bolesti Covid-19: Mišljenja i emocionalni doživljaj učenika od 5. do 8. razreda osnovnih škola u Republici Hrvatskoj. *Školski vjesnik* 70(2), 245–268. <https://doi.org/10.38003/sv.70.2.11>
- [1082] Jurkić Sviben T, Jambrošić NS (2021). (Non)Singing during the Covid-19 pandemic: Opinions and emotional experience of students from 5th to 8th grade of primary schools in the Republic of Croatia. *Školski vjesnik* 70(2), 269–292. <https://doi.org/10.38003/sv.70.2.12>
- [1083] Badovinac A, Par M, Plančak L, ... Musić L (2021). The impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on dental education: An online survey of students' perceptions and attitudes. *Dentistry Journal* 9(10), 116. <https://doi.org/10.3390/dj9100116>
- [1084] Takaku R, Yokoyama I (2020). What school closure left in its wake: Contrasting evidence between parents and children from the first COVID-19 outbreak [Preprint]. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3693484>
- [1085] Azevedo JP, Hasan A, Goldemberg D, Iqbal SA (2021). Simulating the potential impacts of COVID-19 school closures on schooling and learning outcomes: A set of global estimates. *The World Bank Research Observer* 36(1), 1–40. <https://doi.org/10.1093/wbro/lkab003>
- [1086] Kisielinski K, Giboni P, Prescher A, ... Hirsch O (2021). Is a mask that covers the mouth and nose free from undesirable side effects in everyday use and free of potential hazards? *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* 18(8), 4344. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph18084344>
- [1087] Nesešek Adam V, Mesarić J (2020). COVID-19 i maske: Što znamo do sada? *Zbornik sveučilišta Libertas* 5(5), 191–198. <https://doi.org/10.46672/zsl.5.5.13>
- [1088] Leung NHL, Chu DKW, Shiu EYC, ... Cowling BJ (2020). Respiratory virus shedding in exhaled breath and efficacy of face masks. *Nature Medicine* 26, 676–680. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41591-020-0843-2>
- [1089] Esposito S, Principi N, Leung CC, Migliori GB (2020). Universal use of face masks for success against COVID-19: Evidence and implications for prevention policies. *European Respiratory Journal* 55, 2001260. <https://doi.org/10.1183/13993003.01260-2020>
- [1090] Lyu W, Wehby GL (2020). Community use of face masks and COVID-19: Evidence from a natural experiment of state mandates in the US. *Health Affairs* 39(8), 1419–1425. <https://doi.org/10.1377/hlthaff.2020.00818>
- [1091] MacIntyre CR, Wang Q (2020). Physical distancing, face masks, and eye protection for prevention of COVID-19. *The Lancet* 385(10242), 1950–1951. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736\(20\)31183-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736(20)31183-1)

- [1092] Jefferson T, Del Mar CB, Dooley L, ... Conly JM (2020). Physical interventions to interrupt or reduce the spread of respiratory viruses. *Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews* 2020(11), CD006207. <https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.cd006207.pub5>
- [1093] Jefferson T, Jones M, Al-Ansary L, ... van Driel M (2020). Physical interventions to interrupt or reduce the spread of respiratory viruses. Part 1 – Face masks, eye protection and person distancing: Systematic review and meta-analysis [Preprint]. *medRxiv*. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2020.03.30.20047217>
- [1094] Chu DK, Akl EA, Duda S, ... Schünemann HJ (2020). Physical distancing, face masks, and eye protection to prevent person-to-person transmission of SARS-CoV-2 and COVID-19: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *The Lancet* 395(10242), 1973–1987. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736\(20\)31142-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736(20)31142-9)
- [1095] Matuschek C, Moll F, Fangerau H, ... Haussmann J (2020). Face masks: Benefits and risks during the COVID-19 crisis. *European Journal of Medical Research* 25, 32. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40001-020-00430-5>
- [1096] Vainshelboim B (2021). Facemasks in the COVID-19 era: A health hypothesis [Retracted]. *Medical Hypotheses* 146, 110411. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mehy.2020.110411>
- [1097] Vainshelboim B (2021). Retraction notice to “Facemasks in the COVID-19 era: A health hypothesis” [Medical Hypotheses 146 (2021) 5]. *Medical Hypotheses* 152, 110601. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mehy.2021.110601>
- [1098] Guerra DD, Guerra DJ (2021). Mask mandate and use efficacy for COVID-19 containment in US States [Preprint]. *medRxiv*. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2021.05.18.21257385>
- [1099] Mikovits JA, Heckenlively K (2020). *The Case Against Masks: Ten Reasons Why Mask Use Should be Limited*. New York, NY: Skyhorse Publishing. <https://www.skyhorsepublishing.com/9781510764279/the-case-against-masks>
- [1100] Boretti, A. (2021). Efficacy of generalized face masking mandates. *Health Services Research and Managerial Epidemiology* 8, 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.1177/23333928211058023>
- [1101] MacIntyre CR, Chughtai AA, Seale H, ... Quanyi W (2020). Human coronavirus data from four clinical trials of masks and respirators. *International Journal of Infectious Diseases* 96, 631–633. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijid.2020.05.092>
- [1102] De Giorgi G, Speziali MM, Michalik F (2021). The impact of face-masks on total mortality heterogenous effects by gender and age [Preprint]. *medRxiv*. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2021.06.08.21258545>
- [1103] Rancourt DG (2021, September 20). Do face masks reduce COVID-19 spread in Bangladesh? Are the Abaluck et al. results reliable? *Denis Rancourt*. <https://denisrancourt.ca/entries.php?id=106>
- [1104] Desai AN, Mehrotra P (2020). Medical masks. *JAMA* 323(15), 1517–1518. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.2020.2331>

- [1105] Suess T, Remschmidt C, Schink SB, ... Buchholz U (2012). The role of facemasks and hand hygiene in the prevention of influenza transmission in households: Results from a cluster randomised trial; Berlin, Germany, 2009–2011. *BMC Infectious Diseases* 12, 26. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2334-12-26>
- [1106] Barasheed O, Almasri N, Badahdah A-M, ... Booy R (2014). Pilot randomised controlled trial to test effectiveness of facemasks in preventing influenza-like illness transmission among Australian Hajj pilgrims in 2011. *Infectious Disorders: Drug Targets* 14(2), 110–116. <https://doi.org/10.2174/1871526514666141021112855>
- [1107] Aiello AE, Murray GF, Perez V, ... Monto AS (2010). Mask use, hand hygiene, and seasonal influenza-like illness among young adults: A randomized intervention trial. *The Journal of Infectious Diseases* 201(4), 491–498. <https://doi.org/10.1086/650396>
- [1108] Aiello AE, Perez V, Coulborn RM, ... Monto AS (2012). Facemasks, hand hygiene, and influenza among young adults: A randomized intervention trial. *PLoS ONE* 7(1), e29744. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0029744>
- [1109] MacIntyre CR, Cauchemez S, Dwyer DE, ... Ferguson N (2009). Face mask use and control of respiratory virus transmission in households. *Emerging Infectious Diseases* 15(2), 233–241. <https://doi.org/10.3201/eid1502.081166>
- [1110] MacIntyre CR, Zhang Y, Chughtai AA, ... Wang Q (2016). Cluster randomised controlled trial to examine medical mask use as source control for people with respiratory illness. *BMJ Open* 6, e012330. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2016-012330>
- [1111] Cowling BJ, Chan K-H, Fang VJ, ... Leung GM (2009). Facemasks and hand hygiene to prevent influenza transmission in households. *Annals of Internal Medicine* 151(7), 437. <https://doi.org/10.7326/0003-4819-151-7-200910060-00142>
- [1112] Cowling BJ, Fung ROP, Cheng CKY, ... Leung GM (2008). Preliminary findings of a randomized trial of non-pharmaceutical interventions to prevent influenza transmission in households. *PLoS ONE* 3(5), e2101. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0002101>
- [1113] Larson EL, Ferng Y-H, Wong-McLoughlin J, ... Morse SS (2010). Impact of non-pharmaceutical interventions on URIs and influenza in crowded, urban households. *Public Health Reports* 125(2), 178–191. <https://doi.org/10.1177/003335491012500206>
- [1114] Simmerman JM, Suntarattiwong P, Levy J, ... Chotipitayasunondh T (2011). Findings from a household randomized controlled trial of hand washing and face masks to reduce influenza transmission in Bangkok, Thailand. *Influenza and Other Respiratory Viruses* 5(4), 256–267. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1750-2659.2011.00205.x>
- [1115] Jacobs JL, Ohde S, Takahashi O, ... Fukui T (2009). Use of surgical face masks to reduce the incidence of the common cold among health care workers in Japan: A randomized controlled trial. *American Journal of Infection Control* 37(5), 417–419. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ajic.2008.11.002>

- [1116] Long Y, Hu T, Liu L, ... Du L (2020). Effectiveness of N95 respirators versus surgical masks against influenza: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Journal of Evidence-Based Medicine* 13(2), 93–101. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jebm.12381>
- [1117] Radonovich LJ Jr, Simberkoff MS, Bessesen MT, ... Perl TM (2019). N95 respirators vs medical masks for preventing influenza among health care personnel. *JAMA* 322(9), 824. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.2019.11645>
- [1118] Cowling BJ, Zhou Y, Ip DKM, ... Aiello AE (2010). Face masks to prevent transmission of influenza virus: A systematic review. *Epidemiology and Infection* 138(4), 449–456. <https://doi.org/10.1017/s0950268809991658>
- [1119] bin-Reza F, Lopez Chavarrias V, Nicoll A, Chamberland ME (2011). The use of masks and respirators to prevent transmission of influenza: A systematic review of the scientific evidence. *Influenza and Other Respiratory Viruses* 6(4), 257–267. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1750-2659.2011.00307.x>
- [1120] Smith JD, MacDougall CC, Johnstone J, ... Garber GE (2016). Effectiveness of N95 respirators versus surgical masks in protecting health care workers from acute respiratory infection: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Canadian Medical Association Journal* 188(8), 567–574. <https://doi.org/10.1503/cmaj.150835>
- [1121] Offeddu V, Yung CF, Low MSF, Tam CC (2017). Effectiveness of masks and respirators against respiratory infections in healthcare workers: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Clinical Infectious Diseases* 65(11), 1934–1942. <https://doi.org/10.1093/cid/cix681>
- [1122] Xiao J, Shiu EYC, Gao H, ... Cowling BJ (2020). Nonpharmaceutical measures for pandemic influenza in nonhealthcare settings: Personal protective and environmental measures. *Emerging Infectious Diseases* 26(5), 967–975. <https://doi.org/10.3201/eid2605.190994>
- [1123] Zemouri C, Awad SF, Volgenant CMC, ... de Soet JJ (2020). Modeling of the transmission of coronaviruses, measles virus, influenza virus, *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*, and *Legionella pneumophila* in dental clinics. *Journal of Dental Research* 99(10), 1192–1198. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0022034520940288>
- [1124] Bartoszko JJ, Farooqi MAM, Alhazzani W, Loeb M (2020). Medical masks vs N95 respirators for preventing COVID-19 in healthcare workers: A systematic review and meta-analysis of randomized trials. *Influenza and Other Respiratory Viruses* 14(4), 365–373. <https://doi.org/10.1111/irv.12745>
- [1125] Chandrasekaran B, Fernandes S (2020). “Exercise with facemask; Are we handling a devil’s sword?”: A physiological hypothesis. *Medical Hypotheses* 144, 110002. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mehy.2020.110002>
- [1126] Spitzer M (2020). Masked education? The benefits and burdens of wearing face masks in schools during the current Corona pandemic. *Trends in Neuroscience and Education* 20, 100138. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tine.2020.100138>

- [1127] Butz U (2005). *Rückatmung von Kohlendioxid bei Verwendung von Operationsmasken als hygienischer Mundschutz an medizinischem Fachpersonal*. Dissertation: Technische Universität München, Munich, Germany. <http://nbn-resolving.de/urn/resolver.pl?urn:nbn:de:bvb:91-diss20050713-2027575920>
- [1128] Smolka L, Borkowski J, Zaton M (2014). The effect of additional dead space on respiratory exchange ratio and carbon dioxide production due to training. *Journal of Sports Science and Medicine* 13(1), 36–43. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/24570603>
- [1129] Roberge RJ, Kim J-H, Benson SM (2012). Absence of consequential changes in physiological, thermal and subjective responses from wearing a surgical mask. *Respiratory Physiology & Neurobiology* 181(1), 29–35. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resp.2012.01.010>
- [1130] Roberge RJ, Coca A, Williams WJ, ... Palmiero AJ (2010). Physiological impact of the N95 filtering facepiece respirator on healthcare workers. *Respiratory Care* 55(5), 569–577. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/20420727>
- [1131] Pifarré F, Zabala DD, Grazioli G, Maura I de Y i (2020). COVID-19 and mask in sports. *Apunts Sports Medicine* 55(208), 143–145. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apunsm.2020.06.002>
- [1132] Rebmann T, Carrico R, Wang J (2013). Physiologic and other effects and compliance with long-term respirator use among medical intensive care unit nurses. *American Journal of Infection Control* 41(12), 1218–1223. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ajic.2013.02.017>
- [1133] Roeckner JT, Krstić N, Sipe BH, Običan SG (2020). N95 filtering facepiece respirator use during pregnancy: A systematic review. *American Journal of Perinatology* 37(10), 995–1001. <https://doi.org/10.1055/s-0040-1712475>
- [1134] Georgi C, Haase-Fielitz A, Meretz D, ... Butter C (2020). The impact of commonly-worn face masks on physiological parameters and on discomfort during standard work-related physical effort. *Deutsches Ärzteblatt Online* 117, 674–675. <https://doi.org/10.3238/arztebl.2020.0674>
- [1135] Roberge RJ, Kim J-H, Powell JB (2014). N95 respirator use during advanced pregnancy. *American Journal of Infection Control* 42(10), 1097–1100. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ajic.2014.06.025>
- [1136] Kyung SY, Kim Y, Hwang H, ... Jeong SH (2020). Risks of N95 face mask use in subjects with COPD. *Respiratory Care* 65(5), 658–664. <https://doi.org/10.4187/respcare.06713>
- [1137] Epstein D, Korytny A, Isenberg Y, ... Miller A (2020). Return to training in the COVID-19 era: The physiological effects of face masks during exercise. *Scandinavian Journal of Medicine & Science in Sports* 31(1), 70–75. <https://doi.org/10.1111/sms.13832>
- [1138] Mo Y, Wei D, Mai Q, ... Tan X (2020). Risk and impact of using mask on COPD patients with acute exacerbation during the COVID-19 outbreak: A retrospective study [Preprint]. *Research Square*. <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-39747/v1>
- [1139] Goh DYT, Mun MW, Lee WLJ, ... Rajgor DD (2019). A randomised clinical trial to evaluate the safety, fit, comfort of a novel N95 mask in children. *Scientific Reports* 9, 18952. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-019-55451-w>

- [1140] Bharatendu C, Ong JJY, Goh Y, ... Sharma VK (2020). Powered air purifying respirator (PAPR) restores the N95 face mask induced cerebral hemodynamic alterations among healthcare workers during COVID-19 outbreak. *Journal of the Neurological Sciences* 417, 117078. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jns.2020.117078>
- [1141] Tong PSY, Kale AS, Ng K, ... Yong EL (2015). Respiratory consequences of N95-type mask usage in pregnant healthcare workers: A controlled clinical study. *Antimicrobial Resistance & Infection Control* 4, 48. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13756-015-0086-z>
- [1142] Liu C, Li G, He Y, ... Ding Y (2020). Effects of wearing masks on human health and comfort during the COVID-19 pandemic. *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science* 531, 012034. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1755-1315/531/1/012034>
- [1143] Beder A, Büyükkoçak Ü, Sabuncuoğlu H, ... Keskil S (2008). Preliminary report on surgical mask induced deoxygenation during major surgery. *Neurocirugía* 19(2), 121–126. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s1130-1473\(08\)70235-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/s1130-1473(08)70235-5)
- [1144] Fikenzler S, Uhe T, Lavall D, ... Laufs U (2020). Effects of surgical and FFP2/N95 face masks on cardiopulmonary exercise capacity. *Clinical Research in Cardiology* 109, 1522–1530. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00392-020-01704-y>
- [1145] Jagim AR, Dominy TA, Camic CL, ... Oliver JM (2018). Acute effects of the elevation training mask on strength performance in recreational weight lifters. *Journal of Strength and Conditioning Research* 32(2), 482–489. <https://doi.org/10.1519/jsc.0000000000002308>
- [1146] Porcari JP, Probst L, Forrester K, ... Schmidt K (2016). Effect of wearing the elevation training mask on aerobic capacity, lung function, and hematological variables. *Journal of Sports Science and Medicine* 15(2), 379–386. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/27274679>
- [1147] Kao T-W, Huang K-C, Huang Y-L, ... Wu M-S (2004). The physiological impact of wearing an N95 mask during hemodialysis as a precaution against SARS in patients with end-stage renal disease. *Journal of the Formosan Medical Association* 103(8), 624–628. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/15340662>
- [1148] Li Y, Tokura H, Guo Y, ... Newton E (2005). Effects of wearing N95 and surgical facemasks on heart rate, thermal stress and subjective sensations. *International Archives of Occupational and Environmental Health* 78, 501–509. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00420-004-0584-4>
- [1149] Sukul P, Bartels J, Fuchs P, ... Miekisch W (2021). Adverse effects of COVID-protective face-masks and wearing durations onto respiratory-haemodynamic physiology and exhaled breath constituents [Preprint]. *Research Square*. <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-930030/v1>
- [1150] Lee HP, Wang DY (2011). Objective assessment of increase in breathing resistance of N95 respirators on human subjects. *The Annals of Occupational Hygiene* 55(8), 917–921. <https://doi.org/10.1093/annhyg/mer065>

- [1151] Roberge RJ, Bayer E, Powell JB, ... Benson SM (2010). Effect of exhaled moisture on breathing resistance of N95 filtering facepiece respirators. *The Annals of Occupational Hygiene* 54(6), 671–677. <https://doi.org/10.1093/annhyg/meq042>
- [1152] Matusiak Ł, Szepietowska M, Krajewski P, ... Szepietowski JC (2020). Inconveniences due to the use of face masks during the COVID-19 pandemic: A survey study of 876 young people. *Dermatologic Therapy* 33(4), e13567. <https://doi.org/10.1111/dth.13567>
- [1153] Johnson AT (2016). Respirator masks protect health but impact performance: A review. *Journal of Biological Engineering* 10, 4. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13036-016-0025-4>
- [1154] Rosner E (2020) Adverse effects of prolonged mask use among healthcare professionals during COVID-19. *Journal of Infectious Diseases and Epidemiology* 6, 130. <https://doi.org/10.23937/2474-3658/1510130>
- [1155] Azuma K, Kagi N, Yanagi U, Osawa H (2018). Effects of low-level inhalation exposure to carbon dioxide in indoor environments: A short review on human health and psychomotor performance. *Environment International* 121(1), 51–56. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2018.08.059>
- [1156] Drechsler M, Morris J (2021). Carbon dioxide narcosis. *StatPearls*. Treasure Island, FL: StatPearls Publishing. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/31869084>
- [1157] Fothergill DM, Hedges D, Morrison JB (1991). Effects of CO₂ and N₂ partial pressures on cognitive and psychomotor performance. *Undersea Biomedical Research* 18(1), 1–19. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/1902340>
- [1158] Noble J, Jones JG, Davis EJ (1993). Cognitive function during moderate hypoxaemia. *Anaesthesia and Intensive Care* 21(2), 180–184. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0310057x9302100208>
- [1159] Ong JJY, Bharatendu C, Goh Y, ... Sharma VK (2020). Headaches associated with personal protective equipment: A cross-sectional study among frontline healthcare workers during COVID-19. *Headache* 60(5), 864–877. <https://doi.org/10.1111/head.13811>
- [1160] Ramirez-Moreno JM, Ceberino D, Gonzalez Plata A, ... Constantino AB (2020). Mask-associated ‘de novo’ headache in healthcare workers during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Occupational and Environmental Medicine* 78, 548–554. <https://doi.org/10.1136/oemed-2020-106956>
- [1161] Lim ECH, Seet RCS, Lee K-H, ... Ong BKC (2006). Headaches and the N95 face-mask amongst healthcare providers. *Acta Neurologica Scandinavica* 113(3), 199–202. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1600-0404.2005.00560.x>
- [1162] Johnson AT, Scott WH, Lausted CG, ... Johnson MM (2000). Effect of external dead volume on performance while wearing a respirator. *AIHAJ* 61(5), 678–684. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15298660008984577>
- [1163] Shenal BV, Radonovich LJ Jr., Cheng J, ... Bender BS (2012). Discomfort and exertion associated with prolonged wear of respiratory protection in a health care setting. *Journal of Occupational and Environmental Hygiene* 9(1), 59–64. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15459624.2012.635133>

- [1164] Johnson AT, Scott WH, Phelps SJ, ... Koh FC (2005). How is respirator comfort affected by respiratory resistance? *Journal of the International Society for Respiratory Protection* 22, 38.
- [1165] Koh FC, Johnson AT, Scott WH, ... Cattungal S (2006). The correlation between personality type and performance time while wearing a respirator. *Journal of Occupational and Environmental Hygiene* 3(6), 317–322. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15459620600691264>
- [1166] Custodis F, Schirmer SH, Baumhäkel M, ... Laufs U (2010). Vascular pathophysiology in response to increased heart rate. *Journal of the American College of Cardiology* 56(24), 1973–1983. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jacc.2010.09.014>
- [1167] Russo MA, Santarelli DM, O'Rourke D (2017). The physiological effects of slow breathing in the healthy human. *Breathe* 13(4), 298–309. <https://doi.org/10.1183/20734735.009817>
- [1168] Nuckowska MK, Gruszecki M, Kot J, ... Winklewski PJ (2019). Impact of slow breathing on the blood pressure and subarachnoid space width oscillations in humans. *Scientific Reports* 9, 6232. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-019-42552-9>
- [1169] Jamjoom A, Nikkar-Esfahani A, Fitzgerald J (2009). Operating theatre related syncope in medical students: A cross sectional study. *BMC Medical Education* 9, 14. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1472-6920-9-14>
- [1170] Prousa D (2020). Studie zu psychischen und psychovegetativen Beschwerden mit den aktuellen Mund-Nasenschutz-Verordnungen [Preprint]. *PsychArchives*. <https://doi.org/10.23668/PSYCHARCHIVES.3135>
- [1171] Ryan RM, Deci EL (2008). Self-determination theory and the role of basic psychological needs in personality and the organization of behavior. In: OP John, RW Robins, LA Pervin (Eds.), *Handbook of Personality: Theory and Research*, 3rd ed. New York, NY: The Guilford Press, 654–678. <https://psycnet.apa.org/record/2008-11667-026>
- [1172] Kent JM, Papp LA, Martinez JM, ... Gorman JM (2001). Specificity of panic response to CO₂ inhalation in panic disorder: A comparison with major depression and premenstrual dysphoric disorder. *American Journal of Psychiatry* 158(1), 58–67. <https://doi.org/10.1176/appi.ajp.158.1.58>
- [1173] Morris LS, McCall JG, Charney DS, Murrough JW (2020). The role of the locus coeruleus in the generation of pathological anxiety. *Brain and Neuroscience Advances* 4, 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2398212820930321>
- [1174] Gorman JM, Askanazi J, Liebowitz MR, ... Klein DF (1984). Response to hyperventilation in a group of patients with panic disorder. *American Journal of Psychiatry* 141(7), 857–861. <https://doi.org/10.1176/ajp.141.7.857>
- [1175] Rains SA (2012). The nature of psychological reactance revisited: A meta-analytic review. *Human Communication Research* 39(1), 47–73. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-2958.2012.01443.x>
- [1176] Badri FMA (2017). Surgical mask contact dermatitis and epidemiology of contact dermatitis in healthcare workers. *Current Allergy & Clinical Immunology* 30(1), 183–188. <https://hdl.handle.net/10520/EJC-c3ca4ee66>

- [1177] Palmiero AJ, Symons D, Morgan JW III, Shaffer RE (2016). Speech intelligibility assessment of protective facemasks and air-purifying respirators. *Journal of Occupational and Environmental Hygiene* 13(12), 960–968. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15459624.2016.1200723>
- [1178] Heider CA, Álvarez ML, Fuentes-López E, ... Napolitano CA (2020). Prevalence of voice disorders in healthcare workers in the universal masking COVID-19 era. *The Laryngoscope* 131(4), E1227–E1233. <https://doi.org/10.1002/lary.29172>
- [1179] Mendel LL, Gardino JA, Atcherson SR (2008). Speech understanding using surgical masks: A problem in health care? *Journal of the American Academy of Audiology* 19(09), 686–695. <https://doi.org/10.3766/jaaa.19.9.4>
- [1180] Ocansey S, Akoto Y, Abraham C, ... Ntodie M (2021). Face masks may cause visual symptoms and artifacts in ophthalmic patients [Preprint]. *Research Square*. <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-427405/v1>
- [1181] Scarano A, Inchingolo F, Lorusso F (2020). Facial skin temperature and discomfort when wearing protective face masks: Thermal infrared imaging evaluation and hands moving the mask. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* 17(13), 4624. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17134624>
- [1182] Luksamijarulkul P, Aiempradit N, Vatanasomboon P (2014). Microbial contamination on used surgical masks among hospital personnel and microbial air quality in their working wards: A hospital in Bangkok. *Oman Medical Journal* 29(5), 346–350. <https://doi.org/10.5001/omj.2014.92>
- [1183] Chughtai AA, Stelzer-Braid S, Rawlinson W, ... MacIntyre CR (2019). Contamination by respiratory viruses on outer surface of medical masks used by hospital healthcare workers. *BMC Infectious Diseases* 19, 491. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12879-019-4109-x>
- [1184] Monalisa AC, Padma KB, Manjunath K, ... Varsha D (2017). Microbial contamination of the mouth masks used by post-graduate students in a private dental institution: An in-vitro study. *IOSR Journal of Dental and Medical Sciences* 16(5, IV), 61–67. <https://doi.org/10.9790/0853-1605046167>
- [1185] Zhiqing L, Yongyun C, Wenxiang C, ... Zanjing Z (2018). Surgical masks as source of bacterial contamination during operative procedures. *Journal of Orthopaedic Translation* 14, 57–62. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jot.2018.06.002>
- [1186] Asadi S, Cappa CD, Barreda S, ... Ristenpart WD (2020). Efficacy of masks and face coverings in controlling outward aerosol particle emission from expiratory activities. *Scientific Reports* 10, 15665. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-020-72798-7>
- [1187] MacIntyre CR, Seale H, Dung TC, ... Wang Q (2015). A cluster randomised trial of cloth masks compared with medical masks in healthcare workers. *BMJ Open* 5, e006577. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2014-006577>
- [1188] MacIntyre CR, Chughtai AA (2015). Facemasks for the prevention of infection in healthcare and community settings. *BMJ* 350, h694. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.h694>

- [1189] MacIntyre CR, Wang Q, Seale H, ... Dwyer DE (2013). A randomized clinical trial of three options for N95 respirators and medical masks in health workers. *American Journal of Respiratory and Critical Care Medicine* 187(9), 960–966. <https://doi.org/10.1164/rccm.201207-1164oc>
- [1190] Gasparino RC, Lima MHM, Souza Oliveira-Kumakura AR, ... Antunes IR (2020). Prophylactic dressings in the prevention of pressure ulcer related to the use of personal protective equipment by health professionals facing the COVID-19 pandemic: A randomized clinical trial. *Wound Repair and Regeneration* 29(1), 183–188. <https://doi.org/10.1111/wrr.12877>
- [1191] Foo CCI, Goon ATJ, Leow Y-H, Goh C-L (2006). Adverse skin reactions to personal protective equipment against severe acute respiratory syndrome? A descriptive study in Singapore. *Contact Dermatitis* 55(5), 291–294. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1600-0536.2006.00953.x>
- [1192] Hua W, Zuo Y, Wan R, ... Li L (2020). Short-term skin reactions following use of N95 respirators and medical masks. *Contact Dermatitis* 83(2), 115–121. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cod.13601>
- [1193] Techasatian L, Lebsing S, Uppala R, ... Kosalaraksa P (2020). The effects of the face mask on the skin underneath: A prospective survey during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Journal of Primary Care & Community Health* 11, 215013272096616. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2150132720966167>
- [1194] Lan J, Song Z, Miao X, ... Tao J (2020). Skin damage among health care workers managing coronavirus disease-2019. *Journal of the American Academy of Dermatology* 82(5), 1215–1216. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaad.2020.03.014>
- [1195] Szepietowski J, Matusiak Ł, Szepietowska M, ... Białynicki-Birula R (2020). Face mask-induced itch: A self-questionnaire study of 2,315 responders during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Acta Dermato-Venereologica* 100, adv00152. <https://doi.org/10.2340/00015555-3536>
- [1196] Tasic-Kostov M, Martinović M, Ilic D, Cvetkovic M (2021). Cotton versus medical face mask influence on skin characteristics during COVID-19 pandemic: A short-term study. *Skin Research and Technology*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1111/srt.13091>
- [1197] Yaneer B-Y (2020, April 3). Don't rebreath the coronavirus: New mask designs. *New England Complex Systems Institute*. <https://necsi.edu/dont-rebreath-the-coronavirus-new-mask-designs>
- [1198] Darlenski R, Tsankov N (2020). COVID-19 pandemic and the skin: What should dermatologists know? *Clinics in Dermatology* 38(6), 85–787. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clindermatol.2020.03.012>
- [1199] Klimek L, Huppertz T, Alali A, ... Hagemann J (2020). A new form of irritant rhinitis to filtering facepiece particle (FFP) masks (FFP2/N95/KN95 respirators) during COVID-19 pandemic. *World Allergy Organization Journal* 13(10), 100474. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.waojou.2020.100474>
- [1200] Achanta S, Sasidharan S, Majji D, Uppala D (2021). “Mask mouth” during COVID-19 pandemic: A myth or a truth. *International Journal of Medical and Dental Research* 1(2), 56–63. <https://ijmadr.com/view-article/23>

- [1201] Muley P (2020, August 26). ‘Mask mouth’: A novel threat to oral health in the COVID era. *Dental Tribune Southeast Asia*. <https://in.dental-tribune.com/news/mask-mouth-a-novel-threat-to-oral-health-in-the-covid-era>
- [1202] Wong CKM, Yip BHK, Mercer S, ... Wong SY (2013). Effect of facemasks on empathy and relational continuity: A randomised controlled trial in primary care. *BMC Family Practice* 14, 200. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2296-14-200>
- [1203] Smart NR, Horwell CJ, Smart TS, Galea KS (2020). Assessment of the wearability of facemasks against air pollution in primary school-aged children in London. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* 17(11), 3935. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17113935>
- [1204] Forgie SE, Reitsma J, Spady D, ... Stobart K (2009). The “fear factor” for surgical masks and face shields, as perceived by children and their parents. *Pediatrics* 124(4), e777–e781. <https://doi.org/10.1542/peds.2008-3709>
- [1205] Neilson S (2016). The surgical mask is a bad fit for risk reduction. *Canadian Medical Association Journal* 188(8), 606–607. <https://doi.org/10.1503/cmaj.151236>
- [1206] Schwarz S, Jenetzky E, Krafft H, ... Martin D (2021). Coronakinderstudien „Co-Ki“: Erste Ergebnisse eines deutschlandweiten Registers zur Mund-Nasen-Bedeckung (Maske) bei Kindern. *Monatsschrift Kinderheilkunde* 169, 353–365. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00112-021-01133-9>
- [1207] Zoccal DB, Furuya WI, Bassi M, ... Colombari E (2014). The nucleus of the solitary tract and the coordination of respiratory and sympathetic activities. *Frontiers in Physiology* 5, 238. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fphys.2014.00238>
- [1208] Walach H, Weigl R, Prentice J, ... Hockertz S (2021). Experimental assessment of carbon dioxide content in inhaled air with or without face masks in healthy children: A randomized clinical trial [Retracted]. *JAMA Pediatrics*. Published online June 30, 2021. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jamapediatrics.2021.2659>
- [1209] Christakis D, Fontanarosa PB (2021). Notice of retraction: Walach H, et al. Experimental assessment of carbon dioxide content in inhaled air with or without face masks in healthy children: A randomized clinical trial. *JAMA Pediatr*. Published online June 30, 2021. *JAMA Pediatrics* 175(9), e213252. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jamapediatrics.2021.3252>
- [1210] Freiberg A, Horvath K, Hahne TM, ... Seidler A (2021). Beeinflussung der psychosozialen Entwicklung von Kindern und Jugendlichen durch das Tragen von Gesichtsmasken im öffentlichen Raum zur Prävention von Infektionskrankheiten: Ein systematischer Review. *Bundesgesundheitsblatt – Gesundheitsforschung – Gesundheitsschutz*. Online ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00103-021-03443-5>
- [1211] Allison MA, Guest-Warnick G, Nelson D, ... Byington CL (2010). Feasibility of elementary school children’s use of hand gel and facemasks during influenza season. *Influenza and Other Respiratory Viruses* 4(4), 223–229. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1750-2659.2010.00142.x>

- [1212] Coniam D (2005). The impact of wearing a face mask in a high-stakes oral examination: An exploratory post-SARS study in Hong Kong. *Language Assessment Quarterly* 2(4), 235–261. https://doi.org/10.1207/s15434311laq0204_1
- [1213] Roberson D, Kikutani M, Döge P, ... Majid A (2012). Shades of emotion: What the addition of sunglasses or masks to faces reveals about the development of facial expression processing. *Cognition* 125(2), 195–206. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cognition.2012.06.018>
- [1214] Rao N (2006). SARS, preschool routines and children's behaviour: Observations from preschools in Hong Kong. *International Journal of Early Childhood* 38, 11–22. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF03168205>
- [1215] Sim S, Moey K, Tan N (2014). The use of facemasks to prevent respiratory infection: A literature review in the context of the Health Belief Model. *Singapore Medical Journal* 55(3), 160–167. <https://doi.org/10.11622/smedj.2014037>
- [1216] Singh L, Tan A, Quinn PC (2021). Infants recognize words spoken through opaque masks but not through clear masks. *Developmental Science* 24(6), e13117. <https://doi.org/10.1111/desc.13117>
- [1217] Stajduhar A, Ganel T, Avidan G, ... Freud E (2021). Face masks disrupt holistic processing and face perception in school-age children [Preprint]. *PsyArXiv*. <https://doi.org/10.31234/osf.io/fygiq>
- [1218] Gori M, Schiatti L, Amadeo MB (2021). Masking emotions: Face masks impair how we read emotions. *Frontiers in Psychology* 12, 669432. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.669432>
- [1219] Mickells GE, Figueroa J, West KW, ... McElhanon BO (2021). Adherence to masking requirement during the COVID-19 pandemic by early elementary school children. *Journal of School Health* 91(7), 555–561. <https://doi.org/10.1111/josh.13033>
- [1220] Eigsti I-M, de Marchena AB, Schuh JM, Kelley E (2011). Language acquisition in autism spectrum disorders: A developmental review. *Research in Autism Spectrum Disorders* 5(2), 681–691. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rasd.2010.09.001>
- [1221] Vaiouli P, Andreou G (2017). Communication and language development of young children with autism: A review of research in music. *Communication Disorders Quarterly* 39(2), 323–329. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1525740117705117>
- [1222] Magiati I, Tay XW, Howlin P (2014). Cognitive, language, social and behavioural outcomes in adults with autism spectrum disorders: A systematic review of longitudinal follow-up studies in adulthood. *Clinical Psychology Review* 34(1), 73–86. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cpr.2013.11.002>
- [1223] Andreou M, Skrimpa V (2020). Theory of mind deficits and neurophysiological operations in autism spectrum disorders: A review. *Brain Sciences* 10(6), 393. <https://doi.org/10.3390/brainsci10060393>
- [1224] Anonymous (2004). Zakon o zaštiti prava pacijenata. *Narodne novine* 169, 2953. <https://narodne-novine.nn.hr/eli/sluzbeni/2004/169/2953>

- [1225] Jing JLJ, Pei Yi T, Bose RJC, ... Madheswaran T (2020). Hand sanitizers: A review on formulation aspects, adverse effects, and regulations. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* 17(9), 3326. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17093326>
- [1226] Malabadi RB, Kolkar KP, Meti NT, Chalannavar RK (2021). Role of plant based hand sanitizers during the recent outbreak of coronavirus (SARS-CoV-2) disease (Covid-19). *Significances of Bioengineering & Biosciences* 5(1), 000605. <https://doi.org/10.31031/SBB.2021.05.000605>
- [1227] Ale IS, Maibach HI (2014). Irritant contact dermatitis. *Reviews on Environmental Health* 29(3), 195–206. <https://doi.org/10.1515/reveh-2014-0060>
- [1228] Wilhelm K-P (1996). Prevention of surfactant-induced irritant contact dermatitis. *Current Problems in Dermatology* 25, 77–85. <https://doi.org/10.1159/000425517>
- [1229] Samuel E, Babu A, Arjunan S, Mahanty B (2021). Unravelling the enigma of hand sanitizer in COVID-19: A bibliometric analysis of related publications over the year [Preprint]. *Research Square*. <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-526772/v1>
- [1230] Guin JD, Goodman J (2001). Contact urticaria from benzyl alcohol presenting as intolerance to saline soaks. *Contact Dermatitis* 45(3), 182–183. <https://doi.org/10.1034/j.1600-0536.2001.045003182.x>
- [1231] de Groot AC (1987). Contact allergy to cosmetics: Causative ingredients. *Contact Dermatitis* 17(1), 26–34. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1600-0536.1987.tb02640.x>
- [1232] Podda M, Zollner T, Grundmann-Kollmann M, ... Boehncke W-H (1999). Allergic contact dermatitis from benzyl alcohol during topical antimycotic treatment. *Contact Dermatitis* 41(5), 302–303. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1600-0536.1999.tb06175.x>
- [1233] Misteli H (2009). Surgical glove perforation and the risk of surgical site infection. *Archives of Surgery* 144(6), 553–558. <https://doi.org/10.1001/archsurg.2009.60>
- [1234] Larson EL, Norton Hughes CA, Pyrek JD, ... Bartkus JM (1998). Changes in bacterial flora associated with skin damage on hands of health care personnel. *American Journal of Infection Control* 26(5), 513–521. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0196-6553\(98\)70025-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0196-6553(98)70025-2)
- [1235] Löffler H, Kampf G, Schmermund D, Maibach HI (2007). How irritant is alcohol? *British Journal of Dermatology* 157(1), 74–81. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2133.2007.07944.x>
- [1236] Graham M, Nixon R, Burrell LJ, ... Grayson ML (2005). Low rates of cutaneous adverse reactions to alcohol-based hand hygiene solution during prolonged use in a large teaching hospital. *Antimicrobial Agents and Chemotherapy* 49(10), 4404–4405. <https://doi.org/10.1128/aac.49.10.4404-4405.2005>
- [1237] Angelova-Fischer I, Dapic I, Hoek A, ... Kezic S (2014). Skin barrier integrity and natural moisturising factor levels after cumulative dermal exposure to alkaline agents in atopic dermatitis. *Acta Dermato-Venereologica* 94(6), 640–644. <https://doi.org/10.2340/00015555-1815>

- [1238] Emilson A, Lindberg M, Forslind B (1993). The temperature effect on in vitro penetration of sodium lauryl sulfate and nickel chloride through human skin. *Acta Dermato-Venereologica* 73(3), 203–207. <https://doi.org/10.2340/0001555573203207>
- [1239] Ohlenschlaeger J, Friberg J, Ramsing D, Agner T (1996). Temperature dependency of skin susceptibility to water and detergents. *Acta Dermato-Venereologica* 76(4), 274–276. <https://doi.org/10.2340/0001555576274276>
- [1240] Cutuli MA, Guarnieri A, Pietrangelo L, ... Petronio G (2021). Potential mucosal irritation discrimination of surface disinfectants employed against SARS-CoV-2 by *Limacus flavus* slug mucosal irritation assay. *Biomedicines* 9(4), 424. <https://doi.org/10.3390/biomedicines9040424>
- [1241] Lachenmeier DW (2021). Antiseptic drugs and disinfectants with special scrutiny of COVID-19 pandemic related side effects. *Side Effects of Drugs Annual* 43, 275–284. <https://doi.org/10.1016/bs.seda.2021.03.001>
- [1242] Babić Ž, Turk R, Macan J (2020). Toxicological aspects of increased use of surface and hand disinfectants in Croatia during the COVID-19 pandemic: A preliminary report. *Arhiv za higijenu rada i toksikologiju* 71(3), 261–264. <https://doi.org/10.2478/aiht-2020-71-3470>
- [1243] Milella MS, Boldrini P, Vivino G, Grassi MC (2021). How COVID-19 lockdown in Italy has affected type of calls and management of toxic exposures: A retrospective analysis of a poison control center database from March 2020 to May 2020. *Journal of Medical Toxicology* 17(3), 250–256. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13181-021-00839-2>
- [1244] Mahmoud NF, Al-Mazroua MK, Afify MM (2021). Toxicology practice during COVID-19 pandemic – Experience of the Dammam Poison Control Center: Eastern Province, Saudi Arabia. *International Journal of Toxicology* 40(4), 388–394. <https://doi.org/10.1177/10915818211017128>
- [1245] Pereska Z, Simonovska N, Babulovska A, ... Kostadinovski K (2021). Acute severe poisoning with disinfectant in senior aged patient-case report and overview of literature considering age influence on treatment decision in alcohol-based intoxications. *SAGE Open Medical Case Reports* 9, 1–6. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2050313x211047717>
- [1246] Alizadeh A, Moazen N, Pourbadakhshan N, Mostafazadeh B (2021). The outcomes of accidental ingestion of hand sanitizer. *International Journal of Medical Toxicology and Forensic Medicine* 11(3), 34168–34168. <https://doi.org/10.32598/ijmtfm.v11i3.34168>
- [1247] Becker CU, Salomão G, Serapião M, ... Belfort Junior R (2021). Letter to the editor: Ocular surface injury following alcohol-based hand sanitizer use in Covid-19 prevention. *Arquivos Brasileiros de oftalmologia* 84(4), 404–405. <https://doi.org/10.5935/0004-2749.202100105>
- [1248] Beiu C, Mihai M, Popa L, ... Popescu MN (2020). Frequent hand washing for COVID-19 prevention can cause hand dermatitis: Management tips. *Cureus* 12(4), e7506. <https://doi.org/10.7759/cureus.7506>
- [1249] Vaccine Adverse Event Reporting System (2021, December 3). <https://vaers.hhs.gov>